

**Developing a Model to Predict Critical Failure Factors of Small
and Medium-Sized Enterprises:**

An Empirical Study of the UK Fast Food Retail Industry.

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Dedication

This thesis is dedicated to my parents, Allah Dita and Khursheed Begum with sincere love and respect for supporting me in my academic journey. I appreciate their love and prayers that helped me to complete this thesis. I especially want to dedicate this thesis to my mother who eagerly wanted me to complete my thesis, however, passed away last year. I appreciate all her efforts, which motivated me throughout my thesis. Without her continuous support, I would not have been devoted my time to my study and made progress in completing my thesis therefore, I specifically want to dedicate this work to her.

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Abstract

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) contribute to accelerating economic development, jobs creation, development, and strengthening economies in developing and developed countries. However, regardless of the country and industry, SMEs face similar impediments that influence their performance and survival rate. Literature suggests that SMEs face a high failure rate all over the world. Likewise, the failure rate is high in the UK therefore, this area of research needs further consideration, and no guidelines can be developed without identification of the roots for business failure. This research aims to identify the main causes of failure factors in the UK fast food retail stores, develop a model to predict failure, and propose a framework or recommendation to reduce the failure. this research is expected to enhance the business failure knowledge, solve a problem, contribute to SMEs failure literature, enhance the research design for SMEs failure research, offer an academic foundation to decision-makers, and provide an opportunity to academics to debate and evaluate SMEs failure factors in the UK fast-food retail sector. The present research contributes to enhance SMEs performance by identifying the factors linked to the SMEs performance and offers guidelines on how to enhance the chances of business success based on recommendations from successful and failed business owners.

Success and failure were defined to measure the performance of SMEs. According to the definition employed in present research a business is considered failed if ceases to trade within three years and considered successful if continued to trade for more than three years.

The survey was used to collect both types of data, and qualitative data provided the supporting role. The concurrent embedded mixed-method strategy is employed in this research. Questionnaires formed on the google forum were distributed by email and post to successful and unsuccessful SMEs owners to collect quantitative and qualitative data. First, descriptive data analysis was performed to differentiate the characteristics of entrepreneurs and their businesses. Next, exploratory factor analysis was performed to recognize the structure and relationship amongst the variables. Logistic regression analysis was executed to develop a prediction model for SMEs' success and failure and test the hypothesis. The main finding specifies that the model encompassing all the independent variables is statistically significant. The logistic regression analysis outcome reveals that seven factors are statistically significant in the model; these are the type of ownership, owner's experience, poor owner skills, business planning, business location, marketing and management, and intensity of competition. The

mean score result shows that the enterprise factors are the first, environmental factors are the second, and entrepreneurial factors are the third most important factors that affect the business performance.

Similarly, thematic analysis was performed to analyse the three open-ended questions. The results of qualitative data further support the quantitative data and suggest that the enterprise factors are the most important factors that play a crucial role in business performance. There are numerous failure factors in the literature, and it was not possible to include all those factors in one study due to limited time and resources therefore, to identify any missing failure factors from the model an open-ended question was added in the questionnaire to overcome this limitation. The results of the thematic analysis show that some important failure factors not included in this study were also identified. These factors include poor customer service and product quality, pandemic, poor inventory management, legal issues, neglecting home delivery, supplier issues, partnership issue, poor use of technology, and neglecting third-party applications. The last open-ended question results show that the successful and failed business owners recommended that managing these factors can help a business to minimize the risk of failure. These findings can be useful in other alike settings such as other retail sectors and European countries.

Based on logistic regression analysis and recommendations results focusing on owners experience in the relevant field, owners skills, business planning, marketing, and advertisement, high-quality product and services, business location, business growth strategies, financial support, Inventory management, human resource management, business partnership issues, home delivery services, legal compliance, better use of technology, partnering with third-party online applications and managing competition can assist businesses to increase the chances of business success.

Chapter 1: Introduction

It's recognized across the world that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) benefit employment, economy, and cultural diversity in different countries. The researchers, policymakers, international organisations, and investors' focus has been increased on SMEs performance due to its reputation and consequently, becomes the area of interest for researchers (Gherghina *et al.*, 2020; Meghana *et al.*, 2011).

Given this, the present research pursues to recognise the critical failure factors for SMEs in the UK fast food retail industry. The present study focused on SMEs from the fast-food industry in the UK to get in-depth knowledge of failure factors and encapsulate three types of broad failure factors entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors. The present study intends to develop a prediction model that evaluates the odds of business failure in the UK and offers recommendations to increase the chances of business success.

The objective of this chapter is to offer a research overview, provide the research problem, discuss research questions and objectives, and in the end explain the research contributions.

1. Background

SMEs have an essential part to play in accelerating economic growth, creating jobs, developing, and strengthening economies in developing and developed countries (Gherghina *et al.*, 2020; Robson *et al.*, 2008; Philip, 2011; Halabi and Lussier, 2014). SMEs supports economic growth, upsurge the wealth for a country, support swift industrialization, and assist in driving innovation and research, and development (Surya *et al.*, 2021; Franco and Haase, 2010; Harris and Gibson, 2006; Arando *et al.*, 2009; Caca, 2010; Smallbone *et al.*, 2010). In addition, SMEs does not only aid in the development and economic growth but are also considered an engine for recovery during the recession (Cabinet Office, 2013; Unger *et al.*, 2011; Holmes *et al.*, 2010).

The facts and figures show that employment is one of the most crucial benefits SMEs offer to the economy. The main driving factor for employment creation is an expansion of the existing businesses as compared to creating new businesses which further increases their significance (Surya *et al.*, 2021; Lussier, 2010; Amoros *et al.*, 2011).

SMEs contribute to constructing the major share of enterprises around the globe and contribute tremendously to distributing goods and services, offering facilities to the customers, developing an improved living standard, and improving the gross domestic product (Surya *et*

al., 2021; Morrison *et al.*, 2003). There were 6 million SMEs in the UK which makes 99% of the total proportion of UK business (Ward, 2021). Each year the proportion of SMEs upsurges by an average of 3 percent in the UK. Similarly, from the period of 2000 to 2016 the total number of SMEs increased by 64% up to 2.2 million (Rhodes, 2017).

In 2016, the total number of micro-businesses was 5.5 million with 0-9 workers and it makes up 96% of all the businesses. Even though, most of the businesses in the UK consist of small businesses, however, these businesses contribute 37% to employment (Rhodes, 2017). Large businesses produce 40% employment, have more than 250 employees, and contribute 0.1% of total businesses as shown in the chart below (Rhodes, 2017).

Figure 1.1: Business Population Estimates, 2017 (Rhodes, 2017)

Similarly, SMEs create 60% of jobs with a shared annual turnover of £1.9 trillion which is almost 51% turnover of the whole private sector in the UK (Gov, 2017). SMEs contribute expressively to the UK, s GDP.

1.2 Research Problem

SMEs are considered vital for any country, however; different hindrances influence their survival rate and performance. There are several obstacles and weaknesses of SMEs along with certain strengths as compared to large organisations. The stats show that the failure rate is significantly high in SMEs regardless of country and industry due to which focus of academia

and professionals has increased in this area since last several years (Abisuga, 2019; Saleh, 2016; Ropega, 2011; Bates, 2005; Hayward *et al.*, 2006; Lampadarijos, 2015; Bennet, 2016).

According to Turner and Endres (2017), the failure rate of small businesses is more than 50 percent within the first five years. Furthermore, the literature suggests that there is a high SME failure rate all over the world with a failure rate of 60% in Malaysia and 23% in Australia (Marmaya, Razak, Wee, Karim, & Ridzuan, 2018; Ahmad and Seet, 2009).

Similarly, the UK National Statistics (2017) states that the business birth rate increased from 14.3% to 14.6%, the total number of businesses increased from 383,000 to 414,000 between 2015 and 2016. However, along with the rise in the number of births rate the death rate also increased to 328,000 in 2016 as compared to 283,000 in 2015. This shows an increase of 11.6% in the failure rate (See figure 1.2). Furthermore, between 2016 to 2017 the failure rate surged by 12.2 percent from 288,000 to 357,000 in the UK (ONS, 2017).

Figure 1.2: Birth and death rates of businesses in the UK (Wilson, 2017)

Even though, the UK turned into a harbour for embracing entrepreneurial skill and spirits despite those 8 businesses out of 10 fails within their first year of operations (Wilson, 2017). The start-up survival rate in London is underprivileged, only 50.1% of businesses could survive for the first three years which is 3.6% lower than the national average (Nilsson, 2017). The economist John Maynard Keynes is cited: “In the long run we are all dead”. Somewhat, it can be seen in businesses too as after a certain long time they all die or fail. However, it’s a sign of concern that most businesses fail in the early stage and the start-up failure rate in the first three years is alarmingly high in the UK.

Therefore, it's evocative to examine the roots of underprivileged performance and failure due to the high proportion of failure rates in UK businesses. As mentioned earlier in detail that SMEs are very crucial for economic growth and assist in enhancing employability hence, there is a need to increase the numeral of successful start-ups and put efforts to minimize the failure rate and bankruptcy (Mujahid *et al.*, 2019; Carter & Auken, 2006). When a business fails or ends up bankrupt then within the business environment it has several negative effects on all stakeholders. Entrepreneurs lose their time, energy, and investment. Customers find it difficult to get products and distribution of specific goods and services interrupts and workers end up unemployed. It does not stop here but the government also loses revenue in the form of taxes, and other fees and expenses which businesses usually pay for operating in a country. In addition, it also affects the living standards of the local community therefore business failure is a serious event (Raj, 2009). So, it's important to find a way to reduce SME failure.

It is difficult to increase the SMEs success rate unless the details of business failures are not examined and understood properly thus, there is a need to research this significant area to identify the main causes of business failure and develop an action plan to reduce the high failure rate (Abisuga-Oyekunle, Patra and Muchie, 2019; Hyder and Lussier, 2016; Lukason and Hoffman 2015; Storey, 1994; Marom and Lussier, 2014). The best motivation to conduct failure factors studies comes from Abdelsamad and Kindling's (1978) statement which proposes that sometimes it is not possible to avoid the failure entirely however, it is likely to lessen the failure rate through identifying the impact or causes of failure and take precautionary actions.

There are numerous critical failure factors (CFFs) found in business literature that tries to explain the different aspects of small business failure. While the standing of these failure factors available in the literature is questionable as the success and failure factors diverge from each industry and country. In other words, one failure factor may have an excessive significance in one industry however, the same factor may have no or less importance in another country or industry (Saleh, 2016; Lampadarios, 2016; Smallbone and Wyer, 2000; Chemagility, 2008; Rauch *et al.*, 2000; Alfaadhel, 2010; Simpson *et al.*, 2012; Lussier and Pfeifer, 2001; Ogundele, 2007).

Therefore, the present research focuses on one specific business sector and the area of interest is identifying failure factors in the retail sector as retail stores have the second-highest failure rate in the UK (Gov.UK, 2018). This is an area with a strong existence in the UK retail sector

and it assists 10% of all businesses. The retail sector alone produces 19% of employment and similarly, in 2017, it contributed 33% to overall turnover (Rhodes, 2017).

The present research further narrows down the focus on the fast-food retail stores excluding (e.g.) other retail sectors grocery stores and supermarkets, general merchandise stores, specialty stores that sell one type of products, non-store retailers, and other industries to better understand the causes of SMEs failure in one specific area of industry. Healy and Mac Con Iomaire (2018) calculated fast-food restaurants and take away failure rates using longitudinal census data and compared the failure rate with other industries. The findings suggest that the failure rate is higher in the restaurant industry is marginally higher than in other industry sectors. To date, a few studies have examined the failure factors for UK fast food retail industry, and even in business literature very limited research is available on a European level (Healy *et al.*, 2018; Hornke, 2012).

In addition, the stats show growth in fast food burger and chicken restaurants, and the estimated value of fast food will reach £7.2 billion an increase of 4.1% in 2018. It is expected that the growth will continue at a slower rate and market forecast to increase by 5% and value would reach £7.6 billion as shown in the figure below (Intel, 2018).

Figure 1.3: Fast Food Market Value (Intel, 2018) Page 1

The forecast shows that there are opportunities for entrepreneurship evolution in this industry, therefore, it provides the grounds for this research to identify the main causes of failure in the UK fast-food retail stores to increase the chances of success.

In addition, it can be noted that this industry contributes heavily to the UK economy and identifying the failure factors could help the economy to grow. A single type of retail store (fast food) was scrutinized as similar factors likely to influence the performance of the business in a specific industry. Fast food retail stores will function within a fundamentally similar financial environment, heavily depends on limited resources, and will deal with similar problems and constraints. Therefore, one of the key contributions of this study is that having identified 'leading indicators' of fast-food failure factors in one sector of retail can also help to identify the failure factors in other sectors of retail.

It is clear the UK fast food is a significant industry that contributes a lot to the economy however, there is the absence of adequate research on small business failure. Therefore, a rich and precise research gap has been recognized. It is apparent to conduct further empirical research to identify failure factors of the UK fast food retail stores. Consequently, this research focused on one specific industry to make the research more specific. The framework to identify failure factors in fast food retail would also help in identifying the failure factors in other retail sectors.

The product or services which satisfy the customer needs are also very important in the performance of a business. Identifying the product or services gap and serving the segment that existing businesses are not serving can be fundamental in the success of a business. For example, in recent years the veganism has been growing, and all major fast-food restaurants are offering new vegan products. According to Statista (2022) the share of vegan in different age group is increasing in the UK. Therefore, all the major fast-food restaurants have started offering vegan products to satisfy the customer needs. The new restaurants who serve these market needs creatively have more chances to succeed. Similarly, Deliveroo, Just Eats, and Uber eats, found a gap in the market, and enjoyed a significant growth by serving that gap. It shows that product, services, or creative ideas that serve the need of market can play an important role in the success of a business. However, the present research focus on other aspects of the retail industry which influence the performance of SMEs in the UK fast food industry.

1.3 Research Aim

This research aims to investigate the factors associated with business failure in the UK fast food retail industry and propose a framework or recommendation to avoid failure.

1.4 Research Questions and Objectives

The researchers seem to disagree on SMEs success or failure factors however, some common factors have been acknowledged based on prior literature that influences the SMEs performance. Previous research suggests that business growth and survival hinge on internal and external factors. These days running a successful business is much more problematic as compared to any other time in recent history. Due to technological advancement, product development, manufacturing innovation rising international rivalry, and changing business regulations the pressure on the management of SMEs and the failure rate in start-ups increased (Lampadarios, 2016). Several theories help in identifying the issues concerning entrepreneurial, managerial principles, and external factors that made up sets of variables required to run a sustainable business.

Literature review indicates that there are several causes of start-up failures which have been classified into three general themes as extracted from different present journal articles which include (1) Entrepreneurial perspective to elucidate start-ups failure, (2) enterprise factors to explain the start-up failures, and (3) environmental factors to explain start-up failure (Lampadarios, 2016; Saleh, 2016; Blackburn, Hart and Wainwright, 2013; Jasra *et al.*, 2011; Rody and Stearns, 2013). This study anticipates uncovering the relationship between these factors and business failures in the UK fast food industry. Most researchers focused on the successful entrepreneur's opinion to identify the factors which influence the performance of a business. However, it can be valuable to compare the opinions of successful and failed entrepreneurs to develop a model to predict failure factors.

In pursuing this line of investigation, the following questions were seen as important.

RQ: What are the critical factors linked with the SMEs failure in the UK fast food retail industry according to the perception of successful and failed entrepreneurs to predict future performance to avoid failure?

The main research question will be answered by answering the following questions.

- 1- What are the critical entrepreneurial factors that predict SMEs failure in the UK fast food industry?
- 2- What are the critical enterprise factors that predict SMEs failure in the UK fast food industry?

- 3- What are the environmental (external) factors that predict SMEs failure in the UK fast food industry?

1.4.1 Research Objectives

1. To critically evaluate entrepreneurial factors, that predict SMEs failure in the UK fast food industry.
2. To analyse the enterprise (internal) factors, that predict SMEs failure in the UK fast food industry.
3. To investigate the environmental (external) factors that predict SMEs failure in the UK fast food industry.

1.5 Significance and Contribution

The present study investigates the critical failure factors (CFFs) in the UK fast food retail industry according to the perception of successful and failed entrepreneurs. This research offers potentially new avenues and compares the opinions of failed and successful entrepreneurs from the fast-food retail industry. The present research will help new entrepreneurs to recognize the business failure factors and better prepare for the challenges to utilize opportunities. In addition, this research focuses on one industry fast food rather than focusing on several industries at the same time since success and failure factors vary in different industries (Saleh, 2016; Lampadarios, 2016).

The literature shows that various research focused on the SMEs success factors in the UK (Eze, Olatunji, Chinedu-Eze and Bello, 2018; Kumar, 2007; Simpson *et al.*, 2004). Similarly, wide literature can be found on SMEs growth issues (Lampadarios, 2016). However, limited research is available on SMEs failure factors in the UK retail industry (Riviezzo *et al.*, 2015). Even though understanding the causes of failure in a start-up is of great significance while limited but growing knowledge base research exists in literature especially on the small business failure domain in the UK (Ihua, 2009). Furthermore, most of the research on business failure was based on the USA context and more research from other countries is mandatory to achieve robust results (Walsh & Cunningham, 2016). Therefore, this research intends to investigate the failure factors in the UK and then recommend the remedies to minimize the risk of failure. This research intends to assist the new businesses and the current entrepreneur to avoid failure.

There are numerous critical failure factors (CFFs) found in business literature that tries to explain the different parts of small business failure. Though, the standing of these failure factors available in the literature is questionable as the success and failure factors diverge from each industry and country. In other words, one failure factor may have an excessive significance in one industry however, the same factor may have no or less importance in another country or industry (Saleh, 2016; Lampadariou, 2016; Chemagility, 2008; Smallbone and Wyer, 2000; Rauch *et al.*, 2000; Alfaadhel, 2010; Lussier and Pfeifer, 2001; Ogundele, 2007). Therefore, it is obvious problem that gave clear direction to the present study. The success and failure factors of small businesses diverge from each industry and country. It urges further to conduct empirical research on each separate industry and in detailed country situations to examine the impact of previously known failure factors. Hence, it is essential to examine the failure factors in a precise industry and country to discover the critical failure factors related to that industry. In this regard, the present study focuses on the failure factors of one specific industry retail instead of focusing on all industries at the same time.

The measure of performance is another theoretical contribution present research adds to SMEs field in the UK fast food industry as different measures of performance can be employed to determine the business success or failure. There are different measures of performance such as increase in number of customers, customers satisfaction, increase in market share, achieving business goals etc. Nevertheless, commonly used measure of performance is profit or loss. However, business owners are reluctant to share their financial information due to their competitive advantage. Therefore, the present research defines the measure of performance based on definition utilised by the other studies such as that of Pretorius (2009) who used different approach than financial measure of performance. In the present research trade duration has been used to measure the performance of a business instead of profit or loss as this definition better fit with research goal. So, the present definition can be utilized as an effective tool to measure business failure or performance in the UK context.

The literature review indicates that not a sole approved list has been developed to reveal the factors linked to SMEs performance. Therefore, the present research integrated and stretched the previous research work related to business performance and developed a model based on the perception of the UK fast food retail owners' which tend to offer new avenues to the research related to business failure factors in the UK market.

As mentioned in the literature review those factors associated with business success and failure vary, the present research has contributed through selecting a group of factors related to the UK retail industry from different models and studies. This study has provided evidence about the interaction amongst entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors and their roles to predict SMEs failure from the UK context. The results of the logistic regression analysis revealed the capability of the model to predict business failure in the UK context and the association between factors and failure. Consequently, present research determines the most important factors related to performance and focuses on entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors.

The present research is the first study that recommends identifying the major failure factors in the UK fast food industry. The literature suggests that most studies concluded on identifying the major performance-related factors. However, the present study after developing a business failure model offer recommendation on how to overcome these challenges and become successful. These recommendations should serve as a framework that helps the new business to launch their business successfully in the UK retail industry. In addition, the model established based on regression analysis is fit to practice in the other retail sectors. The model can also help to identify the failure factors in other similar countries such as the EU and other developed countries which share the same values, culture, and economy.

Likewise, limited research can be found in the UK and Europe related to the SMEs failure therefore, the present study further adds the knowledge relevant to UK fast food retail industry and create a model to predict the SMEs failure.

Another contribution of the present research is the sample of the respondents as they belong to two unlike groups successful business owners and unsuccessful business owners. In the UK context, researchers have not included both sample groups in the one research. However, this research has adopted a different methodology and collected the data from successful business owners and failed business owners in the fast-food retail industry about business failure to compare their views and better understand the problem. Therefore, the sample supported in developing an inclusive opinion related to the business failure in the UK context.

The results of the present study can help policymakers to develop better policies to increase the chances of business success in the retail industry. As SMEs contribute heavily to the economy of any country enhancing the SMEs success rate will help in reducing unimprovement and improving the economy. The results of the study suggest that SMEs in the UK suffer from

over complex regulatory environment which influences the performance of the business. Furthermore, the pandemic has been identified as one of the major factors through qualitative data analysis which caused many businesses to fail. Therefore, policymakers can make rules and policies that favour SMEs in achieving success. This study will further support the stakeholders such as the government, policymakers, entrepreneurs, business owners to develop a better strategy and enhance the decision-making process to improve the success rate or reduce business failure.

Overall, this research is expected to enhance the business failure knowledge, solve a problem, contribute to SMEs failure literature, enhance the research design for SMEs failure research, offer an academic foundation to decision-makers, and provide an opportunity to academics to debate and evaluate SMEs failure factors in the UK fast-food retail sector. The present research contributes by identifying the factors linked to the SMEs performance and offers guidelines on how to enhance the chances of business success and avoid failure based on recommendations from successful and failed business owners.

1.6 Structure of the Thesis

This thesis follows a commonly utilised research structure and consists of six chapters to fulfil the aim and research gap.

Chapter 1 discuss the overview of the research. It starts with an introduction of SMS, highlights the research problem, and discusses it in detail. It also elucidates the research aim, questions, and objectives. In the end, explain the expected contribution and structure of the research.

Chapter 2 explain the importance of SMEs, offer the definitions of SMEs success and failure, discusses the characteristics, and critically evaluates SMEs failure theories. This chapter evaluates the failure factors and categorises them into entrepreneurial enterprise and environmental factors. Lastly, develop hypothesizes and provide the conceptual framework.

Chapter 3 highlights research philosophies, design, strategy, and justifications for employing them. This chapter also discusses the data collection method, and data analysis techniques adopted for the present research. To end, validity, reliability, and ethical considerations are presented.

Chapter 4 explain the data analysis and offer descriptive and inferential results. First, this chapter provides quantitative data analysis results and then presents the qualitative data

analysis. This chapter elaborates on main failure factors based on data analysis in the UK fast food industry and offers recommendations of successful and failed entrepreneurs.

Chapter 5 presents the discussion in detail. This chapter evaluates the research findings back the findings with other theories and research to make an argument in support of an overall conclusion.

Chapter 6 discuss the research process overview, limitation of the research, contribution, implication, and future research.

1.7 Motivation for this Study

The motivation for this study came from the interest of the researcher and a craving for unremitting personal growth. In addition, being involved in an accountancy firm and working as a business consultant has enormously helped in the realisation of this thesis. The job helped in approaching vital people and securing their assistance. The researcher took all the important steps to ensure anonymity and confidentiality.

The researcher decided to undertake the Ph.D. after working in an accountancy firm for two years. The accountancy firm offered consultancy services to the SMEs to overcome the challenges and grow. After working in the field, the researcher came face to face with SMEs and learned about their challenges and problems. That was the main point that encourage the researcher to develop skills and knowledge further and also investigate the factors influencing the performance of SMEs in one specific industry. The initial research alerted me that the present area of research has failed to get enough attention from researchers and professionals and offered an opportunity to work on the gap in an academic way.

My motivation was to enhance my knowledge about business performance factors while becoming a competent researcher and improving my academic skills. At the end of my Ph.D. journey, I will be a positivistic philosopher, entirely comprehending the paradigm of deductive research, and trained to collect and analyse quantitative and qualitative data.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2. Introduction

This chapter offers a review of literature related to SMEs and their failure factors. This chapter aims to investigate the background of failure factors to clarify the failure phenomenon. The different perspective of the literature is scrutinized through literature. This chapter offers the critical evaluation of the conventional small business failure theories to practice them in conducting similar studies on business failure in the UK context. The literature review helped to develop the conceptual framework which contains three aspects of failure.

Firstly, several dominant definitions of SMEs are presented due to the absence of a collectively acknowledged definition of business failure. Then the unique characteristics of the small firms which differentiate them from large firms are further presented and examined to better comprehend the nature of SMEs. Likewise, it is significant to define and recognize the success and failure of small business context before establishing the SMEs critical failure factors (CFFs). Thus, several definitions of success and failure are explained and the factors which contribute mainly to small business failure are discussed in detail. Modern theoretical bases are used with the most important ones are being from Mayr (2020) Alsalaeh (2015), Lampadarios (2016); Arasti *et al.*, (2014), Lussier and Halabi (2010), and Bannet (2016) along with several studies in the context of SMEs failure.

The failure factors have been categorised into three common themes, entrepreneurial factors, enterprise factors, and environmental factors and then their influence is examined in the UK fast food retail industry.

2.1 SMEs Definition

Economic and social development heavily rely on small and medium-sized enterprises in all over the world (Gherghina *et al.*, 2020; Robson *et al.*, 2008). SMEs support economic growth, upsurge the wealth for a country, support swift industrialization, and assist in driving innovation and research, and development (Surya *et al.*, 2021; Franco and Haase, 2010). There is plenty of research around SMEs along with their importance well recognized i.e., (Mujahid *et al.*, 2019) however there is not a single definition of small business available which would be universally accepted.

Mostly, scholars define SMEs based on several employees such as privately owned SMEs having between 1-9 employees and medium SMEs having 10-99 employees (Surya *et al.*, 2021). According to the other definitions some scholars characterise SMEs based on several employees and annual turnover while others consider them SMEs if they have an informal structure, minimum market share, and are owned by an individual or couple of owners (Belas, Gavurova and Toth 2018; Storey, 1994). On the other hand, some scholars define SMEs based on sales. Mutula and Van (2006) stated that SME can be medium size in one country and large in another due to variances in nature and their operations. Scholars failed to agree on a single definition worldwide. Therefore, it is important to consider the SME definition based on economic and geographical location. The SME definition in some key regions is presented in turn.

Initially, several SMEs definitions in different countries such as the USA and Japan are discussed as these countries have advanced economies, heavy industries, and a strong presence of SMEs which make them more suitable to include. Afterward, to fulfil the aim of this study more relevant EU and the UK definitions are discussed in detail.

US Small Business Association (2003) proposed SMEs definition in the USA and advocate that non-exporting SMEs have less than 500 employee's annual turnover of less than \$7 million. Similarly, SMEs in Japan are categorised based on several employees and stated capital. However, this definition varies according to industry. The retail SMEs employ 50 or fewer employees and have stated a capital of 50 million JPY or less (Hironaka, Ashhari, and Diana-Rose, 2017).

According to EU recommendation (2003), SMEs can be defined as a business with an annual turnover of less than €50 million and a total number of employees less than 250. Likewise, small, and micro business definitions vary according to annual turnover and number of employees.

An independent business without any share in a large company, operated by an individual holder or holders in an adapted way and with negligible influence on the market is considered SME in the UK (Loader and Norton, 2015).

The discussion shows that SMEs definition varies in different countries and industries, sometimes even two scholars from the same country employed different definitions. So, the present study faces a challenge to adopt a meaningful definition. These differences in definitions need to be considered effectively to achieve the aim of this research. These

differences in definitions exist due to the variances in the economic size and nature of the organisations.

Considering the aim and objectives the present study employs a definition of SMEs according to the UK Companies Act of 2006 and Department of International Trade (2021) that states any enterprise employees less than 250 employees and maintain an annual turnover below or up to £25.9 million or an annual balance sheet below or up to £12.9 million. This definition is more suitable for this study as understudy enterprises operate within the UK. In addition, this definition is more recently updated therefore, it reflects the current market conditions in a better way. The definition adopted for this study is presented in the following table:

	SMEs	Large Enterprise
No of Workers	250	250 +
Annual Turnover	£25.9m	£25.9m +
Annual balance Sheet Total	Up to £12.9m	£12.9m +

(UK Companies Act, 2006)

2.2 SMEs Characteristics

There are several characteristics of SMEs which differentiate them from large firms. The literature review coincides that the most important characteristics of SMEs are the informal structures, managed by individual owners, uncertain environment, and very inadequate number of customers (Belas, Gavurova and Toth, 2018; Adams *et al*, 2012). Correspondingly, small businesses have a high risk of failure which makes them emphasize surviving for a small time as compared to planning things for a long time and accordingly focus on cash which they get instead of focusing on profit (Belas, Gavurova and Toth, 2018; Raju *et al.*, 2011; Adams *et al.*, 2012). The distinctive SMEs have limited customers, a few resources, inadequate running cash, rather than focusing on a strategic approach concentrates on current performance, rely on building flat organisational and have poor staff retention (Lukason, 2020; Simpson *et al.*, 2012). Business owner's commitment and motivation contribute to defining the SMEs, making them more distinct as compared to large firms due to which firms employ individual or

approach rather than strategic management (Franco and Prata, 2017; Raju., *et al*, 2011; Bonet *et al.*, 2011; Perks, 2006).

Forsman (2008) further argues about the claim of informality in SMEs and states that it is more likely in small firms to be engaged in informal practices instead of adopting sophisticated planning and control techniques. For example, a small firm’s recruitment process and staff training are mostly informal. There is the absence of formalized internal and external information, communication systems, the problem solving, and response time is faster which makes SMEs responsive to customer needs (Havierniková *et al.*, 2017; Belas *et al.*, 2017; Winch and McDonald, 1999).

2.3 The UK Fast Food Industry and Trends

Branded fast-food restaurants produced the largest share of fast-food market value on the other hand traditional fast-food restaurants were worth £4.9 billion in 2018 (Mintel, 2020). In the foodservice industry, fast food restaurants also known as quick-service restaurants provide drinks and food to customers. Fast food stores and restaurants offer different services such as sit in, take away and order over the phone or internet for home delivery. The amount is paid before eating at these stores or restaurants and operators in the industry do not provide the table service to customers. In the UK there are different segments of the fast-food industry such as burger focused restaurants, pizza parlours, sandwich shops, chicken restaurants, take away food shops and mobile food stands. The present research focuses on SMEs from all segments of the fast-food industry excluding the big chain restaurants and brands such as MacDonald, KFC, Dominos etc as the aim is to develop a model to predict SMEs failure. Table 2.1 shows the total number of fast-food restaurants, takeaways, and cafes in the UK.

Table 2.1: Number of restaurants, takeaways, and cafes in the UK

Description	Count of Businesses
Independent delivery focused restaurants	3,370
Licensed take away restaurants	28,705
Unlicensed restaurants and cafes	22,970
Take-away food shops and mobile food stands	37,465
Public houses	30,885
Total	123,395

After the pandemic the trends have been changed in fast food industry. The government enforced dine-in closure and consumer movement restrictions in 2020/21 such as lockdown has shifted the demand for food service towards the takeaway/ home delivery sector. According to Mintel (2021) 81% of Britain's ordered takeaway or home delivery by November 2020 and almost 49% of these customers ordered through a third-party ordering delivery service.

These changes have developed a new buying behaviour in consumers therefore mostly fast-food restaurants have initiated take away and home delivery services which they did not offer before by building new infrastructure or partnering with third-party service providers. Consequently, consumers have plenty of choices and restaurants have a bigger pool of customers to target.

Third-party ordering services such as Just Eats, Deliveroo, and Uber Eats have helped businesses to manage home delivery services. Apart from that, some localized small third-party delivery service providers are utilizing the opportunity and offering delivery services for fast-food businesses. These small independent start-ups offer great opportunities in boosting the local economy and offer delivery services to the community.

According to Mintel (2021) click and collect service users are increasing consistently since the pandemic broke out. Even though pre-ordering the food and collecting which is also known as click and collect is a new method in the market that has relatively low usage so far, however, it has a lot of potential in the takeaways sector, and it can be a competition for the delivery sector.

In conclusion, due to some recent changes in political policies and environment the consumer buying behaviour has changed. Customers prefer to order the food online and get it delivered to their homes for convenience. In addition, third-party applications have created some new opportunities for businesses to reach a bigger pool of customers. Therefore, these new variables can be crucial in the performance of a business.

2.3.1 VUCA Leadership Model

The notion of VUCA was introduced by the U.S. Army War College to describe the more volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous, multilateral world which resulted from the end of the Cold War (Kinsinger & Walch, 2012). VUCA was later embraced by strategic business leaders to explain the chaotic, turbulent, and rapidly changing business environment that has

become the new normal. It appears that the chaotic new normal in business is real as the Covid 19 caused turbulent environments for all organisations in the world and rendered several business models antiquated. Similarly, technological developments and global disasters interrupted global economies and businesses. In different industries and sectors VUCA concepts have been employed for strategic planning. VUCA model is used in different context such as to make decision, manage risk, plan forward and solve problem.

Volatility can be defined as a rapid change without predictable pattern. Volatility is turbulence and some of the drivers of the volatility are digitalisation, global competition, technological advancement, and business model innovation (Kinsinger & Walch, 2012).

Uncertainty is unpredictability about different issues and events and outcome is unknown. The volatility makes the forecast and decision making difficult based on past issues and events.

Complexity is a situation that has several intersected features and variables which is complicated. There is information available for the businesses about the issue however, the volume is huge and hard to comprehend.

Ambiguity is the lack of clarity about what is real and true (Caron, 2009). It is unexpected due to its new and exceptional nature.

These aspects offer the context in which businesses position their current and future state. In these context businesses develop plans and policies. So, VUCA assist in managing and leading. VUCA is a pragmatic system for readiness and awareness.

2.4 Common Grounds of Business Failure

Literature on business failure incited in the late 1800s after the formation of the commercial banks which helped the financial information to move and expand significantly (Horrigan, 1968). The multidiscipline type of research on business failures has been widely discovered by a combination of research from accountancy, entrepreneurship, economics, information systems, general management, and social psychology (Hambrick, 2007).

Intensive research can be found on two competing schools of thought the deterministic and voluntaristic schools of thought (e.g., Aldrich, 1979; Hambrick & Mason, 1984; Hambrick, 2007). There is a conflict between these two approaches as the deterministic approach suggests that as businesses operate in the environment thus, it can be said that the external factors have a great influence on business failure (Hannan & Freeman, 1977; Aldrich, 1979). While nurture

or voluntaristic approach suggests that in business failure internal factors have a major role to play (Finkelstein, 2005; Hambrick, 2007; Hambrick & Mason, 1984). Therefore, it requires further comprehensive research to better understand the business failure phenomenon in this area.

In addition, the literature suggests that the studies conducted in this area are dispersed across different arenas for instance management, psychology, entrepreneurship, and business. According to Khalil (2016), the focus of the research is less on individual-level failure factors as compared to firm level. Thus, a holistic approach is required which encapsulates all three aspects entrepreneurial, enterprise (internal), and business environmental (external) factors contributing to the early-stage failure of businesses.

It's not possible to gain a deeper understanding of SMEs until the business failure causes are not thoroughly investigated (Michael and Combs, 2008; Halabi and Lussier, 2014). Samuels *et al.* (2008) state that insufficient empirical literature available on failure and in more recent research, Kyriakidou and Lampadariou, (2015), Bennett, (2016), and Garcia *et al.*, (2019) also acknowledge that most entrepreneurship research emphasized business success rather than business failure. Therefore, it is important to evaluate the business failure factors.

Literature suggests that businesses owned by owners with no previous entrepreneurship experience are more likely to fail than other firms (Boden and Nucci, 2000). For instance, business owners with more than 10 years of entrepreneurial experience and good qualifications were less likely to fail. In addition, the same study findings suggest that lack of formal planning more often fails as compared to businesses that have a proper business plan.

Quadir and Jahur (2011) conducted a study in Bangladesh and states that an entrepreneur's success or failure depends on the ability to act effectively to various internal and external risks. Entrepreneurs' direct, frequent, and vast external business contacts assist them in achieving success. Entrepreneurs enhance their positive performance through compiling rapid information about the environmental changes and gaining in-depth knowledge about businesses which helps in positive performance. For example, empirical evidence suggests that successful entrepreneurs mostly consult different stakeholders such as partners, customers, suppliers, and employees while this pattern was opposite in unsuccessful firms. Networking, behaviour, and business performance have a positive relationship (Lee and Tsang, 2001).

It is evident in the literature that several individual factors have an impact on SME performance. These individual factors are referred to as individuals' traits and controlled by

the person. These factors include education level, poor qualifications, previous trading experience, and poor managerial abilities (Arasti *et al.*, 2012; Gaskil *et al.*, 1993; Ihua, 2009).

Similarly, some enterprise-related factors can be found in the SMEs failure literature. The size of the firm is a crucial factor in the failure of small businesses (Bates and Nucci, 1990). The failure rate in small businesses is higher than in large firms. In small businesses, another common enterprise-related factor that impacts failure is insufficient capital as these businesses do not have enough funds to innovate or develop (Audrestsch and Mahmood, 1995).

Furthermore, some of the common enterprise factors considered important in SMEs failure include the firm size, strategic planning, marketing, management, and human capital (Okpara and Wynn, 2007; Gonzales, 2009; Kelley and Nakosteen, 2005; Islam *et al.*, 2011; Littunen and Tohmo, 2003; Holmes *et al.*, 2010). Carter and Auken (2006) acknowledged the main reasons for bankruptcy in Iowa businesses by the assessment of bankrupt and non-bankrupt businesses. The findings of their research suggest that root causes in bankrupt businesses were lack of knowledge and inadequate practice of utilizing the internet in business procedures.

Similarly, some external factors cause businesses to fail. According to a survey, 78% of business owners in the UK claimed that the economy was one of the major hurdles in business success. Similarly, 57% of SME employers mentioned taxation, 56% rivalry in the market, and 52% government guidelines main problems in business success (The Business Innovation and Skills, 2013).

A study conducted by Story (2004) found that lack of institutional support, unnecessary regulations, and insufficient legislation contribute to SMEs' poor performance. The finding suggests that owners of several SMEs criticized the excessive bureaucracy while interacting with the surrounding environment, especially with government organisations. Similarly, some other external failure factors commonly found in the literature are economic conditions, government and institutional support, and available technology (Okpara and Wynn, 2007; Lee & Lee, 2018; Seo and Lee, 2019; Audrestsch, 1995; Franco and Haase, 2010).

Gill and Biger (2012) highlighted that lack of resources and finance contribute to poor performance in SMEs. Similarly, poor financial resources include deprived economic backing from the government, barriers in receiving business loans from lenders, insufficient security to get bank loans, and poor cash flow to run a business.

Suchánek and Králová (2015) conducted a study on food companies in the Czech Republic and found a positive relationship between customer satisfaction factors (product and services) business performance. Similarly, Jahanshahi *et al.* (2011) also found a positive correlation between customer service, product quality, and customer loyalty or better business performance. Similarly, the higher level of inventory management practices helps the business to gain a competitive advantage which leads to improved business performance (Atnafu and Balda, 2018). The automated procurement practices and other inventory management practices have a positive impact on the performance of a business (Masudin *et al.*, 2018).

The review of the business literature helped to recognize several dominant factors which cause a business to fail. These dominant factors have been categorized into three groups which are entrepreneurial factors, enterprise (internal) factors, and environmental (external) factors (Liao, 2004; Alsaleh, 2015; Arasti *et al.*, 2012; Ooghe and De Prijcker, 2008). The literature revealed that the failure factors vary in different studies and scholars failed to agree on one specific set of variables that influence performance. Therefore, it's important to recognise and test the most important failure factors in the UK fast food industry.

In conclusion, SME failure factors are complicated and overlapping. The success and failure factors vary according to the country and nature of the business which means some factors may have an impact in one country while non in another country. The literature highlighted the benefits of SMEs socially and economically therefore, SMEs need to attain more consideration from the literature. The goal of this study is to contribute to the literature. Although there are several studies on business success and failure factors, however, they failed to produce a generally accepted list of factors. The present study attempts to look at the problem in a bigger picture and combine the opinion of successful and failed entrepreneurs to contribute in literature by answering the research question: 'What are the critical factors linked to SMEs failure in the UK fast food retail industry according to the perception of successful entrepreneurs and failed entrepreneurs that could be used to predict future performance? Answering this question will help the SMEs to avoid failure and run the business successfully in the UK market. To answer this question, it is important to consider how to measure SMEs performance such as success and failure.

2.5 Measurement of SMEs Performance

The business performance reflects commercial effectiveness and evaluation of business performance helps in understanding the actual situation of a business. The performance is

considered positive if the business achieves the targets while it is considered negative if fails to achieve the goals (Forsman, 2008). Different scholars argue about the method of measuring the performance of a business in the SMEs context. There are different indicators to measure performance such as financial, continuity to trade business, and personal objectives of owners-manager. Success and failure are common measures of performance in the business field (Simpson et al., 2012). A positive performance can be considered a success for a business while a negative performance can be considered a failure. In the present study success and failure are adopted as a measure of performance to answer the research question. Therefore, it is important to define success and failure and the next section discusses the meaning of success and failure in this study.

2.5.1 SMEs Failure Connotation

It is significant to define the business failure concept for understanding the small business failure phenomenon. Intensive research has been conducted by different researchers from business and management prospects such as entrepreneurs to organisational and accountants to economic theorists. These researchers discuss that the main obstacle in explaining business failure was the absence of a universally accepted definition of business failure. Within a field, two researchers even failed to agree on a definition of business failure, and scholars from different fields were reluctant to accept a single universal definition (Walsh and Cunningham, 2016). There are different interpretations of business failures in the literature, elucidated as cease to operate in the market, discountenance of ownership, and failure to achieve financial targets (Walsh and Cunningham, 2016; Bates, 2005; Cochran, 1981).

It is a complex concept to explain business failure (Wennberg & DeRienne, 2014). Numerous scholars provide an extensive collection of definitions to give a comprehensive definition (Walsh and Cunningham, 2016; Bell and Taylor, 2011).

It is evident in the literature that the discrepancy of business failure definition has a double impact. Firstly, the choice of definition employed in a study would reflect a substantial upshot on recorded failure rate thus, making the comparison of datasets difficult (Watson and Everett, 1996; Cochran, 1981). Secondly, the scope of definition reveals an impact on the recorded results and process therefore, different definitions expand the gap amongst studies (Ucbasaran *et al.*, 2010).

Cochran (1981) expanded and contradicted several business failure definitions from comprehensive to extremely narrow. It has been observed that there are hurdles in measuring

and identifying business failure due to many reasons. First, when a business exits from the market it's hard to locate them, while business is defined as a business exiting the market and stopping trading. Furthermore, it could be hard to identify the reasons for business failure. Lastly, comprehending the impact of business failure from owners may hinge on the objectives that they set to achieve (Carter and Auken, 2006). While in literature five common definitions of business failure can be found which are discussed one by one.

The first definition for business failure employed intensively in the literature is discontinuance of ownership in which resources are sometimes transferred to more profitable opportunities (Fredland and Morris, 1976). Discontinuance of ownership definition discusses businesses, sold for several reasons such as owners' retirement, health reason, or selling it to someone else for profit. Furthermore, in most cases, there is no link between business sales and failure as mentioned earlier many business owners sell it due to sickness, retirement, or other financial gains (Everett and Watson, 1998).

In addition, discontinuance definition relies on entry and exit rates. Numerous authors argue that it is not irrational to use discontinuance as a synonym of failure (Wennberg and DeTienne, 2014; Khelil, 2016; Justo *et al.*, 2015). The business failure means a transfer of the business ownership in this definition while, an owner may sell the business for profit or for moving resources into a more profitable sector (Watson, 2003). Headd (2003) proposed that discontinuance doesn't need to have any link to failure. The business may cease to exist because of acquisition or merger with another business or business owner willingly shut it for some personal gain (Cardozo and Borchert, 2004)

Another common definition in literature for business failure is bankruptcy. Bankruptcy can be defined as the legal exit or dissolution of business through compulsory liquidation (Walsh and Cunningham, 2016; Sheehan, 2014). In a voluntary liquidation, the firm dissolves in the early stages which helps the business to avoid further losses in some cases however, in some circumstances the firm goes through voluntary liquidation to gain some positive objectives such as acquisition or merger.

Bankrupt businesses are easy to identify with a legal process that is held on record therefore it's an appealing definition to use for identifying the impact of business failure factors (Cohchran, 1981). On the other hand, different studies critique as this definition fail to explain the other indicators of failing business such as inadequate rate of return for a business owner (Uchbasaran *et al.*, 2013).

Furthermore, some scholars suggest that business failure means when businesses cease to run their activities and the capital involved in the business is lost. It also includes businesses that fail to earn enough profit or fail to meet the objectives of owners. The issue to employ this definition is that numerous researchers categorize business failure rely on closing (Watson, 2003; Everett *et al.*, 1998; Ropega, 2011).

One of the most used definitions of business failure was presented by Gaskill. *et al.* (1993) stated failure definition as owner urge to sell or liquidate the business to evade loss otherwise to pay off a creditor or exit the business without any profit.

Even though, researchers could not provide a comprehensive definition of business failure analysis of 201 journal articles that contained a clearer definition of business failure shows a focus on several dimensions of failure such as business closure, change of ownership, business file for bankruptcy, and inability to gain desired goals and expectations (Dias, 2017).

Other definitions of business failure from various protectives found in the literature include the following:

Table 2.2: Business Failure Definitions

Source: Walsh and Cunningham (2016)

Lastly, the definition which suits the present study and therefore, employed for this research defines business failure as a business in which the owner is unable to hold control of the business anymore due to bankruptcy, business ceased operations with losing the money to creditors, willingly shutting down business operations with unpaid responsibilities or is in bankruptcy or business cease to exist commercially and as a result of the physical structure of small business willingly or unwillingly has to shut down besides business end operating or transacting within three years (Arasti *et al.*, 2014; Pretorius, 2009). The profit or financial indicators to measure performance could not be utilized due to the lack of financial data about the participating businesses. Therefore, the performance of the business to be successful or failed was measured based on the business ability of trading during a certain period instead of objective measures of success and failure.

2.5.2 SMEs Success Connotation

When the aim is to identify the business failure factors in SMEs it is vital to define the business success. There are some real challenges to defining the term success just like a failure. The term success has many interpretations and perceptions in the SMEs sector (Beaver, 2002). Similarly, the definition of business success varies from owners, and business backing agencies (Saleh, 2016). Literature on small business success suggests that success definition employed by different sectors of business varies and there is not a universally agreed definition of business success or failure (Rogoff et al., 2004).

Mostly the continued viability or longevity has been used as a proxy for business success by researchers (Wasilczuk, 2000; Simpson *et al.*, 2004; Perry, 2001; Everett and Watson, 1998). Yet, all the definitions mentioned earlier present an inappropriate opinion about success as one enterprise might remain operative for a long time and be considered successful, however, it fails to gain sufficient profit or a business cease to exist and owners made a good profit out of it (Walker & Brown, 2004; Rogoff *et al.*, 2004).

Literature advocate that there are numerous methods to measure success such as long-time trade duration productivity, survival, turnover, the size of business, sales growth, status, and return on investment (Alsaleh, 2015; Lampadarios, 2016; Bannet, 2016; Vesper, 1990; Rogoff *et al.*, 2004). Similarly, some other authors proposed that success is measured by profitability (return on investment, profit) and growth (Dess and Robinson, 1984; Smith *et al.*, 1988).

In business literature, growth is considered the most common success indicator by several authors, and it is evident that survival probability is twice in the young growing forms as compared to young nongrowing firms (Al-Tit, Omri and Euch, 2019; Storey, 1998; Brush and Vanderwerf, 1992; Phillips and Kirchhoff, 1989). McDougall *et al.*, (1994) also argue that in the short term the growth harms profitability however, in the long term it favours profitability. Likewise, entrepreneurship and small business literature also back the link between sales growth and profitability and remained the most common indicator to measure firm performance and success (Brannback *et al.*, 2010; Achtenagen *et al.*, 2010; Steffens *et al.*, 2009; Shepherd and Wiklund, 2009; Shepherd and Wiklund, 2009; Kiviluoto *et al.*, 2011). However, businesses are reluctant to share their financial data, and access to financial data is a real hurdle.

In conclusion, a key feature observed in the small growing businesses is a composed position of the possessor's aim, business capabilities, and prospect situation (Morrison *et al.*, 2003). Even though, measuring small business success and growth is challenging still it can be

measured in subjective and objective ways. Therefore, a subjective measure that is qualitatively recognized as soft information includes the owner's assessment of success and personal insight of success. Similarly, hard information or objective measures which are quantitative types includes profit, continuity in operations, and profits (Wasilczuk, 2000).

The literature suggests that most small businesses fail within three years therefore, in the light of the research question and aim successful businesses are those who succeed to overcome different challenges and survive in different situations for more than three years (Wilson, 2017; Arasti *et al.*, 2014; Pretorius, 2009). The research used this definition of success as it best suits the aim and objective of this study and is backed by previous studies.

2.6 Theoretical Framework

It is highlighted in the previous chapter that SMEs have an essential part to play in accelerating economic development, creating jobs, developing, and strengthening economies in developing and developed countries. However, different studies propose that the failure rate of SMEs is more than 50 percent within the first five years. For example, in the UK 8 businesses out of 10 fails within their first year of operations (Wilson, 2017). Therefore, the present study aims to investigate the factors which significantly contribute to the business failure to reduce the business failure and increase the chances of business success.

The business failure literature identified two main streams, deterministic and voluntaristic notwithstanding robust disintegration. The core theories in the deterministic stream include organisational ecology and industrial organisation (Stinchcombe, 1965; Tushman and Anderson, 1986). Similarly, there are plenty of theories that stem from a voluntaristic perspective (Amankwah, 2016). The deterministic approach suggests that most research analyses the performance of the corporates. In this field organisation, ecology research discusses that the death rate in small, or young businesses is higher as compared to big or old firms (Legendre, Nitani and Riding, 2021; Henderson 1999; Nucci 1989). The further scrutiny in this area led to liabilities of newness and liabilities of smallness (Carroll, 1983; Brüderl and Schüssler, 1990; Bates and Nucci, 1989; Freeman *et al.*, 1983). In addition, organisational ecology explains the extensiveness target market of novel establishments. It becomes tough to advance knowledge and skills across the selected market if the market is extensive. Furthermore, this approach highlights that the liability of newness and smallness influence the performance of new businesses (Faroque *et al.*, 2021; Stinchcombe, 1965).

There are several success and failure factors exposed by intensive literature review. Storey (1994) categorised these success and failure factors as internal and external factors based on their significance. The firm structure, internal operations, and external environment have a significant effect on performance. SMEs can control the internal factors while they have little or no control over external factors. However, the pressure from the external factors can be controlled through managing the firm resources (Simpson et al., 2012). Similarly, these external factors can influence the performance of a business such as labour regulations.

Enterprise-related factors are discussed as resources inside the firm. These resources can be controlled by the firm. The resource-based view (RBV) has been widely used by scholars as a theoretical framework to identify the factors that influence the performance of a business (Alsaleh, 2015; Crook et al., 2008). This theory suggests that firm resources differentiate and give a competitive advantage to a business which determines success and failure based on the deployment of firm resources. There are two key points in this theory. The first point is that business consist of a group of productive resources and these resources vary from one firm to another (Penrose, 1959). Secondly, these resources are difficult to imitate (Barney, 1991). These diverse resources help the business to gain a competitive advantage and determine success or failure (Rangone, 1999). One of the most important aspects of the resource-based view is that it emphasizes the internal factors for business better performance (Barney, 1991). The resource-based view proposes that a business must develop and maintain superior skills and resources to retain a competitive edge. Furthermore, a business can achieve competitive advantage by following the VRIO model which suggests that resources need to be valuable, rare, imitable, and organised (Barney, 1991). Therefore, resources owned by an organisation must contain the VRIO attributes.

The resources can be categorised in different ways (see figure 2.1) such as physical capital, geographical location, and human capital. Human capital can be a very significant resource for a firm success, and it includes experience, understanding of employees, intelligence, and management. In addition, according to Barney (2001) resources also encompass firm capital, structure, management, and planning. The firm resources can be classified into tangible resources such as types of equipment and intangible resources such as brand name (Galbreath, 2005).

Figure 2.1: The Resource Portfolio

Source: Galbreath (2005, p.981)

Several scholars utilised the resource-based theory in the field of SMEs such as Rangone (1999) used it to examine how innovation, market management, and production competence can help in gaining competitive advantage. Similarly, O’Cass and Sok (2013) adopted resource-based theory to measure SMEs performance based on a combination of intellectual resources such as marketing competence, product innovation, etc.

Nevertheless, the scholars failed to develop a list of enterprise factors that resulted in the success or failure of SMEs and relied on a combination of resources in their studies. Furthermore, in the case of SMEs tangible resources are more important to maintain a competitive edge as compared to intangible resources.

Simpson et al. (2012) developed a model based on internal and external factors to measure SMEs performance and identify success factors. In this framework, the internal factors encompass the personal and business-related factors. The personal factors include the owner/manager's knowledge, personal experience, skills, motivation, etc. Likewise, the business-related factors consist of finance, planning, and management as shown in figure (2.2).

Figure 2.2: Theoretical Relationships of Success (Simpson et al., 2012; p. 270)

Furthermore, the model proposed that financial and non-financial indicators can be used to measure business performance depending on the definition of success and the influence of these indicators can change based on different phases of business life. The model also suggests that based on feedback about performance the owner's/managers actions ought to change.

Similarly, this model emphasizes the external factors that can influence the performance of SMEs. These factors include competition, suppliers, government, etc. The external factors can cause a threat to SMEs, and they are considered more influential as compared to internal factors (Franco and Haase, 2010). Simpson et al. (2012) also suggested that external factors can have a direct or indirect impact on SMEs performance. For example, suppliers are considered the first link in the supply chain, and they can pose a serious threat to a business.

Alsaleh (2015) also established a model to predict the performance of SMEs based on personal, internal, and external factors. In this framework, the internal factors encompass the personal and business-related factors similar to Simpson et. (2012) model. The personal factors include the owner/manager knowledge, personal experience, age gender, nationality, etc. These personal factors are related to the owners and play a significant role in the positive or negative performance. For example, owners experience assists them to seize opportunities and make strategies to tackle threats. Similarly, the enterprise factors were categorised into business age,

size, marketing, planning, and financial management as shown in figure (2.3). These factors are in control of entrepreneurs and managing these factors can help in avoiding external pressure.

Figure 2.3: The performance Prediction Model

Source: (Alsaleh, 2015)

Alsaleh (2015) also focuses on the external factors and relates them fundamentally to SMEs performance. In this framework, the external factors are categorised into microenvironments such as competition, suppliers, and macro environments such as multinational companies' regulation and risk of terrorism. According to Alsaleh (2015), these factors have a great impact on the performance of a business.

Overall, there are different approaches available in the literature to examine the business performance factors. Some scholars focused on internal factors such as marketing, management, planning while others emphasized external factors. Similarly, Zhang et al. (2016) conducted a study on business performance factors in hotels and restaurants and categorized the factors into internal, external, personal, and geographical factors. Alsaleh (2015) also emphasized three types of factors personal, internal, and external factors to investigate the factors that influence the performance of SMEs. These three types of factors play a crucial role in the success or failure of a business. Therefore, this chapter further discuss the role of entrepreneurial (personal), enterprise (internal), and environmental (external) factors on SMEs performance and develop a hypothesis to predict the influence of these factors on the performance of UK fast food SMEs.

Theme 1: Entrepreneurial Variables in SMEs Failure

Entrepreneurial factors or personal factors are related to business owners. Entrepreneurial factors play a significant role in the success or failure of a business. These entrepreneurial factors can be categorised into demographic characteristics, entrepreneurs' traits, entrepreneurs' experiences, entrepreneurs' skills, and personal characteristics. According to Islam et al. (2011) entrepreneurial intentions, qualities and traits are influenced by entrepreneurs' education, work experience, and demographic characteristics which influence the performance. The literature on SMEs highlighted that entrepreneur play an important role in the success or failure of a business. The owners' characteristics, personality traits, and skills decide the faith of a business. Walker and Brown (2004) stated that owners develop the plan to run the business and perform more than one task in the SMEs therefore, owners control the progress of a business.

In the present study to answer the research question several entrepreneurship theories and theoretical models are relevant to entrepreneurial issues causing SMEs failure: notably age of the owner, gender, knowledge, education, experience, psychological entrepreneurship theories, human capital theory, Sociological entrepreneurship theory, and resource-based entrepreneurship theory.

2.7 Entrepreneurship Theories to Explain SMEs Failure

The performance of small businesses can be explained through entrepreneurship theories. Entrepreneurship theories provide a good chance to emphasize integrating the varied

viewpoints. To analyse the field of entrepreneurship several theories are available in the literature. The roots of these theories can be found in psychology, sociology, economics, anthropology, and management. To answer the research question present stud will employ entrepreneurship theories to evaluate and identify the entrepreneurial factors that influence the performance of small businesses.

2.7.1 Psychological Entrepreneurship Theories

Psychological theories of entrepreneurship emphasize different aspects of the individuals such as mental and emotional aspects which affect the performance of the business (Jovanović *et al.*, 2018; Baum *et al.*, 2014). To identify the failure factors in SMEs the psychological entrepreneurship theories can be employed as characteristics of the owner matters in small businesses due to the smallness of newly established organisations. In newly founded organisations the owners are the principal decision-makers (Côté, 2017; Mellahi and Wilkinson, 2004). Furthermore, Eckhardt & Shane (2003) stated that in small businesses the owners decide the fate of the business.

The entrepreneurship theories can play a significant role in explaining small business failure as these theories emphasize individual-level analysis and characteristics (Baum *et al.*, 2014). There are three commonly known theories linked to the psychological entrepreneurship theories which are personality traits, need for achievement, and locus of control.

2.7.1.1 Personality Traits Theory

Personality traits are the stable features of an individual, expressed in different scenarios (Coon, 2004). The scholars who support traits argue that every individual has unchanging instinctive skills which help individuals to become an entrepreneur or successful entrepreneur (Mayr *et al.*, 2020; Roccas *et al.*, 2002). Through recognizing the characteristics associated with the entrepreneurs the inborn skills or traits can be explained. One of the benefits of explaining personality traits is that it helps in the interpretation of behaviour (Rauch and Frese, 2000). Also, entrepreneurs tend to make a difference individually.

Literature suggests mixed results for the relationship between business performance and personality traits as some researchers failed to find a link between personality traits and business performance (Brockhaus and Horwits, 1986; Gartner, 1989; Low and MacMillan, 1988). On the other hand, intensive literature advocates a positive association between business performance and personality traits (Franco and Prata, 2017; Mayr, Mitter, Kücher and Duller,

2020; Chell *et al.*, 2000; Cooper and Gimeno, 1992). Therefore, it is required to conduct research around this model and utilize it in failure studies to develop some empirical evidence to create a strong link between business performance and entrepreneurs' traits.

There are numerous scholars found a significant link between personality traits and business performance (Mayr, Mitter, Kücher and Duller, 2020; Franco and Prata, 2017; Nadram, 2002; Hill and McGowan, 1999; Man *et al.*, 2002). Similarly, in a study McClelland (1961) identify a link between entrepreneurs' qualities (psychological, sociological, personal) and business performance. Finally, a study conducted on manufacturing SMEs by Karpak and Topcu (2010) suggested that there is a strong relationship between business performance and personality.

In starting new business and survival personality traits contribute significantly. A study based on meta-analysis found a substantial correlation between entrepreneurship and business success which includes the need for achievement, innovation, required autonomy, proactive personality, and stress management (Rauce and Frese, 2007). Although, personality theory for the last few years mainly gravitated to the big 5-factor personality model. Yet, numerous extra traits have been added into the Big 5 for entrepreneurial study such as self-efficacy, risk attitudes, innovativeness, locus of control (Kerr *et al.*, 2018).

Intensive research in this area helped in compiling and identifying several characteristics such as the need for achievement (Ida, 2019; McClelland, 1961), and adaptability (Yang, 2008).

This research aims to identify the causes of business failure therefore, the focus of the research would be on the personality characteristics that contribute to the failure of the entrepreneurs. In detail, the most regularly discussed personality features in the literature include the need for achievement, motivation, and internal locus of control. Therefore, this study will evaluate these most significant personality characteristic factors in-depth to explain the start-up failure.

2.7.1.2 Locus of Control

The concept locus of control was firstly presented by Julian Rotter in 1950 which is a substantial trait of personality and entrepreneurship. Locus of control refers to the degree to which people feel that they have control over the results of events in their life (Engqvist Jonsson and Nilsson, 2014).

The locus of control has two types such as internal locus of control and external locus of control (Crombie, 2000). Locus of control theory proposes that the performance of an entrepreneur's success or failure depends on two factors, entrepreneurs' abilities, and support from outside.

The belief that success or failure relies on the abilities of entrepreneurs is called an internal locus of control while the second part of the theory which suggests that entrepreneurs have no control over success or failure is called an external locus of control. The internal locus of control suggests that life events are manageable, and the individual has control over the life events. However, according to the external locus of control life events depends on external factors which include fate, chance, and luck. The literature on business failure finds a link between internal locus of control and business failure (Crombie, 2000; Robinson *et al.*, 1991; Koh, 1996).

Barrick (2005) claims that “specific ‘traits rely on an explicit description of entrepreneurial activities that may be situated in time, place and role,’ which is why specific characteristics such as risk tolerance, need for achievement, or locus of control are more useful in predicting entrepreneurial performance than the Big Five.” According to Rauch and Frese (2000) entrepreneurs tends to reflect a little higher internal locus of control than other individuals. In a recent study through longitudinal data, Levine and Rubenstein (2017) recognized that self-employed individuals running incorporated businesses tend to have a higher internal locus of control as compared to individuals working in a business for an employer.

Furthermore, Korunka *et al.*, (2004) identified in cross-sectional research that Austrian successful entrepreneurs or owners showed higher internal locus of control than emerging entrepreneurs. Research on Turkish students found that students who want to be entrepreneurs imitated a higher locus of control (Gürol and Atsan, 2006). Likewise, according to Caliendo *et al.* (2014) out of all personality traits internal locus of control is the one that helps in predicting the entry and exit decisions of entrepreneurs.

The entrepreneurial literature further suggests that internal locus of control has a significant correlation with business growth. A study conducted by Kholik (2018) found that internal locus of control has a positive relationship with business performance. Similarly, a business can end up failing due to a lack of internal locus of control (Rauch and Frese, 2007). Lee and Tsang (2001) surveyed SME owners and suggested that there is a substantial relation between locus of control and venture growth rates. The business owner’s success or failure depends on their locus of control (Oktabriyantina *et al.*, 2014).

In addition, locus of control influences the performance of a business (Lampela *et al.*, 2017; Łompieś, 2016). Therefore, it is evident from previous studies that locus of control plays a significant role in new firms’ success or failure.

2.7.1.3 Need for Achievement

McClelland (1961) presented the need for achievement theory which is considered dominant in a workplace context to influence individual actions. This theory suggests that humans have a desire to be successful and accomplish the set goals. This desire or need urges the entrepreneurs to achieve success. Literature on entrepreneurship suggests that the need for achievement is a convincing factor in creating new business and found a link between entrepreneurship, motivation, and achievement (Johnson, 1990; Shaver and Scott, 1991). However, a relationship between entrepreneurship and need for achievement was found in a study on Australian entrepreneurs (Korunka *et al.*, 2003), and Turkish students found a positive relationship (Gürol and Atsan, 2006), while it was missing in research conducted on Swedish entrepreneurship students (Hansemark, 2003).

Similarly, several studies proposed that the need for achievement theory can be used to predict entrepreneurial performance (Ida, 2019; Rauch and Frese, 2007; Collins, *et al.*, 2004). A positive relationship between the need for achievement and the success of small-scale enterprises was found by a review of four studies (Cooper and Gimeno, 1992). Furthermore, Amin *et al.* (2018) proposed that the higher need for achievement has a positive correlation with entrepreneurs' performance.

There is extensive literature on the need for achievement and business success while limited literature can be found on business failure and lack of need for achievement. The need for achievement theory suggests that the high need for achievement in entrepreneurs influences the performance of the business and therefore, it can be said that the lack of need for achievement can be a threat to the survival of a business. Several empirical studies support the need for achievement theory and advocate those managers tend to have lower values of need for achievement as compared to business owners. In addition, a positive relationship has been found between business success and the need for achievement, lack of need for achievement affects the business survival (Davidkov and Yordanova's, 2016; McClelland, 1961).

2.7.1.4 Entrepreneurs Motivation

There is intensive research available on business owners' motivation which proposes that there is a positive relationship between motivation for business running and business performance. In other words, the owner's motivation has an impact on business success or failure. When entrepreneurs set a business, they have different goals based on which they establish their whole setup. These goals have a great influence on the performance of a business such as a

business that has been established to achieve planned goals have a higher probability to grow as compared to a business established to get employment (Smallbone & Wyer, 2000; Barth, 2004; Hamilton and Lawrence, 2001).

A study on critical success factors in Malaysia found a strong relationship between SMEs' success and motivation. It further suggested that there is a difference in certain things between entrepreneurs with high motivation and low motivations. The entrepreneurs with high motivation tend to incessantly progress, enhance operational skills, flank through problems, and are open to further learning and development opportunities as compared to entrepreneurs with a lack of motivation (Rose *et al.*, 2006). Therefore, it can be said that entrepreneurs' lack of motivation leads to business failure.

Agarwal and Dahm, (2015) and Camillo *et al.* (2008) proposed that business owners make all the decisions related to fast-food restaurants, therefore, play a major role in the performance of a business. A study conducted by CB Insights (2018) about the SMEs failure found that along with other factors the lack of motivation was severely linked to the business failure. According to Arasti, *et al.*, (2012) the survival of a business hinge on the motivation of a business owner. Delmar and Wiklund (2008) stated that managers' and owners' motivation influences a firm's outcome. The literature suggests that locus of control, need for achievement, and motivation influence the business failure therefore these factors can be categorized as one called personal traits and corresponding to this argument, the following hypothesis has been developed for testing:

H1: The inappropriate personal traits are positively and significantly associated with business failure in the UK fast food retail industry.

Entrepreneurs Skills

Entrepreneurship skills are also known as management competencies such as personal skills and abilities of entrepreneurs which help the entrepreneurs to perform positively and play a significant role in the success of a firm (Narkhede, Nehete, Raut and Mahajan, 2014; Markman and Barron, 2003)

Alternatively, insufficient management capacity, poor expertise, poor skills, and lack of managerial skills main reason for SMEs failure (Narkhede, Nehete, Raut and Mahajan, 2014; Mughan *et al.*, 2004). Therefore, entrepreneurs' skills play a crucial role in the performance of

a business, and researchers explore to understand the skills and competencies (Man *et al.*, 2002).

Numerous authors studied the association between entrepreneurs' orientation, skills, and firm's performance and described a significant relationship between them (Ali *et al.*, 2020; Anderson, Chandy, and Zia, 2018; Naziha Zuhir, Fansuree Surin, and Loh Rahim, 2019; Narkhede *et al.*, 2014).

Networking skill is considered one of the most important entrepreneurial skills which influence the performance of a business. The social capital theory proposes that networks are very valuable to individuals which helps them to gain the social resources existing in the networks (Seibert *et al.*, 2001). The main purpose of this theory to be developed was to elucidate the family part to enhance the neighbourhood, and human capital growth by family role (Rosa, 1993; Coleman, 1988). Afterward, the same theory expanded and helped in elucidating the formation of industry, discussing career accomplishment, business routine, and business expansion (Aldrich and Fiol, 1994; Seibert *et al.*, 2001; Baron *et al.*, 2003).

It is believed that networking skill plays a significant role in the success of a start-up as it provides market knowledge, expertise, marketing skills, managerial skills, information related to opportunities and threats from competitors (Dolz *et al.*, 2018; Huang *et al.*, 2012; Lin & Si, 2010). Entrepreneurs become part of a big social network which assists them in achieving different opportunities (Dolz *et al.*, 2018; Cllausen, 2006). Sometimes entrepreneurs recognize an opportunity in the business environment however, due to the absence of social connections, fail to exploit the opportunity and start a business (Shane, 2000). There is a common opinion that the accessibility of large social networks assists entrepreneurs to transform the opportunity into a business.

Anderson, Chandy, and Zia (2018) conducted a study to find the impact of business owners' skills on business performance and found a positive relationship. Ali *et al.*, (2020) also conducted a study to find the relationship between intangible skills and business performance and proposed that owners' skills contribute to positive business performance. Asieba and Nmadu (2018) also support these findings and suggest that entrepreneurs' skills play a positive role in a better performance of a business.

Alroaia and Baharun (2017) proposed that entrepreneurial skills can influence the performance of a business. Parsa *et al.* (2005) found similar results and suggested that owner skills influence the performance of restaurants in the USA. The literature suggests that entrepreneurs' skills

play a major role in the positive or negative performance of a business therefore, it is required to test this variable in the UK fast food industry. As a result of the discussion, the resulting hypothesis is shaped:

H2: Poor skills of owner/entrepreneur are positively and significantly associated with business failure in the UK fast food retail industry.

2.7.3.1 Education Level of Owners

It is evident in the literature that education is one of the important factors linked to the performance of a business. Generally, business knowledge is gained by formal business education which enhances the entrepreneur's ability to identify the opportunity, manage resources, and implement the strategies in a better way. Business education enhances business performance by equipping entrepreneurs with skills such as communication, problem-solving, and teamwork (Kim *et al.*, 2006).

In an earlier study on the characteristics of successful owner-managers or entrepreneurs, Collins and Moore (1964) suggested that successful entrepreneurs tended to be poorly educated. However, Douglas (1976) found that probably in the past the entrepreneurs had a poor education however, the situation has changed. He demonstrated a clear rising trend in the formal education level of entrepreneurs. For instance, from 1960 to 1970, while the United States population holding college degrees increased from 7.5% to 10.7%, college-educated entrepreneurs increased from 9% in 1961 to 37% in 1975 (Al-Zubeidi, 2005).

Commonly, entrepreneurs with higher education tend to have better adaptability in different scenarios due to their ability to process the data and superior decision-making (Entrialgo, 2002). The empirical evidence suggests that technical business education assists entrepreneurs in improving analytical skills (Martin *et al.*, 2013). A business owner with educational background is productive, arranges resources competently, and performs tasks effectively. Furthermore, educational background improves the procurement skill and investigating information skills of the entrepreneur. Therefore, educated entrepreneurs have a high probability to run a business successfully.

Innovation is linked to better education as it makes the individual capable of gaining competitive sustainability through improving the behavior (Entrialgo, 2002). A study conducted in the UK chemical industry failure factors found that chances of business failure increase with poor educational background (Lampadarios, 2016). Similarly, Saleh (2016)

found that the success ratio in SMEs increases with the higher education of business owners. In addition, a study conducted in South Africa proposed that lack of education harm SME performance, and with poor education level their chances of failure increase (Fatoki and Asah, 2011). Lee and Hallak (2018) conducted a study to investigate the role of education on the restaurant's performance and found a positive relationship between them.

Cho and Lee (2018) education level of entrepreneurs influence the performance of a business. Similarly, Karadag (2017) suggested that the education level of owner's managers significantly impacts financial performance. The education provides basic skills and academic knowledge to business owners that helped them in their practical life. Business owners with low education are higher likely to fail. Based on that discussion, the following hypothesis is formed:

H3: The education level of business owners is negatively and significantly associated with business failure.

2.7.3.2 Experience of Owners

Literature suggests plenty of causes of business failure though, the most common cause of business failure found in literature is inadequate experience. The scholars suggest that entrepreneurs equipped with experience obtain the required knowledge to achieve the goals and perform the chores successfully (Chnadler and Hanks, 1998; Gimeno *et al.*, 1997).

The human capital theory advocates that experience influences the performance of a business and those individuals who tend to possess more experience are more likely to achieve their goals successfully (Eresia-Eke and Okerue, 2019; Gimeno *et al.*, 1997). In the entrepreneurship literature, the most researched area in human capital is entrepreneurs' experience (Florin *et al.*, 2003; Carter *et al.*, 1997). It seems like experience probably delivers expertise to the entrepreneurs to operate a self-regulating business and utilize the relevant information to exploit opportunities, accelerate the corporate developing procedure and assist in enhancing routines (N., V., and E., 2018; Davidson and Honig, 2003). Some researchers propose that the previous business experience helps in avoiding failure and starting a successful business (Lee, 2019; N., V. and E., 2018; Davidson and Honig, 2003; Bates, 1995).

Experience is an important part of human capital theory and is considered significant for business survival therefore it is a prerequisite to be further discussed. Several researchers' findings suggest that new start-up founders with experience had a favourable role in positive outcomes in business success (Altaf, Ul Hameed, Nadeem and Shahzad, 2019; Nikolaeva,

2007; Duchesneau & Gartner, 1990). Oe and Mitsuhashi (2013) presented mixed results about owner experience in related areas and the success of a new business. Oe and Mitsuhashi (2013) attributed contradictions in research findings and suggested that founders need to share experience throughout a newly established firm and make sure to interpret it fittingly.

Altaf *et al.*, (2019) found in a study that entrepreneurs' prior business experience was a critical success factor, Dobbs and Hamilton (2007) further supported these findings in a study conducted on small firms. There has been intensive research conducted on entrepreneurial experience which suggests that there is a positive relationship between positive business performance and entrepreneurs' prior experience (Van Teeffelen and Uhlaner, 2013; Alfaadhel, 2000; Saleh, 2015).

Similarly, several studies found that the owners/managers' lack of experience also results in causing a business to fail (Gray, 1998; Arasti *et al.*, 2014). The entrepreneurs face several hurdles and difficulties while starting a business therefore, entrepreneurs with prior work experience avoid mistakes and have an edge over the entrepreneurs with no experience (Van Teeffelen, 2008; Amaral and Baptista, 2007).

Oe and Mitsuhashi (2013) propose that it is essential for founders to work hard to utilize their experience and turn it into an organisational asset. Previous employment may equip the founder with routine while this knowledge is essential to be transferred to other people and it fit with start-up activities and structures. Lussier's model is intensively explored in different countries and it suggests that experience is considered a widely approved factor that determines the success or failure of a business (Lussier and Pfeifer, 2001).

Yet, fast food owners with past work experience in similar areas could result in individuals who pose more realistic expectations according to fast food targets and provide them the behaviour required to cope with a financial and organisational crisis. An individual may gain strong communication, customer service, leadership skills, resourcefulness, self-confidence, and the ability to learn from mistakes from prior management experience (Gaskill, *et al.*, 1993).

Prior managerial experience also transfers some operational skills required to run a start-up such as marketing, handling staff, organisation, and effective communication with suppliers and customers (Nikolaeva, 2007). Saleh (2015) stated that it is essential for skills and resources to fit with the required set of skills and resources as the deployment of skills and resources is not enough for a business to be successful until fits closely with required ones. The knowledge

and experience to start a business from the scratch may results beneficial for the founder of a fast-food business.

The work experience in the fast-food business would help the founder to polish his/her skills and make individuals familiar with managerial issues related to fast food business such as how to differentiate a business from other fast-food businesses and how to manage employees (Nikolaeva, 2007). In addition, founders would have good pre-existing network contacts with suppliers and know-how to find the support and advice when required. In conclusion, business failure is influenced by the owner's experience and qualifications and business owners with prior experience perform better than owners with no prior experience.

Similarly, Agarwal and Dahm (2015) conducted a study on fast food restaurants and found out that prior business experience plays a crucial role in the performance of a business. Camillo *et al.* (2008) also proposed that restaurants owners with previous experience have higher chances of succeeding due to knowledge of pricing and menu. Furthermore, Lee and Hallak (2018), Sharlit (1990), and, Lee (1987) also found that experience contributes to the positive performance of restaurants and fast-food businesses. The intensive literature review revealed the importance of the owner's experience in the performance of a business. In the light of this discussion following hypothesis is developed:

H4: The owner experience is negatively and significantly associated with the business failure in the UK fast food industry.

2.8 Gender of Owners

The number of females owning a business is increasing rapidly all over the world as different governments are backing females to participate in entrepreneurial activities however, the number of male entrepreneurs is still far more than female entrepreneurs (Reynolds *et al.*, 2004). Mayr (2020) suggests that the business survival rate is low in female business owners as compared to male business owners. Several scholars from different disciplines argue about the impact of gender on SMEs performance. Radipere and Dhliwayo (2014) investigated the influence of gender on small business performance a found a positive relationship. According to Boden and Nucci (2000), male business owners are more likely to survive as compared to female business owners.

Furthermore, Martínez *et al.* (2007) propose that in developing countries female business owners are less likely to survive as they face challenges with human capital, have a lack of

experience, and lack resources. Likewise, Jamali (2009) argues that female business owners have lack knowledge, struggle with management and technical knowledge resulting in lower productivity and competitiveness.

Ndikubwimana *et al.*, (2020) findings suggest that the business growth rate is lower in businesses managed by females as compared to males. Similar results were found by Watson (2001) who states that in Australian SMEs survival rate is low for female-owned businesses as compared to male-owned businesses. Literature suggests that male entrepreneurs and female entrepreneurs are very unlike in characteristics and learning experience which influence their success rate (Ndikubwimana *et al.*, 2020; Langowitz and Minniti, 2007).

Levie and Hart, (2014) propose that men are more active in entrepreneurship as compared to women therefore, their success rate is also high. Fairlie and Robb (2009) findings reveal that female-owned businesses are less successful than male-owned businesses because women-owned businesses have limited start-up capital, lack of human capital, and lack of prior work experience. Similarly, Khalife and Chalouhi's (2013) findings showed strong evidence that female-owned businesses have lower gross revenue as compared to their counterpart. Hoque and Awang (2019) found that gender has an impact on business performance and male-owned businesses are more likely to grow as compared to female-owned businesses. In the light of this discussion following hypothesis is developed:

H5: The male gender is negatively and significantly associated with SMEs failure in the UK fast food industry.

2.9 Age of Owners

Literature on SMEs failure suggests that the age of an owner can have an impact on the performance of a business. According to Hellmann (2007), the age of the owner has an impact on the success or failure of a business. Edmund *et al.*, (2020) found a significant relationship between owners age and business performance. Kuationen *et al.* (2008) findings revealed that young business owners are more likely to fail as compared to older business owners due to lack of experience and lack of human capital. Belenzon, Shamshur, and Zarutskie (2019) suggested that as older entrepreneurs have more intangible resources such as experience and finance, therefore, they are less likely to fail.

Kritiansen *et al.* (2003) conducted a study on Indonesian SMEs and proposed that young age lowers the chances of business success. Woldie *et al.* (2008) found similar results that

businesses run by middle-aged and older entrepreneurs (more than 40 years old) have more chances to grow.

According to Belenzon, Shamshur, and Zarutskie (2019), older business owners have better chances of survival as compared to younger entrepreneurs due to prior business connections, and a better understanding of business routines and culture. Furthermore, Disney *et al.* (2003) also suggest that age influences the performance of a business and the survival rate increase with an increase in age. Kangasharju and Pekkala (2002) also stated that younger business owners (less than 25) are more likely to fail as compared to older business owners. To further support this argument, Lee (2019) found a relationship between owners age and business performance and concluded that business failure rate is less in older age entrepreneurs. As the age increase, it helps entrepreneurs to gain a broad knowledge of the market, enhance marketing skills, networking, and gain the experience required to overcome internal and external challenges therefore, the survival rate improves with older age. In the light of this discussion following hypothesis is developed:

H6: The older age of owners is negatively and significantly associated with business failure in the UK fast food industry.

Theme 2: Enterprise Related Variables in SMEs Failure

Literature suggests that these enterprise factors can be very crucial in the success or failure of a business. Mostly, the business characteristics such as business age, size of the firm, and type of ownership contribute to the success or failure of a business (Faroque *et al.*, 2021; Kristiansen *et al.*, 2003). Therefore, it is useful to discuss the business characteristics concerning the business performance. In addition, literature on business failure recognized enterprise factors that cause business failure. These factors include marketing, planning, location, and employee competency (Vasan, 2020; Fatemi *et al.*, 2018; Turner and Endres, 2017; Saleh, 2015;). Managing these factors can help the business to overcome the challenges from the external factors. These factors can be managed and controlled, therefore; enterprise factors can be used to predict the SMEs failure in the UK context.

In the present study to answer the research question, several theories are relevant to enterprise issues causing SMEs failures such as the size of business, nature of ownership, marketing and management, location, planning, and employees' competency. This section will discuss these fundamental factors to business survival.

2.7.2 Size of Business

The survival of small organisations also depends on the size of the organisation. The small size of the organisation creates problems and makes survival difficult (Choi *et al.*, 2021; Aldrich and Auster, 1986). There are different researches conducted to quantify the impact of the newness and smallness on performance which suggests that both factors influence the performance of organisations while the effect of newness is considered stronger (Faroque *et al.*, 2021; Halliday *et al.*, 1987). Liability of smallness proposes that small firms face the trouble of poor finances and poor financial funding from lenders (Aldrich and Auster, 1986).

Kale and Arditi (1998) propose that the liability of smallness theory assists in predicting the failure in businesses. This theory suggests that small businesses are more likely to fail as compared to large firms which have fewer threats of survival. The size of a small business influences performance (Bibi *et al.*, 2020; Hannan and Freeman, 1983).

Similarly, the previous literature proposes that the large firms have more resources to overcome the challenges and issues therefore the failure rate is low in a large firm as compared to small firms (McMahon, 2001; Cooper *et al.*, 1989; Aldrich *et al.*, 1989).

The findings of Devila *et al.* (2003) support the theory of smallness and suggest that small business size has a negative association with business survival. However, Baum and Locke (2004) found different results and proposed that there is no significant relationship between firm size and business performance. So, there is no clarity in the relationship between firm size and performance.

In business literature, the size of a firm is measured by turnover or the number of employees in a firm (Bibi *et al.*, 2020; Aldrich and Auster, 1986). In the present research, the size of the business is measured by the number of employees.

These survival issues due to small size can be explained when taking into account somewhat insufficient human capital. In the early years of small businesses, the competition is intensive therefore, the chances of failure are high. Apart from competition the management incompetence and lack of experience also play their part in the destruction of a business. With time the firm starts to grow, and the chances of survival also increase. Stokes and Blackburn (2002) statistically prove that the possibility of a firm to survive increased seven percent by a fluctuation of 1% in business size.

Likewise, the size influences the performance of the business in the fast-food industry (Gaskill, Van Auken, and Manning, 1993). Mayr *et al.*, (2020) found a positive relationship between firm size and business performance. Similarly, Bibi *et al.* (2020) proposed that the failure rate is higher in the early years when the firm size is small. In the light of this discussion following hypothesis is developed:

H7: The size of the business is negatively and significantly associated with the business failure in the UK fast food industry.

2.10 Marketing and Management

According to Chartered Institute of Marketing (2015) marketing involves recognizing customers' needs and then satisfying them while making a profit. The market rivalry between businesses is intensive nowadays even in small businesses so, to survive all businesses require to employ market development (Fatemi *et al.*, 2018; Verhees and Meulenberg, 2004). These days higher quality product services and values which satisfy customers' needs help the businesses to achieve success in the long term. These high-quality products or services are developed through behaviour employed by the market or robust business culture.

The businesses also achieve positive business performance through exploiting market research (Assaad *et al.*, 2020; Simpson and Taylor, 2002). Furthermore, marketing is also stated as a strategy utilized to tackle the competition in the market through aligned targeting and positioning. Small businesses need to spend their initial budget wisely. Instead of spending all the capital on product development uses a handsome amount on marketing as without enough money to acquire customers and build brand business would be ignored. Reijonen (2010) highlighted marketing as a method to create awareness about products or services among customers. Businesses use this awareness to drive the sale and utilize a marketing mix covering product, place, price, and promotion to achieve objectives (Reijonen, 2010).

Assaad *et al.*, (2020) explain the importance of marketing in business success. Kristiansen *et al.* (2003) further argue that business success depends heavily on marketing as business needs to be close to customers and recognize and emphasize market niche to succeed.

SMEs face several challenges such as limited resources, limited finance, and intense competition due to which sometimes marketing appears unnecessary to them to survive and grow. Still, the business growth depends on systematic planning enhanced marketing roles. In addition, enhancing the marketing role assists businesses to overcome several risks. Generally,

marketing issues are referred issues related to products or services, locations, and capital problems (Simpson and Taylor, 2002).

In addition, business literature emphasis on effective marketing for businesses to succeed and avoid failure. According to Eunni *et al.*, (2007) marketing is one of the most crucial factors in SMEs success or failure in China. Chittithaworn *et al.*, (2011) further support this statement and argue that marketing and customer orientation were the most influential factors in the success of SMEs in Thailand.

Botswana *et al.*, (2004) findings suggest that marketing, market research, forecasting for the demand of a product, price strategy, and market segmentation are some of the vital factors that contribute to the success of a business. The same author argued that customer follow-up and retaining customer data also help the business to avoid failure. According to Shalaby (2004), business performance is also influenced by word of mouth and customers characteristics follow up.

Regarding marketing location also help business in performing positively. A good location of business helps the business to present and market it effectively and attract more customers. The business is more visible to the customers. Therefore, it can be said that location is a feature of marketing strategy. Alsaleh (2015) conducted research to identify the factors which influence the performance of SMEs and found that there is a positive relationship between marketing and business performance. Similarly, Lampadarios (2016) found marketing one of the most important influential failure factors in the UK chemical industry.

Poor marketing and advertisement are the main failure factor in restaurants (Jang & Ha, 2009; Lee *et al.*, 2012; Roseman, 2006). Similarly, Agarwal and Dahm (2015) conducted a study on fast food restaurants and found out that competent management plays a crucial role in the positive performance of a business. Camillo *et al.* (2008) suggested that management is one of the main success factors in the restaurant businesses. Kotler, Bowen, and Makens (1996) also proposed that marketing and advertisement are one of the main success factors in the individual restaurant industry. Turner and Endres (2017) conducted a study on developing strategies to enhance business success rate and found that marketing emerged as a common success factor. In the light of arguments following hypothesis is developed:

H8: The marketing and management factor is negatively and significantly associated with the business failure in the UK fast food retail industry.

2.11 Nature of Ownership

The ownership kind has a great influence on the business performance. Literature suggests that running a business in partnership is one of the major reasons for business failure. Partnerships cause conflicts between partners due to lack of trust, lack of clarity concerning the responsibilities of the business owners (Arasti *et al.*, 2014). Bannet (2016) findings suggest that partnership was one of the most important failure factors in the charity domain. The partners tend to have trust and control issues. When it comes to decision-making partners tend to disagree with each other. Apart from those partners can have a conflict on the culture of the business, marketing, expansion strategies, etc. Lu and Beamish (2006) also proposed that partnerships have an impact on the longevity of the business.

Hewitt-Dundas and Roper's (2017) findings suggest that partnership issues are one of the leading failure factors. On the other hand, Marom and Lussier (2014) suggest that businesses run by an individual are more likely to fail as compared to a business operated by more than one owner. In the light of discussion resulting hypothesis is developed:

H9: The business ownership type is positively and significantly related to the business failure in the UK fast food industry.

2.12 Location of Business

The survival of a venture is related to the presence of an ideal business location (Okpara and Wynn, 2007; Stearns, Reynolds & Williams 1995). In business literature, it is repeatedly mentioned that an ideal location assists a business to survive. It can be argued that the success of many small firms can be expressed in one word - location (Wendt, 1972). Certainly, for those in the retailing business, location is a key element for pursuing success as expressed in the retail marketing theme 'Location, Location, Location'.

Kim and Lin (2021) indicated that survival chances are associated with strategy and location. Their findings revealed that firms located away from urban areas had better chances of surviving. In contrast, Birley and Westhead (1990) found that firms located in the prosperous and buoyant markets of the south of England were associated with high rates of small business growth and performance.

Business literature argues that there is a positive relationship between business survival and population size. Market size is larger in densely populated areas which helps the small businesses to survive. On the other hand, in the areas with fewer population businesses struggle

to survive as businesses fail to receive the support required from the minimum population size (Rogerson, 2000). Vasan's (2020) findings suggest that there is a positive significant relationship between business performance and location.

The location of a business has been analysed through different prospective out of which one includes business without customers due to too many businesses in an area (Rogerson, 2000). It becomes very hard for businesses to compete in such an environment due to fewer customers and high competition. A study conducted in Nigeria on small businesses explains that poor location was the biggest challenge for businesses to grow and survive (Okpara, 2011). In a small business, context location is considered a significant element in success or failure (Jardon, 2018; Okpara and Wynn, 2007). Similarly, several scholars argue that in a business survival location can play a critical role (Alfaadhel, 2010; Lussier *et al.*, 1995; Bradley, 2000).

A study based on home businesses found that poor location reduces the chances of business survival, and a positive relationship was found in several studies between the location of retailers and business survival (Ejembi and Ogiji, 2007; Ighthem, 2012; Strydom, 2015; Mbonyane and Ladzani, 2011). There is a relationship between business success or failure and location as many businesses become successful or survive due to their prime location (Schaefer, 2006). The same trend has been found in big brands such as McDonald's, KFC, Burger King, and other prominent brands. These brands choose a location to open new retail stores at prime locations, in malls, or on high streets. Therefore, the business owners need to evaluate several factors before establishing a business such as visibility of the business, footfall, and level of competition.

Parsa *et al.* (2019) investigated why restaurants fail and found a positive relationship between business failure and location. Graham, Khan, and Ilyas, (2017) conducted a study on the fast-food retail stores in Pakistan to develop a model for measuring the performance of retail stores and proposed that location help in acquiring new customers. In addition, Parsa *et al.*, (2014) stated that location is a significant factor in the survival of restaurants. The success and failure of fast-food stores and restaurant locations play a major role (Kotler, Bowen, and Makens, 1996). Block *et al.* (2004), also found a correlation between quick-service restaurant locations and performance. In the light of discussion subsequent hypothesis is developed:

H10: The prime business location is negatively and significantly associated with the business failure in the UK fast food retail industry.

2.13 Employees Competency

Intensive literature is available on human capital which significantly influences business performance (Khalique, 2014; Haris and Helfat, 1997; Mincer, 1974; Becker 1983). Most of the research around human capital focused on investing in training as a strategy to enhance performance (Panagiotakopoulos, 2011; Combs *et al.*, 2011; Bryan, 2006; Combs *et al.*, 2006; Colombo and Grilli, 2005). Hence, businesses enrich with skilled and talented employees perform better than businesses with unskilled employees.

It is evident in the literature that a firm's growth-oriented strategy depends on it is the capability to attract and retain competent employees which helps them to survive and grow (Pena, 2002; Barringer and Jones, 2004). In a firm growth, the employee is the most crucial resource firm contains (Bibi *et al.*, 2020; Robson and Bennet, 2000; Lin, 1998).

A comparison between firms with human resource departments and firms without them shows that minimum cost output is advanced in firms with human resource departments (Bonet *et al.*, 2011). In the early stages of establishment, businesses require a competent and skilled workforce to compete with their rivals and enhance their performance. It's useful for the owners/managers to augment managerial skills such as fulfilling workers' development requirements, participative management, and assigning duties to a worker making them feel more empowered (Chaganti *et al.*, 2002).

Furthermore, the literature suggests that firms with more talented employees are more successful as compared to other firms (Dobbs and Hamilton, 2007). It clearly shows that talented employees contain more skills, experience, knowledge, and reliability which help the firms to grow faster (Bonet *et al.*, 2011; Pasanen and Laukkanen, 2006). As a result, the employee's competencies can be seen as a crucial factor that can contribute to the success or failure of a business.

Lastly, a positive relationship has been found between the availability of skilled employees and firm growth (Bibi *et al.*, 2020; Dobbs and Hamilton, 2007; Foley and Green, 1989). It means that firm survival and growth depend on the skilled workers in a firm which are considered a significant resource for a firm. Similarly, Bennet (2006) also offers some empirical evidence to prove a positive relationship between business growth and workers' skill level. Several other scholars further back this claim and suggest that those firms that lack technically qualified and skilled employees demonstrate slow growth and it also affects their survival (Qamariah *et al.*, 2019; Storey, 1994; LeBrasseur and Zanibbi, 2003; Lin, 1998).

Enz (2004) conducted a study on restaurants and proposed that employees' competency and business performance have a positive relationship. Similarly, Chen, (2018) investigated the factors that contribute to the success of restaurants and suggest that competent employees assist in the positive performance of a business. In the light of the argument following hypothesis is developed:

H11: The employee competency factor is negatively and significantly associated with business failure in the UK fast food industry.

2.14 Strategic Business Planning

Strategic planning also holds unique importance along with some other factors in the literature of business failure. In general, an idea allows the entrepreneurs to start a business however, intensive planning is necessary to transform the idea into starting an actual business. Several studies found a positive relationship between firm strategic planning and their growth and survival (Fatemi *et al.*, 2018; Lins *et al.*, 2017; McMahon, 2001; Okpara and Wynn, 2007). In a study based on an analysis of 24 empirical studies, Kraus *et al.* (2006) found a positive relationship between strategic planning and firm survival. Similarly, in a similar study Fatoki (2014) proposed that businesses with poor business planning are more likely to fail. Perry (2002) and Van Aard and Bezuidenhout (2000) also found a similar result in their study which suggests a positive relationship between poor business planning and business failure.

Some scholars argue that small firms mostly plan through formal ways and take a long time in planning. However, in business literature, most scholars further argue that SME owners employ informal ways to develop a strategic plan and hardly follows the proper planning steps in a rapidly changing environment due to lack of time and focus more on running the managerial tasks (Chen *et al.*, 2010; Vodopivec, 2012). Furthermore, in a research Sumantra (2008) found that planning is not a compulsory element to business success however, it offers several positive benefits to the businesses.

Strategic planning assists businesses to gain positive outcomes through developing related information, offering enhanced knowledge of the environment, and avoiding uncertainty (Assaad *et al.*, 2020; Kuratko and Hodgetts, 2004). Similarly, Turner and Endres (2017) further emphasize business planning by stating that planning, time management, can help a business to be successful.

In the early years, small businesses are vulnerable and more likely to fail due to which entrepreneurs need to develop short- and long-term strategies to avoid failure (Assaad *et al.*, 2020; Woods and Joyce, 2003; Monk, 2000; Sauser, 2005). Moreover, George *et al.* (2019) further supports this claim and suggest that strategic planning ensure business success and assists business in deteriorating the probability of business failure.

Parsa *et al.* (2005); Perry (2001) investigated the success factors in fast-food restaurants and found a positive relationship between strategic planning and positive performance. Camillo *et al.* (2008) investigated the factors that influence the performance of restaurants and proposed that a strong business plan is necessary for the survival of a business. In the light of discussion this hypothesis is developed:

H12: The business planning factor is negatively and significantly associated with the business failure in the UK fast food industry.

Theme 3: Environment Related Variables in SMEs Failure

2.15 Business Environment

There is a common notion that the business environment possesses diversity as sometimes trading conditions for different SMEs vary within the same industry (Simpson *et al.*, 2012). The business environment is considered difficult and dynamic which poses a threat to the businesses. Along with some threats the environment also offers opportunities for businesses. Business literature suggests that environmental forces provide opportunities for the business, create constraints, and contribute to business success and failure (Lee & Lee, 2018; Lio, 2004; Ooghe & De Prijcker; Wiklund and Shepherd, 2003; Hawawini *et al.*, 2002; Burns, 2001).

Barker (2005) stated that multiple factors are internal and external contributors to the failure of small businesses. Therefore, the third theme of small business failure emphasis external or environmental factors causing business failure. Different business environmental deficits can cause a business to fail. These business environment obstacles frequently arise in a sequence and are mostly unpracticable (Oparamma *et al.*, 2010). The most common factors causing business failure mentioned by previous studies include poor economic conditions, poor government policies, and competition (Seo and Lee, 2019; Liao, 2004; Ooghe & De Prijcker, 2008; Oparanma *et al.*, 2010; FEE, 2004; Bosma *et al.*, 2009; Liao *et al.*, 2008).

Oparamma *et al.* (2010) researched external factors and found that poor economic conditions and poor infrastructure leads to business failure. Seo and Lee (2019) further argue that a

competitive environment makes it difficult for a business to survive and only businesses capable of acquiring profit and financial affluence can survive.

The concept of “environmental munificence” is another issue that falls under environmental factors. Another common factor discussed in business environment literature is environmental munificence which discusses government legislation, license laws, interest rate, and networking. This viewpoint proposes that a lack of such support may have a negative influence on the performance of a business (Anderson & Tushman 2001). It is believed that environmental uncertainty and the constantly changing business environment are sometimes beyond the control of entrepreneurs. As a result, these uncertainties such as technological uncertainty, unstable political conditions, and lack of sales demand can cause a business to fail (Anderson & Tushman, 2001).

This research has narrowed down the factors from business literature to address the critical failure factors relating to the business environment. These factors are political, economic factors, and intense competition (Faroque *et al.*, 2021; Arasti *et al.*, 2015; Azimzadeh *et al.*, 2013; Bennet, 2016; Oparanma *et al.*, 2010; Ooghe & De Prijcker, 2008).

2.16 Political Environment

The political environment has a great impact on business performance. The political environment has several features that influence business activity including the political system, political institutions, and the method of government to run the economy (Otter, 2014). Political stability has a great significance in business success and business growth in any type of political system (Faroque *et al.*, 2021; Guo and Shi, 2012).

Cateora and Graham (2001) found that businesses small or large local or international cannot operate effectively until emphasis on the impact of the political environment. The countries with political stability hardly face social unrest. The government back the industries, technological advancement and attract the investors by offering them different facilities, as a result, economy boost (Allard *et al.*, 2012). On the other hand, those countries that face political instability fail to appeal to investors and encourage the growth of new businesses (Globerman & Shapiro, 2003).

In different countries, government policies refer to government involvement in SMEs by offering information services and running the project to support businesses (Agnese *et al.*, 2018; Peng, 2003; Worthington and Britton, 2009). Government projects and activities have a

great impact on the performance of a business (Hanlon & Saunders, 2007; Fan, 2003). The business literature indicates that government policies influence the business performance and several scholars argue that for SMEs development government support play a vital role (Park, Lee, and Kim, 2019; Okpara and Wynn, 2007; Adesua, 2006; Storey, 2000; Bridge *et al.*, 2003; Parker, 2000).

The government policies can assist in SMEs development by enhancing performance (Smallbone and Welter, 2001). There is intensive literature that proposes that many businesses fail due to poor government policies (Oparanma *et al.*, 2010; FEE, 2004). SMEs face different types of pollical obstacles which pose threat to their survival, however, the most important barriers include poor institutional support, extreme regulations, and insufficient legislation. According to Gallup Organisation (2007), mostly SMEs from Europe claim that administrative rules are the crucial business constraint and businesses operate in an over-regulated environment. This situation further gets worse due to a lack of awareness and limited information.

Several scholars argue that failure rates upsurge as a result of excessive taxation and extreme regulation, on the other hand, flexible bank lending helps in deteriorating the graph of business failure (Oparanma *et al.*, 2010; Gaskill *et al.*, 1993; Burns, 2001). According to Reynolds *et al.* (2001), government regulations were pointedly involved in SMEs failures in the UK. Likewise, Swierczek and Ha (2003) support these findings and suggest that extreme regulations and lack of institutional backing create hurdles in SME growth. Alfaadhel (2010) researched SMEs success factors and found that in Saudi Arabia SME development relies on the positive role played by the Chamber of Commerce. The department for Business Innovation and Skills (2011) surveyed through telephone interviews from 4580 respondents in the UK and found regulation as one of the major causes of business failure. These regulations included tax-related problems, planning, and environmental regulations.

In addition, the government policies and projects which assist the entrepreneurial growth are tax rules, administrative measures, developing laws related to businesses, offering information to entrepreneurs, loans and financial support, developing the essential infrastructure, and indorsing entrepreneurship (Park, Lee, and Kim, 2019; Lundstrom & Stevenson, 2001; Azimzadeh, 2013). Arasti *et al.* (2014) in a study highlighted that government unsuitable policies can play a crucial role in the failure of SMEs.

Parsa *et al.* (2005) studied successful and failed restaurants and suggested that financial failures resulted from restrictive government regulations in the USA. Similarly, Camillo *et al.* (2008) also identified political factors that influence the restaurant's viability. Othman (2018) conducted a study on restaurants success factors and found a positive relationship between political factors and business success. Considering this discussion following hypothesis is developed:

H13: The inappropriate government policies are negatively and significantly associated with business failure in the UK fast food industry.

2.17 Economic Environment

Economy poses a threat to a business and business owners have no control over the economy as Fredland and Morris (1976) argue that during “cyclical downturns the marginal firm is more likely to fail.”

Literature suggests that several studies found that inadequate economic circumstances influence the survival of a business (Assaad *et al.*, 2020; Douglas *et al.*, 2017; Burns, 2001; Liao, 2004; Ooghe & De Prijcker, 2008). Like other failure factors, intensive literature has been conducted on an economy which is considered the third most important failure factor causing a business to fail (Douglas *et al.*, 2017; Birley and Niktari, 1995). Oparanma *et al.* (2010) further support this claim and suggest that poor economic condition is one of the major challenges for SMEs' survival. Fee (2004) explains that unusual events or economic distress occurrences in a country or region can change buying behaviour, reducing customers buying power, unavailability of a product or raw materials, customer strikes which ultimately may cause businesses to fail.

Different economic factors describe an economy's progress and influence business operating mechanisms and decision-making (Worthington and Britton, 2009; Cateora and Graham, 2001). These economic factors consist of foreign exchange rates, inflation rates, foreign direct investments (FDIs), and interest rates (Worthington and Britton, 2009). More specifically, in an economy interest rate influence the growth and expansion of a firm by affecting the cost of capital. Exchange rates further influence the import-export price and supply (Cateora and Graham, 2001). There are several policy schemes available to enhance SMEs finance control and improve competency by making the capital available for SMEs through interest subsidies and direct loans (European Commission, 2003; Cressy, 2002; Maeseneire & Claeys, 2012).

In addition, the limited cash flow creates hurdles for the businesses to run their operations smoothly and exploit opportunities in the market (Khan, Quaddus, Weber, and Geneste, 2020; Locke, 2004). The different channels of finance have a positive effect on the growth of SMEs which shows that a capital market with enough financing networks offers better access to financial resources for SMEs (Guo and Shi, 2012). GEM also argues that financial access to SMEs such as debt, grants, subsidies, and other types of financing offered by the government helps the SMEs to grow (Levie *et al.*, 2014; Amoros *et al.*, 2013).

Literature suggests that in different stages of business development credit schemes and other poor financial support established as one of the main reasons for slower growth and poor performance (Khan, Quaddus, Weber and Geneste, 2020; Korunka *et al.*, 2010; Alsos *et al.*, 2006; Evans and Jovanovic, 1989; Bates, 1990; Dobbs and Hamilton, 2007; Alfaro *et al.*, 2004). In the case of accepting equity finance, the business owners renounce half of the control to an individual or financial institution which discourages them as business owners tend to keep the control of the business to grow according to their terms (McMahon, 2000; Carter and Van Auken, 2005). When these small businesses acquire the loan at a high-interest rate it becomes very difficult for them to return the loan which causes their businesses to fail. Therefore, interest rate one of the indicators of the economy has a great impact on business performance.

Masama and Bruwer (2018) conducted a study on the South African fast-food SME and found that economic factors influence the sustainability of SMEs. Agarwal and Dahm, (2015) also conducted a study on restaurants success factors and found out that economic factors play an important role in performance. Parsa *et al.*'s (2019) findings suggest that economic factors have an impact on restaurants failure. In the light of this discussion following hypothesis is developed:

H14: The inappropriate economic condition is positively and significantly associated with business failure in the UK fast food industry.

2.18 Competition

Competition exists in every type of business and industry. The survivor principle suggests that incompetent new entrants fail as a result of competition (Lien and Klein, 2013). So, observing the actions of surviving businesses in an industry can help in recognizing the survival policies. Every business face competition as soon as it enters the market from different other competitors and only those businesses survive which encompasses valuable attributes (Nikolić *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, to survive a business, one needs to overcome turbulence issues. Besides small

businesses competition also affects the performance and survival chances of large firms (Nikolić *et al.*, 2015; Al-Shaikh, 1998).

Within the UK there is intense competition in certain sectors of the food industry such as grocery, food processing, and fast food. The number of competitors in a sector which is also known as competitive density influence the survival of a new business (Assaad, 2020; Nikolaeva, 2007). Similarly, Bennet (2016) conducted a study in the non-profit domain and found that competition was one of the main factors causing failure in new charities. Lampadariou (2015) found competition as one of the main influential failure factors in the UK chemical industry. Furthermore, Saleh (2016) led research on Saudi Arabian SMEs and proposed that intense competition increases the chances of business failure. When the new competitor appears and entrepreneurs fail to manage the competition it makes the business survival difficult (Assaad, 2020; Upson & Green, 2017).

Accordingly, SMEs should tackle competition as one of the major challenges to be successful (Kristiansen, 2002). A study from the Iranian market found competition as one of the most influential factors causing businesses to fail (Arasti *et al.*, 2014). Additionally, Temtime and Pansiri, (2004) also support this claim that competition intensity can harm the business performance.

Department of Business Innovation and Skills (2013) conducted a survey study in the UK and proposed that SMEs managers described the competition as one of the leading failure factors. Gill and Biger (2012) identified the growth issues in the Canadian market and results show that competition was one of the issues in SMEs growth. Lastly, Franco and Haase (2010) conducted a study on Portugal SMEs about poor performance factors and results show competition put a negative influence on business performance.

In fast-food restaurants competition is one of the leading failure factors. Parsa *et al.* (2005) stated that high competition in the restaurant business increases the chances of failure. Similarly, Kotler, Bowen, and Makens's (1996) findings suggest that restaurant density of competitive intensity contributes to the failure. Douglas *et al.* (2018) also highlighted the importance of competitive forces in the survival of restaurants and cafes. In the light of this discussion following hypothesis is developed:

H15: Intense competition in the market is positively and significantly associated with business failure in the UK fast food retail industry.

2.19 SMEs Critical Failure Factors Model

There is intensive research available on SMEs however, the literature review revealed the absence of commonly acknowledged theory and SME definition (Arasti *et al.*, 2014; Lampadarios, 2016; Saleh, 2016; Chawla *et al.*, 2010). Likewise, the definition of business success and failure varies from each country and industry. Based on intensive literature review, validated model and studies the business failure factors have been categorised into the entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors as shown in figure 2.4 (Lampadarios, 2016; Saleh, 2016; Rody and Stearns, 2013; Jasra *et al.*, 2011; Simpson *et al.*, 2012).

Figure 2.4: SMEs Failure Factors Classification based on Literature review

These factors require validation from each country and industry as their importance varies in different industries. Figure 2.5 presents the categorization of the factors and a list of failure variables whose influence has been examined for SMEs in the UK fast food retail Industry. The model below is adapted from the literature which was developed after analysing the different failure and success models from the literature. This model is different from the other models mentioned in the literature as it encapsulates all three important aspects of business failure and explains the crucial failure factors. This is a model developed by the author based on the existing theories on start-up failure and success.

Figure 2.5: The Research Model

Source: Author designed based on the literature review

2.20 Conclusion

This chapter utilize SMEs-related theories to develop the theoretical framework. It discusses the vital problems related to present research such as the absence of universal SMEs definition, SMEs success and failure definition, and non-appearance of commonly acknowledged performance measures. Following this, the main factors that influence the SMEs performance were categorised into three general themes and discussed in detail. Then, hypotheses were formed, and a research model was established. In the end, the summary of the chapter was presented. The next chapter presents the research methodology.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

In this chapter, the research methodology, research philosophy, research strategy, research approach, sampling, and other research tools employed for this research are explained discussed and justified in detail. Firstly, research philosophy is explained concerning paradigms of the research structure. In the next step, the research strategy and approach have been explained and justified for the present research. The sampling method and data collection methods are explained and justified for this research and in the end, a conclusion is provided following data analysis procedures for this research.

3.1 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy can be defined as a process to create research knowledge, background. The research paradigm can assist in defining the nature of research philosophy (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019). The perception, beliefs, and exploring different theories and practices are considered parts of the paradigm which helps in conducting research. Paradigms are often called concepts, statements, or propositions that have a loose link, however, contribute to research construction and are sometimes referred to as motive or research purpose (Weaver and Oslon, 2006; Crossan, 2003). There are three different ways to think about research philosophy or three components of the research paradigm (Guba and Lincoln, 1994; Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2012). These three approaches are explained as follows.

Ontology is based on a mutual assumption about the core of phenomena which normally developed to comprehend the society's actual nature. These assumptions explain the development of the world and how things are made up (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

In Epistemology common assumptions assist in examining the nature of the real world in the best possible way. In other words, our beliefs about how individuals may learn information about the world (Saunders *et al.* 2015).

The third approach is methodology in which a mixture of different research methods is utilized to examine the link between human nature and to investigate the methods to examine the real world to acquire knowledge (Saunders *et al.*, 2012).

Ontology has further two features known as objectivism and subjectivism (Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2012). According to objectivism social phenomena exist that have no relationship to social actors (Bryman and Bell, 2015; Bryman and Bell, 2011). This approach points toward a fact

that the world or organisation can be observed from an exterior viewpoint based on real processes.

On the other hand, subjectivism emphasis that social reality can be developed by social actors' perceptions (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). This aspect states that individuals use the social experience to construct the social reality and the opinion of individuals directly involved in activities can help in understanding social construct (Bougie and Sekaran, 2009; Bryman and Bell, 2011).

The paradigm benefits can be achieved through defining the standards of paradigm and subjects for the investigation because of theoretical questions coming up from several conceptions and explanations of social realism. Furthermore, there are several other paradigms which include positivism, interpretivism, critical theory, and postmodernism becoming well-known due to recent development in social science research. It is obvious by inquiries that differences in the paradigms are required to be explored as it is not possible to measure one paradigm against another (Weaver and Olson, 2006). Therefore, it is important to understand and assess the employed paradigm.

Normally, there are two frequently used paradigms within research studies positivism, and interpretivism (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). The positivistic approach proposes that the research of human behaviour should follow the methods employed by studies in natural science (Saunders *et al.*, 2013). The positivists discover social reality through detecting human behaviour.

Moreover, the positivism method is used to develop knowledge through objective perceptive that purpose to signify and measure while trying to guess and examine the relationship between significant variables (McGregor and Murnane, 2010). Positivism is widely used in dominant institutional concepts within social research, and it needs to collect quite a lot of samples to achieve precise and generalized results (Therenu *et al.*, 2007).

The positivism approach focuses on measurable observations and analysing through statistical tools (Bryman and Bell, 2015). This approach is eminent as a theoretical deductive which focuses on developing quantitative data through using organized research tools notably experiments and surveys to generate a link amongst variables (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, this approach helps in achieving standardization and easily collecting and arranging gathered data. Lastly, the other researchers can test and replicate the research findings easily.

On the other hand, interpretivism relies on individuals acquired working experience as social structure utilize it to express reality (Creswell, 2018). The interpretivism comes out of participants' experience, and opinions concerning the understudied case, and interpret the perceptions which need quite a few cases or samples. Therefore, it is obvious that this approach is completely subjective which depends on individual opinions (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). This approach is famous as inductive which collects quantitative data through using unstructured methods such as interviews and focus groups.

Even though both research methodologies practice unlike research approaches and methods, however, both schools of thought are significant in their influence on research, and both produce generalized and robust findings (Bryman and Bell, 2015; Saunders *et al.*, 2019; Creswell, 2018). Both paradigms have strong point and feebleness and the use of the method rely on research questions and the aim of the study (Saunders *et al.*, 2019; Bryman and Bell, 2011).

In this study to achieve the aim and objective researcher employ as per Bryman and Bell (2011) the objectivistic approach as social entities occurs as an expressive reality and believe that there is an exterior lookout that can be used to view the organisation.

The present research aims to investigate the critical failure factors in the UK fast food industry based on already established theories related to SMEs failure therefore, this research employs a positivistic approach. The present research pursues to distinguish or assess a phenomenon of business failure factors, identifying the other common failure factors missing from the literature, and present recommendations to encourage SMEs supportable development and success in the UK fast food retail industry. The nature of these questions is confirmatory and explanatory therefore, it further back the positivism paradigm.

3.2 Research Approach

In social sciences, there are two widely used research approaches known as deductive and inductive approaches (Saunders *et al.*, 2012; Bryman and Bell, 2018; Creswell, 2015). The choice of research approach depends on the research questions and starting point. It is essential to explore both approaches before choosing to employ one.

Figure 3.1: Research Approaches (Saunders, *et al*, 2012)

In general, deductive research is employed in the positivism paradigm and it is quantitative (Saunders *et al.*, 2019; Lee and Lings, 2008). In the deductive approach, a conceptual and theoretical framework is developed based on existing theory and tested through structured research methods such as experiments and surveys therefore theory is the first source of knowledge (Lee and Lings, 2008; Saunders *et al.*, 2019; Gill and Johnson, 2010). Accordingly, in the deductive approach hypotheses are developed and tested through the scientific method with mostly quantitative datasets (Gill and Johnson, 2010). This approach follows the process from theory to confirmation. These under investigating theory or hypotheses are approved or invalidated in the finding section. In short, a theory is tested or validated in deductive research (Saunders *et al.*, 2019).

In contrast, inductive research is related to phenomenological philosophy and qualitative methods (Saunders *et al.*, 2019; Gill and Johnson, 2010; Bryman and Bell, 2015). An inductive approach is considered flexible as pre-determined theory is not required to conduct the research. This research starts from observation or interviews and develops a theory in the end (Kasi, 2009; Sekaran and Bougie, 2010). The inductive approach is utilized in an area with limited existing research and explores the reality through individuals' past experiences and opinions (Gill and Johnson, 1991). Therefore, the data collected in this method is mostly qualitative. In inductive research, the process starts from the general truth and moves towards

specific conclusions. It starts with an extensive description and endures with predictions for precise explanations backing it (Osugwu, 2020; Saunders *et al.*, 2019).

Subsequently, in inductive research researchers exploring a research problem collect the data mostly through interviews or focus groups and analyse the data to develop theory (Saunders *et al.*, 2000; Lee and Lings, 2008). The inductive approach is opposite to the deductive approach as theory would follow data. The inductive approach tries to find simple interpretations from specific cases, and it includes going from observing individuals to accounts of wide-ranging shapes, normally it is stated as stirring from the precise to the general interpretations (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). Consequently, the inductive approach compiles qualitative data to build theory and elucidate a phenomenon (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018; Saunders *et al.*, 2019).

The present research aims to utilise existing theories and test them to identify the failure factors and develop a prediction model in the UK fast food retail industry. The approach in the present research is deductive as the fundamental attitude of this research is to apply failure theories, in this case, recognized failure factors, to precise circumstances, in this case, the fast-food industry. The research aims to test hypotheses by conducting a survey and proving or invalidating the hypotheses in the findings. The construction of the theoretical model additional strengthens the deductive nature of the research.

3.3 Research Method

There are two common methods qualitative and quantitative research methods which have opposing views about how the social reality can be studied (Bryman and Bell, 2015; Saunders *et al.*, 2012). According to Wang (2008), the choice of employing quantitative or qualitative approaches depends on different research questions, and then a decision is made to choose the research method.

Generally, a quantitative approach is used when the question is to find the relationship or impact of one variable on another, examined by objective methods (Bryman, 2008). In this approach, data is collected in a structured way that can be quantified and statistically tested (Wang, 2008). In other words, this approach tends to present the results through measuring the data so that phenomenon could be explained instead of understanding the meaning and ideas (Alvesson and Deetz, 2000). The quantitative research method assists in developing knowledge and helps in achieving the objective of the study through quantitative data such as surveys and later statistical tests are conducted on the data to validate the results (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

This method also allows the other researchers to replicate the study in different conditions and industries to find out the generalisability of the results (Saunders and Lewis, 2012).

In contrast, the quantitative research method is utilized when the question can be answered through the individual experience, and socially shaped reality (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). Siwińska *et al.* (2020) also argue that the qualitative approach explores the qualities and meaning that cannot be experimentally scrutinized effectively. Denscombe (2003) proposed that the strategy used to collect primary data from fewer participants such as interviews or case studies provide a deep understanding of the topic and the research problem. Furthermore, Wang (2008) argues that data collected with in-depth interviews and observations share a lot of experience and help to explore areas with little research available that cannot easily be explored through quantitative methods. Table 3.1 present the pros and cons of qualitative and quantitative methods.

Table 3.1: The strength and weaknesses of quantitative and qualitative methods

(Dilanthi et al., 2002, p.20)

The qualitative and quantitative methods are considered harmonising instead of competing (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018; Gray, 2006). Both research methods can be mixed and utilized to conduct research (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). To research by mixing these two research approaches is known as mixed-method research (Saunders *et al.*, 2019; Bryman and Bell, 2015). In mixed-method research, both types of data are collected and analysed in a single study to develop robust results (Petska and Creswell, 2005).

According to Creswell and Creswell (2018), a mixed-methods approach can be explained as a mixture of methodologies in a single study to explain a phenomenon and it offers higher validity and reliability as compared to a single methodological approach to explain a problem. Gray (2006) explains that generally research tries to explore different research questions and one research method may be unsuitable to be adopted for the research and requires mixed methods.

Creswell *et al.* (2003) further support the use of mixed methods by stating that a mixture of both approaches is often utilized to explore specific research topics which cannot be explored using a single approach in a study and needs robust results. According to Vanderstoep and Johnston (2009), mixed-methods research develops results better than both qualitative and quantitative. Scott and Marshall (2009) also argue that mixed methods help to produce the outcomes considered as unbiased and robust. Teddie and Tashakkori (2009) recognise three parts in which mixed methods are better as compared to the solitary method. The mixed-methods approach collects the quantitative and qualitative data which helps to solve a variety of confirmatory and exploratory questions at the same time, offers superior implications and a variety of deviating opinions. Table 3.2 explains the different characteristics of the mixed method.

Table 3.2: Landscapes of diverse research methods

Quantitative Research	Qualitative Research	Mixed-Method Research
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use coding. • Structured questions, scientific method, surveys, quantify data for superior results. • Use different statistical tools for better results. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergent Approaches. • Unstructured open-ended questions or semi-structured questions. • Data collections methods include focus groups, case studies, interviews, text data, and audio-video data. • Content analysis and thematic analysis. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use both methods emerging and coding. • Both structured and unstructured questions. • Utilize both types of analysis quantitative and qualitative analysis.

(Adapted from Wang, 2008)

Greene *et al.* (1989) mentioned these specific reasons due to which researchers should consider using mixed methods:

Triangulation: means using over one technique to investigate the same research question while exploring the same area of a research problem. It is important to mention that using more than one method helps to develop robust results which are considered more acceptable.

Triangulation can also assist in defusing biasness in a specific source of data, researcher, or technique while using with a combination of other data sources, and also enhance validity and reliability of the research (Creswell and Creswell, 2018; Bryman and Bell, 2015).

Complementarity: refers to gaining better knowledge to comprehend the research problem and explain the research findings. In a single study, both types of data can be collected by the researcher to simultaneously solve the confirmatory and exploratory research questions, develop and test theories in a single study (Morse, 2003; Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003; Wang, 2008).

To answer the research question and accomplish the aim of the present research the mixed method approach is employed. The previously identified failure factors have been inspected in one specific industry. The present research is based on research questions that try to find the relationship between two variables through objective methods (Creswell, 2011) and develop hypotheses to discover generalizations in the results using statistical analysis (Creswell, 2011), the quantitative method seems the most suitable technique.

Furthermore, this research also seeks to inspect the explanation of chosen failure factors, identify the other factors causing businesses to fail, and pursue recommendations from successful and failed entrepreneurs to avoid failure in the UK fast food retail industry. The qualitative method is employed to back the primary aim through collecting the opinions. Therefore, the mixed-methods technique is utilised to address the confirmatory and explanatory questions in which complementary qualitative data roots within main quantitative data.

3.4 Research Strategy

Saunders *et al* (2019) stated that research strategy is essential in achieving the research objectives in any study. As soon as the research purpose is clear, and a research method is selected the next essential step is to select an appropriate research strategy to compile data required to explain theories and answer research questions (Bernard, 2000).

According to Kuhn (1979) research strategies are a set of views, morals, and methods collectively segmented by affiliates of the scientific community, work as a director to dictate the problem type faced by scientists, and explanations accepted by a scientist (Bribesh, 2006). Saunders *et al.* (2012) identify 5 key categories of research strategies:

- 1) Experiment: comprises the description of theoretic hypotheses; samples are selected from known populations; sample division in unlike experimental circumstances; overview of deliberate alteration in different variables; and measuring variables in small amount and controlling further variables.
- 2) Survey: encompasses compiling data from a large sample through structured methods. Data can be collected in different ways such as structured interviews, questionnaires, and observations.
- 3) Case study: encompasses the examination of a specific current area within actual context through numerous foundations of evidence.

- 4) Grounded theory: established with the help of data collected through several observations or interviews mainly concerning an inductive approach.
- 5) Action research: deal with change management and it requires practitioners and researchers to the alliance.

Yin (1994) states that the choice of research strategy depends on the circumstances and type of the research. Therefore, there are advantages and drawbacks associated with each research strategy and each strategy encompasses a different method of data collection and analysis. The research plan needs to be appropriate and related to the topic for collecting data.

In the present research the philosophy is positivistic, deductive technique with mixed data collection method therefore, it's reasonable to use a self-administered survey questionnaire. The present research seeks to investigate the critical failure factors in the UK fast food industry and develop a model to predict failure; therefore, the survey strategy is considered appropriate. The data collection through questionnaires would assist in recognizing the promising failure factors in the UK fast food retail industry cost-effectively and competently. The quantitative and qualitative data can be collected by questionnaire. In addition, data is utilized to propose probable causes for the specific relationship amongst variables (factors and retail SMEs failure) and established model (failure factors framework). Employing a survey strategy for this research offers additional control over the research process.

The present research utilised the mixed methods approach hence, a suitable mixed-method strategy needs to be employed.

According to Creswell (2009), there are four vigorous features: timing, weighting, mixing, and theorizing.

Timing

There are different ways to collect quantitative and qualitative data. It can be collected in stages or both at the same time. The execution is simultaneous when a collection of qualitative and quantitative data is completed at the same time which is also known as concurrent. On the other hand, when data collection is completed in stages it depends on the research purpose which type of data needs to be collected first. In the present study, data are collected concurrently, and the application is concurrent.

Weighing

It involves the significance of the research method quantitative or qualitative in specific research. It means which type of data is dominant in the study. Based on research purpose, the target group, the interest, and priority of the researcher's weight can be equal or in some studies, one type of data might be dominant. In the present research, quantitative research is dominant, qualitative study is utilised to support quantitative study and inspect the most important failure factors along with recommendations.

Mixing

Mixing quantitative and qualitative data can be done by merging data together or keeping them separate or shared in between two extremes. Mixing involves two extremes on one end and on the other end, both types of data are kept isolated. There is another type of mixing in which both types of data joint halfway these two extravagances.

In general, mixing can be divided into three types:

Connected involves the mixing of qualitative and quantitative research in which data analysis is connected and data collected in two different phases.

Integrating involves combining the two data sets of quantitative and qualitative data.

Embedding involves the collection of two types of data in which one type of data (qualitative) which fulfils the aim of the research offers supportive information to the other (quantitative).

In the present study embedding, qualitative data into quantitative data is used as the aim is to inspect the critical failure factors and qualitative data play a supporting role.

Theorizing

It is important to check a theoretical viewpoint gives direction to the whole project. The researchers fetch framework, theories guess their investigations. It is important to check a theoretical viewpoint gives direction to the whole project. The researchers fetch framework, theories guess their investigations. The factors mentioned earlier assisted in developing this mixed-method study. The mixed-method strategy employed in the present research depends on Creswell *et al.* (2003) six major strategies.

Sequential Explanatory strategy involves gathering and analysing quantitative data in the first stage and then gathering and analysing qualitative data in the second stage based on the primary quantitative analysis outcomes. In general, quantitative data is considered dominant and data mixing happens once the primary quantitative findings advise the collection of the qualitative

data. So, it is obvious that two different types of data are connected however, keeping both types of data separate.

Sequential exploratory strategy is opposite to the sequential explanatory in which qualitative data is collected in the first stage and based on primary qualitative data quantitative data is collected in the second stage. Opposite to the sequential explanatory approach weight is generally given to qualitative data and mixed by quantitative and qualitative data analysis.

Sequential transformative Strategy involves two separate stages of data collection. In this strategy, the project is completed in two stages with a theoretic lens covering the sequential methods. Like other strategies, this approach also starts with the initial stage and then the second stage of data collection.

Concurrent triangulation strategy involves collecting both types of data at the same time and doing the comparison of two datasets to describe any similarities or variances. In this approach, quantitative and qualitative methods are executed separately so the strength of one technique can back the other.

Concurrent embedded strategy deals with collecting the qualitative and quantitative data simultaneously. In this mixed method, there is an initial data collection approach that leads the research and the secondary dataset offers a supportive role in the process. In this approach, the initial data collection is considered dominant and the second dataset is assumed less important embedded in the predominant method. The nesting expresses that the second method of data collection may discourse a different question as compared to the primary method.

In the present study, the concurrent embedded mixed-methods strategy is employed as qualitative data give support to quantitative data. Both types of data are collected concurrently in the present research.

3.5 Data Collection

The aim and objectives of this research can be achieved by data collection. Two types of data can be collected to complete research which include primary data and secondary data. The primary data can be collected through quantitative and qualitative data collection methods. While secondary data is the one compiled already for some other purposes (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). In the present research, mixed-method approach is employed.

3.5.1 Secondary Data

The secondary data can be collected from surveys, documentaries, and other numerous available database sources (Saunders and Lewis, 2012).

Sources of secondary data include books, personal sources, journals, newspapers, websites, government records, etc. The secondary data is considered significant in writing a literature review an initial phase of the research and contributes to developing new ideas about the research (Bell, 1999).

Secondary data is required before conducting the primary research as it helps in highlighting appropriate published research, categorise the academic theories, scrutinize the descriptions of the ideas under study and generating explanations to lead the research, developing the features of the ideas, and evaluating the prevailing tools (Saunders *et al.*, 2012).

The secondary data has been used in the present research to fulfil the aim and objectives of the research. Firstly, an intensive literature review was conducted on business failure factors, and different online databases and academic journals were used.

As a result, common failure factors were categorised that helped in developing a conceptual framework. The conceptual framework helped in inspecting common failure factors and developing an effective data collection tool.

3.5.2 Primary Data

In quantitative research, the most common method to collect the primary data is known as a survey. There are several different forms of surveys however, generally, two types of surveys are utilized by the researcher to collect data in quantitative research such as interviews and questionnaires. The interviews reveal individual opinions and beliefs about a topic however, questionnaires reveal the difference in trends across individuals (Thomas, 2003; Creswell and Creswell, 2018).

According to Creswell (2008), a questionnaire is a survey type that is designed to collect the data from individual participants by completing and returning it to the researcher. The present study utilizes a survey strategy to assemble primary data through questionnaires. According to Bryman and Bell (2011) questionnaires helps in collecting data from several participants to gather measurable data regarding different variables which are scrutinized to distinguish designs of connotation. Questionnaires are considered effective when the aim is to collect the data from a large sample size at different locations (Denscombe, 2007). Busentiz *et al.* (2013)

also explain that questionnaires have multipurpose characteristics and can be used to collect both subjective and objective types of data by open and closed-ended questions.

The data can be collected through different styles of questionnaires such as self-administered and structured interviews questionnaires. The most common method used in conducting research is a self-administered questionnaire which is normally completed via internet, delivery, or post. Alternatively, the telephone or in-person method is utilized to conduct interview questionnaires.

In the present research self-administered questionnaires are selected to collect the primary data as they are considered an easy and cheap method of data collection while allowing a widespread topographical area to be accomplished from a large population. The self-administered questionnaire with a mixture of internet-based questionnaires is chosen to collect the response from participants as shown in figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: The Web Questionnaire Process (Adopted from Fan and Yan, 2010)

In addition, numerous questions can be combined in self-administered questionnaires and responses can be collected within six weeks. This strategy of collecting data is effective as it allows respondents to take their time to complete the survey at their convenient time after understanding the context of research and gaining information to answer the questions according to their best understanding. Furthermore, previous studies propose that internet-based questionnaires are considered more favourable with a high response rate as owners of SMEs tends to prefer online surveys as compared to the face to face or telephone interview (O'Regan, 2000; Chawla *et al.*, 2010; Arasti *et al.*, 2012; Saleh, 2015).

Online questionnaires help to reduce the biasness and are considered efficient to collect responses from large samples in less time. In addition, the online questionnaires are economic, time-efficient, and convenient for respondents and researchers (Creswell, 2008; Neuman,

2006; Summers *et al.*, 2002). In the present study, the questionnaires were also distributed to the respondent and collected after being completed by the researcher as this method is highly common in the UK.

According to Bryman and Bell (2015) along with many benefits, questionnaires have a low response rate which is considered a major drawback. Therefore, different strategies were used to increase the response rate. First of all, the significance of the present study and outcome benefits of the present study was written in a cover letter and attached to a postal questionnaire. The researcher also offered that interested respondents will receive a copy of the research findings. Furthermore, in a cover letter, the respondents were assured that their information will be kept confidential and anonymous. The researcher also contacted the potential respondents via phone or email to remind them about the survey deadline, and answer their questions.

3.6 Sampling and Data Collection Technique

Sampling is a method to select a limited number of respondents from the total population who meet the criteria to achieve the aim of the study by analysing the data (Corbetta, 2003; Sanders *et al.*, 2019).

It is essential to select the appropriate sample size by choosing the group of people, respondents, or cases related to the study systematically (Racha, 2002). Generally, it is unrealistic to gather the responses from the whole population as it is time-consuming, expensive, or not possible. Therefore, a reduced number of respondents are selected which represent the whole population and pose the same characteristics (Neuman, 2006). In the sample selecting process the most crucial thing is defining the population and sample framework. It is believed that people from the same population represent the same characteristics the researcher wants to study.

Probability and non-probability sampling are the two main sampling methods utilized by the researchers. It is valuable to understand the sampling method before using it. In probability sampling, all the people in a population have an equal opportunity to be selected for participation in the study while, non-probability is a method in which not all the people in a population have an equal chance to participate (Neuman, 2006).

Some studies also employ census instead of any sampling method when it is possible to collect the response from the whole population and analyse (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). According to

Curran and Blackburn (2001), it's hard to get data from SMEs due to the unavailability of an up-to-date list of SMEs.

Since there was no official list of failed or successful fast-food businesses the first challenge for the researcher was to compile a list of the fast-food businesses which fulfil the criteria of the sampling frame. The researcher contacted the insolvency register team and asked them for some help in getting access to bankrupt businesses in the UK. The insolvency register member shared some important links such as The Gazette and insolvency register search option available for the public which contains the list of all insolvent businesses from different industries.

The Gazette is one of the official journals of record or government gazette which publish certain statutory notices such as insolvencies records. The Gazette contains official data and useful material and records that can be downloaded without any cost related to insolvent businesses. The Gazette is a rich source of open data, including longitudinal datasets and linked data. It's free for the developer community to use and repurpose and (unless stated otherwise) is free to use under the Open Government Licence (The Gazette, 2022).

The insolvency businesses list found in The Gazette was very vague and it was not specific to one industry but contained the details of all the insolvent businesses from different industries. Therefore, there was a need to narrow down the list to only those businesses which contained the details of insolvent fast-food businesses from London. Firstly, the researcher acquired the list of failed (Bankrupt, Insolvent) businesses through visiting The Gazette website and Company house insolvency register. In the next step, the list was reduced to only bankrupt fast-food-related restaurants and takeaways through filtering the data.

This was a lengthy and tiring process, however; the researcher successfully compiles an up-to-date list of the businesses that went bankrupt in the last 5 years. The list acquired from the insolvency register and The GAZETTE official public record was quite large which was reduced to almost 1400 fast food businesses from London with contact addresses (often email address, home address, and phone number).

Similarly, the researcher compiled a list of successful businesses by visiting the company house website. The company house has all the details of the registered businesses in the UK. The researcher downloaded the list of 8 hundred thousand businesses registered in the last 5 years and then reduced the list to only fast-food-related takeaways and restaurants through filtering the data.

After the processing of data, a list of a total of 2700 fast food-related businesses from London was compiled. Questionnaires were sent to the potential participants randomly from the list by post and email and only those responses were accepted which fulfilled the sampling criteria below. Primarily, the plan was to collect the responses from successful entrepreneurs through personally visiting different high streets and malls from different parts (East, West, South, North, and Central) of London to have an equal representation of samples. However, due to the unexpected circumstances Coronavirus pandemic, the researcher had to change the data collection strategy to avoid any physical contact. Therefore, in the first step, a list of fast-food retail businesses from London was compiled. The questionnaire was designed in a way to collect responses from the target sample groups that fulfil the criteria of successful and unsuccessful businesses.

Simple random sampling was adopted for the present research to generalize the findings and give an equal probability to the sampling frame to participate. The small and medium-size fast food businesses were selected randomly from the list. The sample was selected based on different criteria. As the United Kingdom is huge so it was not possible to collect the data from different parts of the country due to limited time and resources. The businesses based in London were selected as a sample as London is the largest city in the UK with the highest number of SMEs and failure rates. The second criteria of the sample are the age of the business which helps in measuring the performance of the business, business will be considered successful if trade for more than three years and failed if went bankrupt within three years (Arasti *et al.*, 2015; Pretorius, 2009).

The sample in the present study includes two types of business owners' successful entrepreneurs (owners of successful businesses) and unsuccessful entrepreneurs (owners of failed businesses). Therefore, only those businesses were selected to participate as successful businesses who traded for more than 3 years while for the failed businesses only those responses of entrepreneurs were considered valid which went out of business within the first three years of starting business. As there was not an official list that specifies the successful and unsuccessful businesses, therefore, the researcher excluded the businesses from the list that failed to fulfil the sample criteria based on a questionnaire. In the present study the financial performance indicators cannot be used as firstly it is not possible to get the real financial data from the failed businesses and also businesses are reluctant to share their financial data due to competition and privacy reasons.

The third criteria are the business size which is measured by the number of employees. The study aims to identify the failure factors in the UK fast food businesses, therefore, employs SMEs definition according to the UK Companies Act of 2006. According to this definition, SMES are businesses employees less than 250 employees and maintain an annual turnover below or up to £25.9 million or an annual balance sheet below or up to £12.9 million.

In short, regarding the sampling frame, only those responses were considered valid which full fill the following criteria: SMEs defined by the UK Companies Act of 2006 that is enterprise employees less than 250 employees, located in the London, single business entity, deprived of any manufacturing ability, maintain an annual turnover below or up to £25.9 million or an annual balance sheet below or up to £12.9 million.

In this study owners of the UK, fast food retail stores are the key informants. The owners are selected as a sample as they are the most knowledgeable people about the issue under study (Kumar *et al.*, 1993). The owners are suitable for present research as they have all the knowledge of different areas of the businesses. The owners of the UK fast food retail stores can offer insight into the causes of business failure and recommendations to reduce the chances of failure. It has long been argued that owners understand the challenges and hurdles faced by the entire organisation while intermediate and junior managers have dubious rationality as they have lack of knowledge about the whole business operational mechanism and therefore, owners are expected to deliver the correct answers (Zahra and Covin, 1993; Snow and Hrebiniak, 1980).

Literature about business failure also suggests that numerous scholars' emphasis on the owners/managers as people at high positions poses relevant experience and knowledge to explain the factors critical to business failure (Bennett, 2016; Zahra *et al.*, 2014). According to Galapova and McKie (2012) owners generally make decisions and strategies to operate their business effectively based on their personal beliefs and behaviours.

3.7 Pilot Test

A pilot study can be defined as a replica of the main study collected on a small scale aimed to identify and resolve probable weaknesses, insufficiencies, doubts, and issues in all parts of the research before collecting the actual data (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

The literature emphasizes performing a pilot study before the actual data collection (Neuman, 2006). The pilot study helps to identify the errors and helps to ameliorate the method and structure used to collect the study for the main research. A pilot study offers satisfactory feedback about the data collection tool in a real-life setting. The data in the pilot study is collected from the same or similar targeted participants who participate in the main study as well which also helps in evaluating reliability and data analysis.

Furthermore, Bell (2010) proposed that a pilot study helps to inform the researcher about the likelihood of completing the questionnaires by the participants, identify the relevance, clarity, and understanding of questions, evaluate the instructions to complete a questionnaire, and recognize the issues practical in nature such as data coding. The literature identifies the advantages of using a pilot study (Saunders *et al.*, 2019; Bryman and Bell, 2011; Yin, 2004; Tashakkori and Teddlie, 1998; Cooper and Schindler, 2003). Similarly, several studies from business failure factors have employed the pilot study previously (Arasti, 2004; Bannet, 2016; Lampadariou, 2016; Arasti *et al.*, 2016).

In general, a pilot study aims to polish the questionnaire and make it user-friendly, easy to understand to increase the probability of participants' responses. The pilot study also assists in checking the validity of the questions and consistency of the data (Saunders *et al.*, 2012). Therefore, this study also employed a pilot study before collecting the main data to make sure the questionnaire fulfils the aim of the present research, enhances the questionnaire, and checks the validity and reliability of the data collection tool.

It took 25 days to complete the pilot study for the present research. The pilot study questionnaire link was sent to the respondents through email and time was recorded to take the survey. Furthermore, the respondents were asked to share their views about questions content, clarity, phrasing, and replication of questions. The feedback was crucial to enhance the survey layout, format, and clarity.

The researcher distributed 60 questionnaires equally between successful and failed entrepreneurs through the email link and 29 business owners (Successful 18, Unsuccessful 11) participated and completed the questionnaires with a 48% response rate. Any type of physical contact was avoided for the safety of the participant and to avoid the spread of Covid 19. The participants showed interest in the study and expressed that the outcome of the study will prove very beneficial for the new businesses. The researcher informed the potential participants that research findings will be shared with them which motivated them to participate.

Overall, participants specified their understandings and ideas about the questionnaire. The participant's feedback helped to improve the questionnaire. Most of the participants gave positive comments about the questionnaire while a few respondents proposed format changes. In the beginning, the questionnaire was very long almost 5 pages and the average time recorded to complete the questionnaire was 25 minutes. The researcher considered the respondent's feedback and reduced the questionnaire length and time to 15 minutes. Hence, the pilot study helped to enhance questionnaire layout, and average completing time before conducting the main study. The pilot study also helped in aligning the questions according to the aim of this research.

Cronbach Alpha was used to measure the reliability of data by measuring the internal consistency of the items. Table 3.3 illustrates that Cronbach alpha overall score was 0.849 and according to Hancock and Mueller (2010), the value of Cronbach Alpha more than 0.70 shows high consistency between the items. Similarly, the Cronbach Alpha score was calculated for entrepreneurial, enterprise, and external factors which were 0.864, 0.872, and 0.925 respectively. It shows that there was no issue of reliability associated with the questionnaire in a pilot study. A similar questionnaire was exploited in the main study.

Table 3.3: Cronbach Alpha for Entrepreneurial, Enterprise, and Environmental Factors

Reliability	Entrepreneurial	Enterprise	Environmental	Overall
Cronbach Alpha	0.864	0.872	0.925	0.849
Number of Items	8	13	7	28

3.8 Main Study

The duration to collect data for the main study took more than the planned time due to the pandemic. The data collection period covered 8 months due to difficulties that occurred as a result of Covid 19. A questionnaire developed on the Google forum was sent by email and posted to almost 4100 strong sampling frames of successful and failed entrepreneurs and any kind of physical contact was avoided due to pandemics.

Compiling the list of the failed businesses was a big struggle for a researcher. First, the pandemic spread chaos and fear among people and caused delays in data collection. Secondly,

it took a long time to generate and organize the list that also increase data collection time. Regardless of the known difficulties in approaching failed SMEs researchers managed to compile an up-to-date list of failed and successful businesses. All enterprises in the collected databases were discretely confirmed in the next step by the researcher to guarantee that they satisfy the conditions and requirements of the research. The link online questionnaire was sent to the participants by post and email which made it easy for them to access the questionnaire through their phone or laptop.

The respondent's participation was enhanced by adopting the electronic mail surveys techniques suggested by Childlow (2009), and Dillman *et al.*, (2009) for increasing respondents' participation. The covering letter was sent to all business owners from the compiled list along with a questionnaire that introduce the respondents to the study. This cover letter aimed to introduce the participants to research objectives, importance, and to provide the web questionnaire link to ensure participation.

A second email was sent to remind the business owners to participate who had not participated yet in the survey. The email also explained the importance of the respondent's participation and the time it would take to complete it. As a result, the response rate was increased.

The cover letter included in the questionnaire also explained that the participant's details would be kept anonymous and confidential by keeping the names and organisation names anonymous to achieve the truthfulness of acquired data. To obtain the trust of respondents the researcher's name, telephone number, and email address was added to the cover letter.

To increase the response rate, the researcher also contacted some business owners through telephone to arrange a phone meeting to complete a questionnaire. The researcher read the questionnaire to the business owners over the phone and sent a copy of the questionnaire to some of them if they wanted to read it themselves. The researcher wrote the responses of the respondents on Google Forum by completing an online questionnaire. This method helped to increase the response rate by offering convenience to the respondents and helped collect rich qualitative data.

A questionnaire was mailed and emailed (in Google forum) to almost 4100 strong sampling frames. After following up 101 responses (4%) from successful entrepreneurs and 108 responses (8%) from failed entrepreneurs were collected. The researcher managed to collect a total of 209 responses in almost 8 months from potential respondents who met the criteria of this study as mentioned in the literature review. It took longer than the planned time to collect

data due to the difficulties mentioned earlier. There were 15 responses excluded from the study as they failed to meet the criteria of the sample. So, in total 209 responses were accepted for the analysis.

3.9 Questionnaire Design

The questionnaires are considered an important tool to collect the primary data and their design and structure of questions can help in collecting more consistent and valid data (Saunders *et al.*, 2012). Therefore, questionnaires play an important role in collecting reliable data.

The questionnaire contains the questions related to failure factors arising from entrepreneurial, enterprise and environmental factors which are linked to influencing the performance of SMEs and contribute to the success or failure of a business in the UK market. The final questionnaire consists of factors proposed by previously discussed academic theories and literature.

The first part of the questionnaire consists of a cover letter which is recognized as a useful piece of paper to motivate participants to take part in a survey. The cover letter gives the introduction of the researcher, discusses the aim of the research and anticipated outcomes of the research. In addition, the cover letter offers clear guidance about completing the questionnaire and some important information related to the time to complete a questionnaire. The letter also provides the contact details of the researcher. Thus, the cover letter helps to build a bridge of trust and confidence between researcher and participants which assists in increasing response rate (Dillman and Chrustian, 2005).

The questionnaire consists of three parts. The first part consists of demographic questions about owners and business characteristics such as age, gender, experience, number of employees, duration of business trade, ownership type, etc. The demographic questions about owners and businesses contain closed-ended multiple-choice questions in the first section. The closed-ended question technique is employed for the first part of the questionnaire as it is easier to administer, quick completion time, and is considered more reliable (Einola and Alvesson, 2020).

The second part of the questionnaire is about the factors derived from the owners' attributes, internal factors, and external factors which influence the SMEs failure in the UK market. These variables have been categorized into entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors to make it easy for the respondent to understand the structure and answer the questions.

The third part of the questionnaire consists of three open-ended questions. These questions helped in collecting detailed data related to respondents' choice to select specific failure factors, what crucial failure factors missing from a questionnaire and in the end seek recommendations. This section offers support to the previously recognised critical failure factors through quantitative data and assists in compiling the qualitative data on the other failure factors and suggests recommendations to reduce the risk of failure.

In the present research, Likert scale questions ordinal in nature are utilized to collect the responses. The questions are measured using a simple five-point liker scale ranging from "very unimportant" (coded 1) to "very important" (coded 5), matching to other studies in the relevant area (Arasti *et al.*, 2014; Saleh, 2015; Okpara and Okpara, 2011).

A Likert scale is a most frequently utilised measure in studies from different subjects. This method is used to identify the agreement level of respondents with a declaration (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). It's suggested that a reasonable level of responses categorized must not exceed more than 9 or less than 3 to minimize the biasness of respondents (Aaker *et al.*, 2007). Therefore, in the present research responses are collected using a five-point Likert scale to make the standardized measurement in the survey. The 7 or 9 points Likert scale has avoided reducing the questionnaire completion time as the questionnaire contains several variables and also 5-point Likert scale offers enough judgment between agreement levels (Saunders *et al.*, 2011).

The questions were constructed based on variables identified from the literature. It's important to highlight that some of the questions were constructed for the sole purpose of the present research. Furthermore, an effective format and design have been selected for the questions to increase the response rate. Dillman (2000) highlights the importance of the first question and suggests that the survey completion depends on it. Saunders *et al.*, (2019) suggest that easy wording needs to be used in questions so the respondents can easily understand and answer them to their best knowledge.

Dillman (2000) proposed that apart from good questions the visual appearance, layout, and language are also equally significant to motivate the participants to complete the survey. According to respondents adding an extra page is more suitable as compared to a cramped questionnaire. In addition, a questionnaire can be made appealing and increase the response rate by using simple wording for each question.

In the present research, the questionnaire is precise, short, and clear. The length of the questionnaire influences the response rate and it's believed that longer questionnaires

discourage respondents to complete the questionnaire. In contrast, a short questionnaire may portray poor-quality research and discourage respondents to participate. According to researchers, a self-administered questionnaire acceptable to respondents is between four to eight A4 pages long. In conclusion, the length of a questionnaire can play an important role in increasing the response rate (Saunders *et al.*, 2011).

3.10 Data Analysis

This research used a mixed-method therefore both qualitative and quantitative data need to be analysed effectively.

This section converse and clarify both types of data analysis.

3.10.a Quantitative Data Analysis

It is vital to organize the data in an appropriate way to interpret and analyse the results after collecting the data. Following the collection of questionnaires, to ensure proper analysis questionnaires are coded and analysed using the Social Science Statistical Package (SPSS). SPSS is a widely used statistical tool in social sciences and this software is also utilized for data management (Saunders *et al.*, 2019; Bryman and Bell, 2011). SPSS assists in the quick data analysis process. This software can import data from any type of file, generate order according to different cases and later use these cases to develop descriptive statistics, tabulated reports, etc. It can perform complex statistical analyses. Another major reason to use SPSS s compared to other analytical tools is simple to use and cost-effective while, the software is complex to use and requires extra training and practice. However, the researcher needed the training to run SPSS and acquired it by joining data analysis training programs and workshops. The other academics also offered their expert opinion in statistical analysis.

It is imperative to prepare data before preceding descriptive data analysis and data cleaning and screening were employed to obtain the data unambiguousness (Pallant, 2013; Creswell, 2008). The coding system is utilized such as for Male = 1, and Female = 2 used in a statement. So, these types of variables can be measured through scores 1 and 2. Before initiating the descriptive data analysis it is central to clean data and get rid of errors mixed up in data while the data collection process. Afterward, each variable was evaluated to complete the data cleaning process. In this process, a review of the limits of the variables was conducted and the range score for each variable was checked.

Furthermore, the researcher investigated the missing data issue and tried to resolve it before data analysis. There are different methods to resolve the issue of missing data through SPSS (Pallant, 2013; Creswell; 2008). In the present research, the missing data cases are excluded as missing data can harm the purpose of the research

There are different types of data including categorical and numerical data. Categorical data signifies features. Therefore, it can be used to explain a person's gender, and language. Nominal data shows separate components and it is used to label variables. Ordinal values embody separate and well-organized units. While, numerical data contribute to measuring with the help of numbers (Barrow, 2013; Howell, 2013).

When variables are categories based on common grounds (in the case of present research failure factors significance in the UK fast food industry) the utilized measure is known as ordinal (Rovai *et al.*, 2013; Gravatter and Wallnau, 2012). The ordinal scale represents a logical or organized relationship between categories (importance) from very unimportant to important. And it involves numerical values (1 to 5) in which a precise numerical amount of specific value has no importance beyond their capability to begin a position over dataset points (Howell, 2013; Brysbaert, 2011; Barrow, 2013).

In the present research, descriptive data were collected to understand and discuss the demographic characteristics of the enterprises and business owners. Similarly, the data discussing the failure factors in the UK fast food industry is ordinal. In this research demographic characteristics (such as age, gender, education, work experience of owners) and enterprise typology (such as the size of the firm, location, turnover, trading duration) are analysed through descriptive statistics (Rovai *et al.*, 2013; Burns and Burns, 2012). To analyse the demographic data in further detail and for contrast, cross-tabulation and frequency analysis are adopted (Rovai *et al.*, 2013; Gravatter and Wallnau, 2012). Hence, employed analysis is descriptive to illustrate the variances between successful businesses and failed businesses via calculating the percentages and frequencies.

3.10. a.1 Factor Analysis

The research instrument developed in the present research has been authenticated by utilizing the factor analysis which assists in reducing a large number of variables to more dense factors however, it cannot be used to identify the differences between the groups or test the hypothesis (Finch, 2019; Pallant, 2013; Coakes, Steed, and Price, 2008). There are two common approaches, confirmatory factor analysis, and exploratory factor analysis. Confirmatory factor

analysis helps to uncover the factor structure of a dataset (Mueller, 2001). On the other hand, exploratory factor analysis is a technique that assists in uncovering the primary structure of a comparatively large set of variables (Finch, 2019; Pallant, 2013; Mueller, 2001).

In the present research, exploratory factor analysis was employed to recognize the structure and relationship amongst the variables (Finch, 2019; Baglin, 2014; Barendse, 2015). This process involves transforming the entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors into new variables and discovering each different factor depending on a set of original items also known as factor components. In starting the data analysis process exploring factor analysis is known very significant. Exploratory factor analysis is used to assess the dimension and structure to reduce the number of variables and help to develop a precise set of factors to evaluate results.

Furthermore, exploratory factor analysis also helps in recognizing the structure of interrelationship between a large number of correlated variables and developing a smaller set of variables as compared to the original set of variables. Subsequently, it will help to generate an understandable and further dense dataset as compared to the original dataset. The most important thing in research is to investigate the relationship between the variables and find the best way to interpret them (Hair *et al.*, 2006). The several considerations in the exploratory factor analysis are discussed in further detail.

The first assumption of implementing the factor analysis on the dataset is using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin test (KMO) and Bartlett's test, which assist in assessing the applicability of the factor analysis through identifying the correlation among variables that helps in recognizing comprehensible factors (Finch, 2019; Mueller, 2001; Fields, 2005). The values of the KMO test which varies from 0 to 1 helps in measuring the frequency of differences in different factors. The KMO scores 1 express a strongly correlated structure between the original variables therefore, this technique helps to develop a set of reliable factors. In contrast, the low KMO score shows a weak pattern structure, and conducting factor analysis would not be very useful (Andy, 2013; Fields, 2005). Kaiser 1974 recommends accepting values greater than 0.5 as barely acceptable. KMO values of less than 0.5 should lead to more data collection or choosing more variables to include (Andy, 2013).

Hutcheson and Sofroniou (1999) defined the scores of the KMO into unlike categories where a KMO score of more than 0.9 means superb, 0.8 to 0.9 means great, 0.7 to 0.8 means are good, and 0.5 to 0.7 means fair. Yet, the importance of Bartlett's test of sphericity cannot be ignored

as the score ($p\text{-value} < .05$) also assists in conducting a detailed factor analysis (Andy, 2013; Fields, 2005). Hence, before conducting factor analysis it is important to run both tests to check the validity of conducting factor analysis.

Factor extraction defines the small set of factors to reveal the relationship between the variables which helps in untying the smallest independent factors and making a choice about the number of factors to be extracted and selecting the model (Andy, 2013; Pallant, 2013). There are different types of factor extraction such as Principal Components & Factors, Generalised Least Squares, Unweighted Least Squares, Maximum Likelihood, Alpha, and Image Factoring (Field, 2005; Andy, 2013). In the present study, Principal Components Analysis is practiced, summarising the information for several factors which is a commonly used method through statistical software.

The factors produced through principal component analysis are the same in numbers as original factor variables. Therefore, to differentiate the variations in the original data a technique is required to control the remaining justifiable factors. The decision of retaining the valuable factors depends on a specific method screen test (Finch, 2019; Field, 2005). This test helps you to discover the point at which the change occurs in the shape and direction converts to horizontal through examining different values in the factors (Pallant, 2013).

The factor loading values helps achieved by extracting the factor based on nominated initial variables. The factor loading values also help to identify the comparative input of the original factor to every extracted factor (Andy, 2013). The factor loading values vary from -1 to 1 and in the analysis, only those values are considered significant which are greater than .40 (Field, 2005).

In the end, an overview of exploratory factor analysis can be obtained through factor rotation and interpretation. The exploratory factor analysis offers a denser set of variables by interpreting the most relevant factors. Furthermore, the factor loading is enhanced and made unique through utilizing factor rotation effectively (Pallant, 2013; Hair *et al.*, 2006). Similarly, the Varimax rotation method is another important technique that can assist in understanding factors (Field, 2005).

3.10.a.2 Correlation

The strength and relationship between the variables have been identified through parametric test Pearson correlation coefficient (r) on the other hand, for the non-parametric statistic, the

Spearman Rank correlation is used. In the Pearson correlation test, the value range between -1 and +1 shows the strength of the relationship between variables while 0 shows there is no correlation between variables. According to Cohen the correlation strength between variables depends on value range such as large = 0.50 - 1.0; medium = 0.30 – 0.49; and small 0.10 – 0.29 (Dunn *et al*, 2017; Pallant, 2011). Furthermore, the correlation between variables can be positive (+) or negative (-) which requires different considerations to direct the relationship between variables (Dunn *et al*, 2017; Pallant, 2011). Pearson correlation also assists in unfolding the strength and direction of a linear relationship between factors extracted and differentiates the extracted factor correlation from factor analysis.

3.10.a.3 Logistic Regression Analysis

In the present research logistic regression analysis is utilized to identify the relationship between the dependent dichotomous variable SME failure, which possibly will be yes or no, and independent factors, entrepreneurial factors, enterprise (internal) factors, and environmental (external) factors. When the dependent variable is dichotomous the logistics regression analysis can be used to compare two groups (Austin and Merlo, 2017). The logistic regression analysis performs two different purposes. First, logistic regression assists in predicting group association through calculating the performance and odd ratio which displays the outcomes. Also, it describes the interrelating relationships and strengths between variables. Furthermore, for the logistic regression analysis, the assumption of a linear relationship between dependent and independent variables is not necessary however, the dependent variable need to be dichotomous and requires a substantial sample size (Hyouun-Ae, 2013).

Thus, logistic regression analysis has been employed to measure the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The coefficient b is used to express each independent variable. This coefficient helps in generating a measurement of the separate sovereign difference in the dependent variable. The regression model gives a probability of 0 and 1 to the dependent variable. Therefore, the dependent variable numerical value is not generated by the logistic regression (Austin and Merlo, 2017).

3.10.a.4 Odds Ratio in Logistic Regression

In the present study, the log odds measurement has been achieved from the b coefficients of the regression equation through SPSS software. In addition, a single component change in the outcome variable defines the change in the average value of a dependent variable. The coefficients b can be found in SPSS in column b called variable in the equation. Logistic

regression analysis computes the alteration in the dependent variables log odds. In the case of a binary variable, the chances of association of the target group are the same as the odds of connection in the target group separated by the odds of the other group. The range of the odds values varies from 0 to infinity (Andy, 2017).

3.10.a.5 Model Fit and the Likelihood Functions

Likelihood can be defined as probability under a stated hypothesis. Two hypotheses are of utmost importance to discuss in logistic regression. The first one is a null hypothesis which happens in logistic regression when the value of all coefficients turns out to be zero. On the other hand, the alternative hypothesis occurs when the value of predictors in the model diverges meaningfully from null to zero (Andy, 2017; Austin and Merlo, 2017).

The likelihood ratio test contains a $2\log$ likelihood ratio. The researcher model with the predictor is considered suggestively dissimilar from the model consisting of constant with a significance value of $p < 0.05$ or lower. It evaluates the enhancement in fit which explanatory variable produced compared with the null model. The significance of the ratio can be measured with Chi-square. Thus, the significance level of less than 5% indicates that independent variables have no increased effect based on their inclusion (Andy, 2017).

3.10.b Qualitative Data Analysis

In the present research qualitative data was compiled through three open-ended questions added at the end of the questionnaire. The qualitative data back the quantitative data that aim to inspect the critical failure factors in the UK fast food industry.

Qualitative data also helped to receive the opinions of business owners about previously identified failure factors. The qualitative data aim to understand the business failure factors in detail and offer a richer picture of business failure factors in the UK fast food retail industry. The qualitative data consists of three open-ended questions which aim to identify the most important failure factors, any other failure factors missing from the present study, and lastly, compile a list of recommendations to avoid failure in the UK fast food industry.

The literature suggests that qualitative data can be analysed based on the significance of the outcome rather than following a standard way to process the qualitative outcomes (Bryman and Bell, 2011; Patton, 2002; Creswell, 2009). Qualitative data analysis can be achieved through arranging big data in themes and categories to make meaning out of it (Saunders *et al.*, 2012).

In the present research thematic analysis is used to analyse the qualitative data with the help of NVivo software. Generally, thematic analysis is applied to a set of interview transcripts or survey responses when the aim is to find out people's views, opinions, knowledge, and experiences from a set of qualitative data. It is a method of analysing qualitative data in which common themes, ideas, and patterns are identified coded, and taken out meaning (Castleberry & Nolen, 2018). The stages involved in analysing qualitative data are discussed in detail as follow:

Firstly, before data analysis data it is important to understand the data and read through it. The initial notes need to be made about the important information at this stage to get familiar with the data. In the second stage, the data need to be coded. Coding can be defined as highlighting the important information in the text and patterns and writing their short labels or code to explain content. At this stage, every response or transcript is explored and important text is highlighted and new codes are developed.

In the next stage, these codes are arranged to identify a pattern among them which helps in creating themes. In general, themes are considered broader than the codes and sometimes combination of several codes helps to develop a theme. It's important to make sure that themes precisely represent the data and certain steps are taken such as comparing themes with the dataset to achieve it. Lastly, a final list of the themes is named and defined.

3.11 Validity and Reliability

It's very significant to emphasize validity and reliability for effectively achieving the aims and objectives of the study. The validity and reliability of the utilized instrument help to shape the merit of the study (Bryman and Bell, 2011). These two factors influence achieving the generalized results. In simple words, validity and reliability reduce the errors and assist in achieving the right answer (Saunders *et al.*, 2012).

Validity defines the association between the research aims, objectives, questions, and research outcomes. In other words, it helps to identify if the research outcome and objectives are aligned with each other. On the other hand, reliability refers to consistency in research findings if repeated employing the same research methodology (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

3.11.a Validity

Validity can be achieved by developing an instrument that satisfies the purpose of creation (Yin, 1994). Research can have errors such as imprecise research measures, poor samples that

influence the validity (Saunders *et al.*, 2007; Pallant, 2013). Gill and Johnson (1997) also shed light on the significance of the validity and states that valid measures will help you to achieve the validity. The use of precise measurement tools by the researcher that is easy to understand to produce accurate outcomes, assist in achieving validity criteria, and avoid vagueness.

The validity of the instruments used to collect the data is assumed through employing the following techniques:

- An intensive literature review was conducted to compile the characteristics used in the questionnaire, therefore, backed by the small business literature.
- The validity was also assured through feedback from industry experts, professionals, and academics.
- A pilot test was utilized.
- The foundation of the questionnaire was previous studies related to SMEs failure factors.
- The researcher tried to use simple wording to avoid any misunderstanding in any of the questions and offered clarification if required.

3.11.b Reliability

Reliability can be defined as a statistical measure that leads to producing generalized results through survey instruments tools (Litwin, 1995; Pallant, 2013). Reliability refers to the degree to which the statistical tools can produce consistent results and shows stability, producing the same results if the instrument is applied in different cases (Cooper and Schindler, 2001; Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2012). In other words, reliability can be achieved through reproducing the same outcomes under similar conditions on all occasions (Bell, 1993; Sekaran, 2003). Thus, the information must offer reliable and unchanging outcomes to reach reliability. The reliability of the research instrument depends on the consistency and significant relationship between responses. Infact it shows the accuracy of different items measurement to explore the same issue (litwin, 1995).

Reliability in the questionnaires can be achieved by developing clear questions which leads to better understanding and receiving correct answers. Serious steps have been taken to enhance the reliability of the research. Firstly, the questionnaire is developed from business failure literature and clear questions are formulated. Different reviewers such as industry experts, statisticians, academics reviewed the questionnaire and passed their comments to enhance it. A pilot study was also conducted based on real business owners from the UK fast food industry

which helped to enhance the instrument along with the data collection method. In more detail, the following steps have been taken to achieve reliability.

- A well-expressed and robust instrument has been employed.
- To avoid misinterpretation during the decoding process vibrant objectives and statements have been utilized.
- An intensive literature review has been conducted to better comprehend the problem.
- The options were given to respond to rate each failure factor based on importance and further asked to identify failure factors missing from this study
- A pilot study has been conducted, and their outcome helped to enhance the validity and reliability.

Furthermore, an internal consistency score is widely used to describe the random errors in scale (Pallant, 2013). The internal consistency score is evaluated through the items of scale to examine similar qualities. Cronbach alpha score which varies from 0 to 1 (positive and minus function) assist to examine the reliability of measuring scale since 1951, such as questionnaire (Pallant, 2013). The scale is considered acceptably consistent with an alpha value of 0.50 and 0.60 within the behavioural and social sciences, however, the required coefficient alpha value is 0.70 in all cases (Hancock and Mueller, 2010).

3.12 Ethics

There are four common ethical principles highlighted by Bryman and Bell (2011) in business research which include, lack of informed consent, deception, harm to respondents, and invasion of privacy. Saunders *et al* (2012) offer further details of the ethical issues in conducting research that needs to be taken into consideration such as respect for others, honesty, and neutrality of the researcher, avoid harm to a participant, participants privacy, right to withdraw partially or completely from research, data confidentiality, participant anonymity, informed consent of the participants, honesty in data analysis and reporting findings, ensuring researcher safety and managing data properly.

The researcher has considered all the ethical issues. This research is planned revised and conducted to guarantee that results offer integrity, worth, and excellence and benefit the society and participants. The researcher follows the research ethical principles and codes of practice for research dealing with human participants of his educational institute (University of West Scotland). Similarly, the researcher also follows the code of practice of other well-known

institutes (University of Cambridge, 2019; London South Bank University, 2019) and professional bodies (Market Research Society, 2019). The main ethical considerations for this study are mentioned below.

3.13 Risks to Participants and Researcher

Throughout conducting research it's important to consider the limitations and hitches. During the data collection period, a pandemic spread all over the world rapidly which was a serious threat to the well-being of participants and researchers. The researcher made some changes in the data collection method to ensure the safety of the researcher and participants by avoiding any physical contact. To minimize any potential risk the questionnaire was formed and distributed through online channels and some of the questionnaires were completed through phone calls.

The participants were followed through email and any kind of physical contact was avoided for the safety of the participants. The participants were followed for any clarification or understanding through phone calls or emails and the researcher made sure to avoid any kind of physical contact. To further diminish any hazards all respondents were over 18 years old, and an informed consent form was included in the questionnaire.

The researcher undertook training workshops about data collection and reporting on delicate matters. The participant identity was kept anonymous and an informed consent form prepared the researcher to manage the hinders and tackle difficult situations.

3.14 Health and Safety

The research was designed and executed to ensure the health and safety of participants and researcher. The factors mentioned under risk are only health and safety issues and there are no other considerable issues.

3.15 Participation and Withdrawal from Research

The respondent can participate voluntarily in the research. Along with the consent form researcher distributed the information sheet with all the relevant information discussing risks, research, and actions related to this research. The participants were offered enough time to comprehend the aim of the research, informed their contribution is voluntary, and benefits of the outcomes. The participants were also informed that they can withdraw at any time deprived

of any consequence. The researcher informed the participants that the research findings will be shared with them which will benefit them in understanding failure factors.

3.16 Information Sheet

An information sheet was sent to the participants with all the information about research aim objectives and research method, the purpose of research, procedures, risks, and benefits of the research. The contact details of the researcher and institute research ethics officer are also provided so the participant could inform about any violation of the research ethic. Plenty of time was specified for the participants to read the information sheet and discuss with pertinent members if required.

3.17 Confidentiality and Anonymity

All the crucial steps are taken by the researcher to ensure the confidentiality and anonymity of the participants. The information collected during this research is kept under great care and the identity of an individual or organisation would not be disclosed publicly under any circumstances. Similarly, the identity of the participants or any information that reveal their identity would be avoided to disclose. To keep the anonymity of the participants, the researcher has used the codes instead of participants' names such as respondents 1, 2, 3, etc. The data will be identified only through a code with personal details kept in a locked file with access only to the researcher keeping it away from unauthorized access. The data will be demolished after five years of completion of this research. The data obtained may be published in a journal or conference paper however, the researcher will make sure to keep participants' names and identities confidential.

3.18 Data Security

The researcher will comply with the Data Protection Act 1998 to collect and store data. The researcher will comply with the University's data protection policy and guidelines and take every step to protect the anonymity and confidentiality of the data. The data will be destroyed after the research aim is achieved. The sensitive information will be kept secret and it will not be disclosed to any party. Only the researcher will have access to the sensitive data. Any information obtained during this study will be kept strictly confidential. The gathered data will be stored in encrypted files and stored in a password-protected laptop. The access to the gathered data will be limited to the researcher and unauthorized access will be avoided by

protecting the files with a password. To assure confidentiality the researcher will also follow the UWS guideline for ethical practices.

Participants will be identified only through code or numbers with personal details kept in a locked file with access only by the researcher. After the successful completion of this study, all the data will be destroyed. The data obtained may be published in journals or conference papers however, the researcher will make sure to keep participants' names and identities confidential.

Overall, all the ethical issues are identified by the researcher, and adequate steps are taken to avoid any ethical issues. Additional legal and ethical issues related to the data collection, or storage are considered carefully by the researcher.

3.19 Limitation of the Research

The present study has limitations as it is communal in any academic work. It is very important to discuss these limitations as they can influence the research findings. These limitations are explained in this section.

The first and most important limitation was the absence of SMEs financial data to evaluate the performance of the participating businesses such as turnover or profitability over a period so it was not possible to measure the performance of SMEs based on financial indicators. Therefore, the performance of the business to be successful or failed was measured based on the business ability of trading during a certain period instead of objective measures. According to the definition employed in present research a business is considered failed if ceases to trade within the first three years and is considered successful if continued to trade for more than three years.

Moreover, there was no official list of successful and failed businesses therefore, the researcher had to compile a list of successful and failed businesses from different sources such as The Gazette, insolvency register, and company house. It was very challenging to compile a list of the fast-food businesses which fulfil the sampling criteria. The data file acquired from the Gazette, insolvency register, and company house was very large and unorganised. The researcher spent some time organising and filtering the data to separate the businesses that fulfil the sampling criteria. As the data was large and unorganised there is a possibility that some of the businesses (successful and failed) are missing from the list and the list does not represent the actual number of successful and failed businesses from London. All the businesses in the

collected databases were discretely confirmed by the researcher to guarantee that they satisfy the conditions and requirements of the study.

This study is precise to one area of retail so, some factors may be more important in some other retail sectors. Focusing on one sector of retail makes the research limited and the failure factors could vary in the other sectors of the retail industry. Therefore, this research emphasizes future research to research different sectors of retail and different industries to generalize the results.

Another important limitation is the geographical area. The present research focused on fast food businesses from London and so, the factors associated with the performance can be different in the other areas of the UK. It was not possible to access all the SMEs in the UK due to limited time and resources.

Furthermore, due to limited time and lack of resources, it was not possible to include all the failure factors found in the literature review. However, the research included an open-ended question investigating any other failure factors missing from this study to make sure the most relevant failure factors related to the fast-food industry could be identified. The recommendation also includes some factors identified through qualitative data. In the previous literature, there is not a single list of agreed factors that influence the performance of a business positively or negatively. Therefore, it was a difficult job to assemble a list of factors influencing business performance. To overcome this issue the researcher focused on factors that were backed by several authors and ignored the others. Although a rigorous literature review was performed, however, some factors may have not been included. Therefore, this study also utilized open-ended questions to identify any other failure factors missing from the literature. The factors identified through qualitative data can be tested in future research to generalise the results.

The researcher also acknowledges that there are numerous methodological limitations such as data collection method mainly depend on one method a questionnaire. The interviews with respondents could have helped to triangulate the findings. However, using more than one data collection method may cause sampling issues, reporting issues, and increase the time and resources required (barney, 2009).

One of the most important limitations of the present research is the fact that it's not possible to find out if the planned person (business owner) completed the questionnaire or whether it was answered by another colloquies or managers. Likewise, there is no way to find out the honesty of responses but then again must count on the goodwill of the participants.

3.20 Conclusion

This chapter discusses all the methodological considerations suitable for the present research. The present research aims to utilise the existing failure factors theories and investigate the UK SMEs failure factors from the fast-food retail industry. Therefore, to achieve the objectives of the research a positivistic approach has been employed.

The deductive approach is utilised as the aim is to test the existing theories in a specific situation in this case on the fast-food retail industry. Following this data collection method and sampling method is discussed in detail. Then, the reliability and validity of the research tool are presented. In this regard, a pilot study and Cronbach alpha have been used. Following this data analysis methods for quantitative and qualitative data are presented to clarify the process and techniques to be utilised during the analysis. In the end, all ethical features are measured and resolved. The next chapter presents the findings.

Chapter 4: Findings of the Research

This chapter discusses and reports the empirical research findings. Firstly, this chapter presents the outcome of the demographic descriptive analysis of the participants and businesses using descriptive statistics. Then exploratory factor analysis is performed, and the reliability of each factor is presented. Following that, Pearson correlation is performed to inspect any relationship between constructed factors. The logistic regression analysis results are offered to analyse the entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors to predict business failure. In the end, for qualitative data thematic analysis results are presented.

Quantitative Data Findings

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

This section explains the demographic characteristics of the participants. The data about different characteristics of the owners such as age, gender, education, experience, and position of the business owners is collected to better understand their profile in the UK fast food industry. This study aims to identify and compare the failure factors according to the perception of successful and unsuccessful entrepreneurs. In this research, the target sample is successful and unsuccessful entrepreneurs.

Figure 4.1 shows that in total 209 responses were collected from small and medium-sized fast food retail stores in the UK through a survey out of which 101 responses were collected from successful entrepreneurs and 108 responses were collected from unsuccessful entrepreneurs. The owners of the UK fast food retail stores are considered the potential sample as they have a better insight into the problems businesses face and offer astute recommendations.

To answer the research question success and failure have been defined. A business will be considered successful if trades for more than three years and failed if went bankrupt within three years (Arasti *et al.*, 2015; Pretorius, 2009).

Figure 4.1: Classification of Businesses

4.1.1 Owners Characteristics

4.1.1.1 Gender of Business Owners

Based on 209 responses received the results indicate the dominance of the successful male (91%) participants which is much higher than their female counterparts, representing 9% of the total population (see figure 4.2). Similarly, the number of failed male participants is higher than the failed female participant with 90% and 10% respectively. So, most responses were collected from males in both categories.

Figure 4.2: Gender Results

4.1.1.2 Age of Business Owners

The age of the successful and failed entrepreneurs has been divided into five groups. Figure 4.3 shows that most of the participants belonged to the age group of 35 - 44 with 68 replies out of which 36 responses were collected from successful entrepreneurs while 32 responses came from unsuccessful business owners followed by the age group of 45 to 54 with 64 responses. In addition, results for age group 25 - 34 show that number of unsuccessful business owners is (45) higher than successful business owners with 19 responses. The smaller number of responses came from the age group 55+ with 13 responses 10 from successful and 3 from unsuccessful business owners in the UK fast food industry. Similarly, no response was collected from the age group 18 – 24.

Figure 4.3: Age of Business Owners

4.1.1.3 Education Level of Owners

Regarding the level of education, nine different levels were used to collect the responses. Figure 4.4 shows that most of the responses for successful business owners came from, bachelor's degree holders, no qualification, A-Levels or equivalent, primary education and diploma holders with 32%, 19%, 16%, 13%, and 10%, respectively. The number of responses was low from people with professional qualifications (4%), and GCSEs (5%). On the other hand, in the case of unsuccessful business owners, most of the participants attained a low level of education such as 26% of participants obtained primary education, 21% A-Levels, and 12%

owners obtained no education at all. Furthermore, 18% of participants obtained a bachelor's degree, 2% master's degrees, and only one participant hold a Ph.D. degree. Based on the data, successful entrepreneurs hold higher qualifications while unsuccessful entrepreneurs have a low level of education.

Figure 4.4: Education Level of Owner

4.1.1.4 Experience

The finding regarding previous experience shows that a higher number of successful entrepreneurs had previously owned a business, while the higher number of unsuccessful business owners were those participants with fast related experience or no previous experience (see figure 4.5). Similarly, the lowest response rate in successful businesses came from people with no experience 3% while, a low response rate was received from unsuccessful business owners who owned a business with an 8% response rate.

Figure 4.5: Experience of Owners

4.1.1.5 Ownership Type

The position of the respondents was divided into three groups sole owners, managers, and business partnership. The responses from the managers were considered invalid as only the business owners were considered the main participants of the study. The result in figure 4.6 shows that most of the responses were collected from the sole owners 81% in the case of successful business owners and 63% unsuccessful business owners. In contrast, 19% of successful business owners owned a business in partnership, and similarly, 37% in the case of unsuccessful businesses. The result shows that business owners with partnerships are more likely to fail as compared to sole business owners.

Figure 4.6: Ownership Types

In general, the average participant (successful) in this research is male, over 34 years of age, educated to a minimum degree level, owned a business, or have working experience in the UK fast food industry. On the other hand, the average participant (unsuccessful) in this research is male, 25 – 34 years of age, with no or low education, and holds no previous experience or entrepreneurial activity. The summary of the owner’s demographics can be seen in the table below.

Table 4.1: Summary of Owners Demographics

Personal Variables	Successful Frequency (n=101)	Percent	Unsuccessful Frequency (n=108)	Percent
Gender				
Male	92	91%	97	90%
Female	9	9%	11	10%
Age				
18-24	0	0%	0	0%
25-34	19	19%	45	41%
35-44	36	35%	32	30%

45-54	36	36%	28	26%
55+	10	10%	3	3%
Education				
No Education	21	19%	13	12%
Primary Education Certificate	13	13%	28	26%
GCSEs or Equivalent	5	5%	12	11%
A-Levels or Equivalent	16	16%	23	21%
Diploma	9	10%	9	9%
Bachelor's Degree	33	32%	20	18%
Master's Degree	0	0%	2	2%
PhD	0	0%	1	1%
Professional Qualifications	4	4%	0	0%
Experience				
No Experience	3	3%	23	21%
Owned a Business	49	49%	9	8%
Government/Public Sector	9	9%	15	14%
Fast Food related/ Managerial	40	40%	61	57%
Other	0	0%	0	0%
Ownership Type				
Sole Owner	82	81%	68	63%
Manager	0	0%	0	0%
Business Partnership	19	19%	40	37%
Other	0	0%	0	0%

4.1.2 SMEs Characteristics

This section discusses the characteristics of the participating businesses. In this study, the data was collected about different characteristics of the SMEs such as the age of business, location, number of employees, and an annual turnover of the firms operating in the UK fast food retail industry to gain a better understanding of the firms and fulfil sample criteria.

4.1.2.1 Age of Business

SMEs trade duration benefits in defining their performance as explained in chapter 2. Any business operating for more than three years was considered successful. Similarly, a business is considered failed, filed bankruptcy within the first three years of their operation since it is not possible to access the financial data or any other performance indication-based data. The result in figure 4.7 shows that of most of the unsuccessful participating businesses 42% failed between 1 – 2 years and 33% between 2 – 3 years. The failure rate was comparatively low in early-stage less than one year with a 25% failure rate.

Figure 4.7: Age of Business

4.1.2.2 Size of Business

The present study reflects a good picture of SMEs. Figure 4.8 shows that the majority of businesses successful or unsuccessful have less than 5 employees. However, only 13% of successful and 8% failed businesses have more than 10 employees. All the businesses have

employees less than 50 and those companies with a large number of employees (more than sample criteria) were excluded from this study.

Figure 4.8: Business Size

4.1.2.3 Annual Turnover

The annual turnover of each business is also recorded and only those companies are included in this study with an annual turnover of less than £2 million. Any company with an annual turnover of more than £2 million was excluded from the study. Similarly, this study emphasizes the SMEs operating in London. The descriptive result in figure 4.9 shows that all the participating businesses annual turnover was less than £2 million.

Figure 4.9: Annual Turnover

Overall, the average participating business (successful) in this research is established business trading for more than three years, located in London, with an average turnover of less than £2 million, with an average of 5 – 50 employees. While the average participating business (unsuccessful) in this research is new business trading for 1 - 3 years, located in London, with an average turnover of less than £2 million, and employing 5 – 10 workers. The summary of the SMEs demographics can be seen in the table below.

Table 4.2: Summary of SMEs Demographics

Organisational Variables	Frequency Successful (n=103)	Percent %	Frequency Unsuccessful (n=105)	Percent %
Trade Duration				
Less than 1 years	0	0%	27	25%
Between 1 and 2 years	0	0%	45	42%
Between 2 and 3 years	0	0%	36	33%
More than 3 years	101	100%	0	0%

Annual Turnover				
Less than £2 million	101	100%	108	100%
£2 million- £6 million	0	0%	0	0%
£6 million- £25.9 million	0	0%	0	0%
More than £25.9 million	0	0%	0	0%
Business Size				
Less than 5	43	43%	52	48%
6-10	45	44%	47	44%
11-50	13	13%	9	8%
51-250	0	0%	0	0%

4.2 Exploratory Factor Analysis

This part discusses the results of exploratory factor analysis for entrepreneurial, enterprise, and external environments. The entrepreneurial aspect is measured by 9 items, enterprise with 15 items, and external environment with 9 items. The construct of the study has been explained through different methods. The new factors were extracted with the help of the principal component method in SPSS. The degree of relationship between the resulting factors is discovered through measuring the correlation. Lastly, for each factor, the reliability is also calculated.

4.2.1 Exploratory factor Analysis for the Entrepreneurial Aspect

The first assumption of implementing the factor analysis on the dataset is utilizing the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin test (KMO) and Bartlett's test, which assist in assessing the applicability of the factor analysis through identifying the correlation among variables helps in recognizing comprehensible factors. Therefore, KMO and Bartlett's test is utilized to assess the applicability of the factor analysis in the present study. After running the KMO test in SPSS the statistic was found to be 0.773 (> 0.50) and the result of the sphericity test shows the significant value (P-value < 0.001) which specifies that exploratory factor analysis is suitable in the present study.

Factor analysis helps to reduce the number of factors from many factors to make the data more meaningful and easier to interpret. It is important to discuss the two criteria on which the extraction of the entrepreneurial factor depends. The first thing which needs to be considered is observing the total variance explained table to approve mechanisms with an eigenvalue of more than one. Secondly, individual factors need to contain 3 items and any component less than three items required a rotation once more (Hancock, Stapleton, and Mueller, 2019). As suggested by the conceptual framework (see chapter three) 3 factors were developed based on the test (see Appendix 1).

Table 4.3: Total Variance Explained for Entrepreneurial Factor

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		Cumulative %	Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings
	Total	% Of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% Of Variance		Total
1	4.332	48.129	48.129	4.332	48.129	48.129	3.334
2	2.242	24.912	73.042	2.242	24.912	73.042	3.260
3	2.182	24.245	97.286	2.182	24.245	97.286	3.180

The table of total variance explained shows the initial eigenvalues and after the extraction eigenvalues for three linear factors. Table 4.3 discuss the eigenvalue clarified eigenvalue with a percentage of variance. It can be seen in the table from a percentage of variance column that the first factor displays more variance (48.129%) as compared to the second (24.912%) and

third factor (24.245%). Similarly, after the rotation, the Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings column shows that the first factor displays more scores (3.334) as compared to the second (3.260) and third factor (3.180). The results indicate that these factors are a decent reflection of the entrepreneurial factors. The Principal Component Analysis produced an explanation of each entrepreneurial factor as conversed in the following section.

4.2.1.1 Owner’s Experience Factor (OPE)

Three items were used with loading scores between 0.999 and 0.992 to measure the owner's experience factor (OE). Each item is ranked based on mean scores. The third item has the highest mean score of 4.2679. The mean score for the first and second items is 4.263 and 4.258 as shown in table (4.4).

Table 4.4: Description of Owners Experience Factor

Owners Experience Component	Loading	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
Prior Work Experience	0.999	4.2632	0.89477	2
Inadequate Experience	0.992	4.2584	0.89348	3
Poor Industry Experience	0.996	4.2679	0.89603	1

4.2.1.2 Poor Personal Traits of Entrepreneurs (PTE)

The poor personal traits of entrepreneurs (PTE) factor contain 3 items arranged in compliance with their respective influence via factor loading (See Table 4.5). The loading score for three items of entrepreneurs is between 0.984 to 0.991. The ranking of the items depends on the mean score. It is noted that lack of motivation for continuation of a job ranks 1st due to a higher mean score of 2.9330. The lack of locus of control ranks second on the table with a mean score of 2.9282. While lack of need for achievement item scored 2.9234 and secured third place in the table.

Table 4.5: Description of Owners Poor Personal Traits Factor

Entrepreneurs Poor Personal Traits Component	Loading	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
Lack of Need for Achievement	0.984	2.9234	1.14097	3
Lack of Locus of Control	0.991	2.9282	1.13494	2
Lack of Motivation for Continuation of Job	0.989	2.9330	1.12887	1

4.2.1.3 Owners Inappropriate Personal Skills (OIPS)

Owners inappropriate personal skills factor contain 3 items arranged in compliance with their respective influence via factor loading. Each item is ranked based on mean scores and the loading score for three items is between 0.956 and 0.990. It is noted that poor networking skills rank 1st due to a higher mean score of 4.1053. The lack of poor management skills ranks second on the table with a mean score of 4.09. While the third item poor marketing skills has the lowest mean score of 4.08 and secured third place in the table.

Table 4.6: Description of Owners Poor Capabilities

Entrepreneurs Personal Traits Component	Loading	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
Poor Marketing Skills	0.973	4.0766	0.99705	3
Poor Networking Skills	0.990	4.1053	0.96994	1

Poor Management Skills	0.956	4.0861	0.96189	2
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4.2.1.4 Description of the Entrepreneurial Factor

In the entrepreneurial factors ranking of the items depends on the mean score. The owner's experience OE score is higher with a mean score of 4.3 as compared to, the poor skills of entrepreneurs mean score of 4.1 and poor personal traits of entrepreneurs PTE score of 2.9 (See Table 4.7).

Table 4.7: Ranking of Entrepreneurial Factor

Factors	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
Owner's Experience Factor, (OE)	4.2632	0.89476	1
Poor Personal Traits of Entrepreneurs, (PPTE)	2.9282	1.13493	3
Poor Skills of Entrepreneurs, (PSE)	4.0894	0.976294	2

4.2.1.5 Reliability of Entrepreneurial Factors

Table 15 shows the internal consistency of the entrepreneurial factors through Cronbach's alpha scores. The Cronbach's alpha score shows that there is a good internal consistency as the score for each factor surpasses the recognized value of 0.60 (Malhotra, 1993). The alpha score shows decent reliability depending on a score between 0.996 to 0.972.

Table 4.8: The Reliability of Entrepreneurial Factors

Entrepreneurial Factors	Items	Cronbach's Alpha Score
Owner's Experience Factor, (OE)	3	0.996
Poor Personal Traits of Entrepreneurs, (PPTE)	3	0.988

Poor Skills of Entrepreneurs, (PSE)	3	0.972
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4.2.2 Exploratory Factor Analysis for Enterprise Aspect

The KMO and Bartlett's test is utilized to assess the applicability of the factor analysis in the present study. After running the KMO test in SPSS the statistic was found to be 0.784 (> 0.50) and the result of the sphericity test shows the significant value (P-value <.001) which specifies exploratory factor analysis can be utilized for enterprise factors. Factor analysis helps to reduce the number of factors from a large number of factors to make the data more meaningful and easier to interpret. It is important to discuss the two criteria on which the extraction of the entrepreneurial factor depends.

The first thing which needs to be considered is observing the total variance explained table to approve mechanisms with an eigenvalue of more than one. Secondly, individual factors need to contain 3 items and any component less than three items required a rotation once more (Hancock, Stapleton, and Mueller, 2019). As suggested by the conceptual framework (see chapter three) four factors have been constructed based on the test (see appendix 1).

Table 4.9: Total Variance Explained for Enterprise Environment

Initial Eigenvalues				Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		Cumulative %	Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings
Component	Total	% Of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% Of Variance		Total
1	5.673	37.823	37.823	5.673	37.823	37.823	5.294
2	3.039	20.261	58.084	3.039	20.261	58.084	2.982
3	2.900	19.336	77.420	2.900	19.336	77.420	3.095
4	2.135	14.231	91.651	2.135	14.231	91.651	3.533

The table of total variance explained demonstrates the initial eigenvalues and after the extraction eigenvalues for four linear factors. Table 4.9 discuss the eigenvalue clarified eigenvalue with a percentage of variance. Furthermore, it can be seen in the table from a percentage of variance column that the first factor displays more variance (37.823%) as compared to the second (20.261%), the third factor (19.336%), and the fourth factor (14.231%). Similarly, after the rotation, the Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings column shows that the first factor contains the highest score (5.294) as compared to the remaining factors (2.982, 3.095%, 3.533%). The results indicate that these factors are a decent reflection of the enterprise factor as the total variance of 5 variables is over 60 (Pallant, 2013). The Principal Component Analysis produced an explanation of each entrepreneurial factor as conversed in the following section.

4.2.2.1 Business Planning Factor (PBP)

The business planning (BP) factor contains 3 items arranged in compliance with their respective influence via factor loading. Each item is ranked based on mean scores and the loading score for three items is between 0.981 and 0.987. It is noted that alternative business plan to overcome emergency changes ranks 1st due to a higher mean score of 4.26. The business plan means the score is 4.24 and it ranks second on the table. While the third item clear direction to run a business has a mean score of 4.22 and secured third place in the table.

Table 4.10: Description Business Planning

Business Planning Component	Loading	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
Business Plan	.981	4.2392	.79069	2
Alternative Business Plan to overcome Emergency Changes	.987	4.2584	.81467	1
Clear Direction to Run Business	.986	4.2249	.82167	3

4.2.2.2 Business Location Factor (PBL)

The business location (BL) factor contains 3 items arranged in compliance with their respective influence via factor loading (See Table 4.11). Each item is ranked based on mean scores and the loading score for three items is between 0.990 and 0.993. It is noted that prime location ranks 1st due to a higher mean score of 4.2488. The location with high footfall means the score is 4.24 and ranks second on the table. While the third element location suitable for business has the lowest mean score of 4.2153 and secured third place in the table.

Table 4.11: Description of business location Factor

Business Location Component	Loading	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
Location with high Footfall	.990	4.2392	.98556	2
Location Suitable for Business	.993	4.2153	.97889	3
Prime Location	.990	4.2488	.98318	1

4.2.2.3 Marketing and Management Factor (MM)

The marketing and management (MM) factor contains 6 items arranged in compliance with their respective influence via factor loading (See Table 4.12). Each item is ranked based on mean scores and the loading score for six items is between 0.860 and 0.933. It is noted that advertisement through the internet and advertisement and promotion has a higher mean score of 4.2584 as compared to the rest of the items. Social media marketing and effective management have a mean score of 4.2010. It can be seen that knowledge of managerial tasks mean score is 4.181 and rank 5th on the table. Lastly, good control has the lowest mean score of 4.1770.

Table 4.12: Description of Marketing and Management Factor

Marketing and Management Component	Loading	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
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Traditional Marketing and Advertisement	0.872	4.2584	0.87719	2
Advertisement through Internet	0.860	4.2584	0.87719	1
Social Media marketing	0.933	4.2010	0.83654	3
Effective Management	0.933	4.2010	0.83654	4
Knowledge of Managerial Tasks	0.909	4.1818	0.81184	5
Good Control	0.907	4.1770	0.80994	6

4.2.2.4 Employees Competency Factor (EC)

The employee competency (EC) factor contains items arranged in compliance with their respective influence via factor loading (See Table 4.13). The loading score for these three items is between 0.982 to 0.993. It is noted that skilled staff ranks 1st due to a higher mean score of 4.1531. The high staff retention and motivated staff contain the same mean score of 4.1435.

Table 4.13: Description of Employees Competency Factor

Employees Issues Component	Loading	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
Motivated Staff	0.991	4.1435	.78964	3
Skilled Staff	0.993	4.1531	.79391	1
Staff Retention	0.982	4.1435	.80770	2

4.2.2.5 Description of the Enterprise Factor

In the enterprise factors ranking of the items depends on the mean score. It's clear that poor business planning score is higher with a mean score of 4.24 on the other hand, business location

means the score is 4.23, marketing and management factor mean score is 4.21, and employees' competency score lowest 4.16 (see Table 4.14).

Table 4.14: Ranking of Enterprise Factor

Factors	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
Business Planning	4.2408	0.8090	1
Business Location	4.2345	0.9825	2
Marketing and Management	4.2129	0.84154	3
Employees Competency	4.1467	0.7971	4

4.2.2.6 Reliability of Enterprise Factors

Table 22 shows the internal consistency of the enterprise factors through Cronbach's alpha scores. The Cronbach's alpha score shows that there is a good internal consistency as the score for each factor surpasses the recognized value of 0.60 (Malhotra, 1993). The alpha score shows decent reliability depending on a score between 0.955 to 0.992.

Table 4.15: The Reliability of Enterprise Factors

Enterprise Factors	Items	Cronbach's Alpha Score
Business Planning	3	0.984
Business Location	3	0.992
Marketing and Management	6	0.955
Employees Competency	3	0.990

4.2.3 Exploratory Factor Analysis for Environmental Factors

KMO test and Bartlett's test are utilized to assess the applicability of the factor analysis in the present study for external environment factors. After running the KMO test in SPSS the statistic

was found to be 0.790 (> 0.50) and the result of the sphericity test shows the (P-value $<.001$) which specify exploratory factor analysis can be utilised for environmental factors. Factor analysis helps to reduce the number of factors from a large number of factors to make the data more meaningful and easier to interpret. It is important to discuss the two criteria on which the extraction of the external environmental factor depends.

The first thing which needs to be considered is observing the total variance explained table to approve mechanisms with an eigenvalue of more than one. Secondly, individual factors need to contain 3 items and any component less than three items required a rotation once more (Hancock, Stapleton, and Mueller, 2019). As suggested by the conceptual framework (see chapter three) three factors have been constructed based on the test (see appendix 1).

Table 4.16: Total Variance Clarified for Environmental Environment

Initial Eigenvalues				Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		Cumulative	Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings
Component	Total	% Of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% Of Variance	%	Total
1	4.274	47.492	47.492	4.274	47.492	47.492	3.470
2	2.716	30.180	77.672	2.716	30.180	77.672	3.065
3	1.668	18.535	96.206	1.668	18.535	96.206	3.315

The table of total variance explained demonstrates the initial eigenvalues and after the extraction eigenvalues for two linear factors. Table 4.16 discuss the eigenvalue clarified eigenvalue with a percentage of variance. Furthermore, it can be seen in the table from a percentage of variance column that the first factor displays more variance (47.492%) as compared to the second (30.180%) and third factor (18.535). Similarly, after the rotation, the

Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings column shows that the first factor contains the higher score (3.470) as compared to the second factor (3.065) and third factor (3.315). The results indicate that these factors are a decent reflection of the enterprise factor as the total variance of these five factors is over 60 (Pallant, 2013). The Principal Component Analysis produced an explanation of each external or environmental factor as conversed in the following section.

4.2.3.1 Inappropriate Government Policies Factor (IGP)

The Inappropriate government policies (IGP) factor contains 3 items arranged in compliance with their respective influence via factor loading. Each item is ranked based on mean scores and the loading score for three items is between 0.984 and 0.996. It is noted that poor government policies rank 1st due to a higher mean score of 4.3349. Lack of government support to entrepreneurs has a mean score of 4.3348 and ranks second on the table. While the second item high government taxes have the lowest mean score of 4.3158 and secured third place in the table.

Table 4.17: Description Inappropriate Political Policies

Inappropriate Government Policies Component	Loading	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
Poor Government Policies	0.996	4.3349	0.92132	1
High Government Taxes	0.995	4.3158	0.91766	3
Lack of Government Support to Entrepreneur	0.984	4.3348	0.92132	2

4.2.3.2 Inappropriate Economic Conditions Factor (IEC)

Inappropriate economic conditions (IEC) factor contains 3 items arranged in compliance with their respective influence via factor loading (See Table 4.18). The loading score for these three items is between 0.964 to 0.997. It is noted that the high-interest rate ranks 1st due to a higher mean score of 4.1196. The unstable economic environment means score is 4.114 and ranks

second on the table. While the third item poor economic growth scored 4.1053 and secured third place in the table.

Table 4.18: Description of Economic Issues Factor

Employees Issues Component	Loading	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
High-Interest Rate	0.964	4.1196	1.06520	1
Poor Economic Growth	0.995	4.1053	1.03237	3
Unstable Economic Environment	0.997	4.1148	1.03600	2

4.2.3.3 Intense Competition factor (IC)

The intense competition (IC) factor contains 3 items arranged in compliance with their respective influence via factor loading. Each item is ranked based on mean scores and the loading score for three items is between 0.951 and 0.978. It is noted that intense competition rank 1st due to a higher mean score of 3.9665. The no product differentiation ranks second on the table with a mean score of 3.9426. While the third item international competitors and high quality of their products have lowest mean score 3.9234 and secured the third place in the table.

Table 4.19:

Table 4.19: Description Intense Competition

Intense Competition Component	Loading	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
Intense Competition	0.978	3.9665	1.03489	1
International Competitors and High Quality of their Products	0.951	3.9234	1.02557	3
No Product Differentiation	0.962	3.9426	1.04078	2

4.2.3.4 Description of External or Environmental Factors

The ranking of the environmental factors of the items depends on the mean score. It's clear that the intense competition score is higher with a mean score of 4.3 on the other hand, the economic issues mean score is 4.1 and inappropriate political policies score the lowest 3.9 (see Table 4.20).

Table 4.20: Ranking of External Factors

Factors	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
Intense Competition	4.3285	0.92010	1
Inappropriate economic conditions	4.1132	1.0445	2
Inappropriate Political Policies	3.9442	1.03375	3

4.2.3.5 Reliability of the External or Environmental Factors

Table 28 shows the internal consistency of the external factors through Cronbach's alpha scores. The Cronbach's alpha score shows that there is a good internal consistency as the score for each factor surpasses the recognized value of 0.60 (Malhotra, 1993). The alpha score shows decent reliability depending on a score between 0.962 to 0.992.

Table 4.21: The Reliability of External Factors

Environmental Factors	No of items	Cronbach's Alpha Score
Inappropriate Government Policies	3	0.992
Inappropriate economic conditions	3	0.985
Intense Competition	3	0.962

4.3 Correlations Analysis Between the Constructed Factors

Bivariate correlation analysis is conducted to inspect any relationship between constructed factors. The strength of the relationship between the factor is recognized through the coefficient of the correlation and it can range from -1.00 to +1.00 (Pallant, 2007). Cohan (1988) provided the following guidelines to interpret the correlation matrix value, $r = 0.10$ to 0.29 minor association, $r = 0.30$ to 0.49 average association, $r = 0.50$ to 1.0 high association.

The Pearson (rho) correlation coefficient reveals the relationship between overall factor variables and shows that owners previous experience factor (OE) value ($r = 0.246$, $p < 0.01$) and owners' poor traits (OT), have a significant but small positive correlation which proposes that with more owners experience they tend to focus more on personal traits. In addition, the owner's experience factor (OE) and owners' poor skill (OPS) ($r = 0.250$, $p < 0.01$) also persist a small correlation. In other words, an increase in owners' experience assists in enhancing personal skills in entrepreneurs.

A small association exists between the owner experience and marketing and management factor ($r = 0.220$, $p < 0.01$). It means that substantial owner experience will increase the importance of marketing and management factor. Similarly, a small and significant positive experience exists in owner experience and employees' competency (EC) ($r = 0.278$, $p < 0.01$). It shows that the more the owner has experienced more owners pay attention to employees' competency.

A small association exist between owners' poor traits (OPT) and owners' skills (OS) ($r = 0.229$, $p < 0.01$). It shows that owners' trait has a positive influence on owners' skills. A small and positive correlation was found between the owners' poor traits (OPT) and business planning (BP) ($r = 0.145$, $p < 0.05$) and competition (IC) ($r = 0.141$, $p < 0.05$). It means that with an increase in owners' traits the emphasis on business planning and competition increase. Likewise, owners' traits have a small positive and significant relationship with business location (BL) ($r = 0.178$, $p < 0.05$). It indicates that with enhanced owner personal traits the focus on business location factor increases.

Moreover, a medium level significant relationship found between business location (BL) and marketing and management (MM) ($r = 0.334$, $p < 0.01$). It shows that a better business location will enhance marketing and management. Similarly, there is a large level of positive significant correlation between business location (BL) and intense competition (IC) ($r = 0.669$, $p < 0.01$). So, business location influences the intensity of competition.

Marketing and Management (MM) and employee's competency (EC) ($r = .162, p < 0.05$) revealed a significant positive relationship. It shows that with improvement in marketing and management role the employees' competency also improve. Moreover, the correlation coefficient value for marketing and management factors revealed a small correlation with competition (IC) ($r=0.277, p<0.01$). These outcomes specify that marketing and management factors influence the competition factor.

Furthermore, a medium and positive significant correlation is found between Inappropriate government policies (IGP) and Inappropriate economic conditions (IEC) ($r=0.409, p<0.01$). It revealed political factors influence the economic factor (ECF).

The results of spearman's correlation analysis show that majority of the correlation between different factors is low which proposes the nonappearance of multi-collinearity between the failure factors.

Table 4.22: Spearman (rho) Correlation

		PPE	PPT	PES	PBP	PBL	PMM	EI	PEI	PI	ICC
OE	Pearson Correlation	1	.246	.250	.062	.067	.220	.278	-.100	.117	.103
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.376	.334	.001	.000	.149	.093	.139
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
PPT	Correlation Coefficient	.246	1	.229	.145	.178	.111	.104	.141	.007	.020
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.001	.036	.010	.110	.133	.042	.924	.771
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
PES	Correlation Coefficient	.250	.229	1	-.078	.106	.050	.029	.029	-.047	.052
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.001		.262	.128	.468	.672	.679	.502	.454
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
BP	Correlation Coefficient	.062	.145	-.078	1	.135	.025	.068	-.041	.037	.022
	Sig. (2-tailed)										
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.376	.036	.262		.052	.718	.325	.555	.598	.748
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
BL	Correlation Coefficient	.067	.178	.106	.135	1	.344	.031	.669	.100	.076
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.334	.010	.128	.052		.000	.654	.000	.150	.277
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
MM	Correlation Coefficient	.220	.111	.050	.025	.344	1	.162	.277	.031	-.033
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.110	.468	.718	.000		.019	.000	.659	.640
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
EC	Correlation Coefficient	.278	.104	.029	.068	.031	.162	1	.022	.050	.098
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.133	.672	.325	.654	.019		.755	.472	.158
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
IEC	Correlation Coefficient	-	.141	.029	-.041	.669	.277	.022	1	.162	.108
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.149	.042	.679	.555	.000	.000	.755		.019	.118
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
IGP	Correlation Coefficient	.117	.007	-.047	.037	.100	.031	.050	.162	1	.409
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.093	.924	.502	.598	.150	.659	.472	.019		.000
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
IC	Correlation Coefficient	.103	.020	.052	.022	.076	-.033	.098	.108	.409	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.139	.771	.454	.748	.277	.640	.158	.118	.000	
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209

4.4 Logistics Regression Analysis

In the present study logistic regression analysis is utilized to analyse the entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors to predict business failure. The logistic regression analysis has employed as the dependent variable is dichotomous (i.e., failure either yes or no). The dependent factor is a business failure while the independent variables are entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors which are discussed in detail in chapter 3. In this study dependent, variable business failure is measured based on bankruptcy. The businesses are classified as a failure if they went bankrupt within three years, on the other hand, businesses are considered successful if continued to operate for more than three years (Arasti *et al.*, 2012). This definition is adopted in the present study to run the multiple regression analysis to develop the business failure prediction model and test the hypotheses developed in chapter 3. Accordingly, the labelling for the dependent variable is in this manner:

0 (No): business success (it has not ceased to operate for more than three years)

1 (Yes): business failure (it has ceased to operate within first three years)

The first independent factor is an entrepreneurial factor which includes all the factors relevant to the business owners such as gender (GEN), owners age (AGEO), owners previous experience (OE), owner education level (EDU), ownership type (OT), poor personal traits (PPT), and poor owners' skills (POS). The second independent factor is associated with business internal factors which include the size of the business (NOE), business planning (BP), business location (BL), marketing and management (MM), and the employee's competencies (EC).

The third and last independent factor encapsulates environmental factors such as level of competition (IC), Inappropriate government policies (IGP), and Inappropriate economic conditions (IEC).

Table 4.23: Logistic Regression Model Test Results

Factors	B	p-value	Exp (B)	95% for EXP (B)	
				Lower	Upper
Gender	0.80	0.885	1.083	0.336	3.205
Age	0.137	0.453	1.147	0.802	1.641

Education Level of Owners	-0.104	0.222	0.901	0.763	1.065
Size of Business	-0.274	0.272	0.761	0.467	1.239
Kind of Ownership	0.500	0.009	1.648	1.133	2.398
Owners Experience	-0.439	0.009	0.645	0.463	0.898
Poor Personal Traits	0.087	0.581	1.091	.800	1.489
Poor Owner Skills	0.447	0.021	1.564	1.069	2.288
Business Planning	-0.536	0.22	0.585	0.370	0.926
Business Location	-0.553	0.023	0.575	0.358	0.925
Marketing and Management	-0.506	0.049	.603	.363	1.000
Employees Competency	-0.323	0.168	0.724	0.457	1.146
Inappropriate Economic Condition	0.296	0.258	1.345	0.810	2.233
Inappropriate Government Policies	-0.107	0.542	0.898	0.636	1.268
Intense Competition	-0.363	0.017	0.695	0.516	0.936
Constant	6.961	.002	1054.9		
Model Test Results					
-2 Log Likelihood	230.5				
Model Chi-square	59.0				
Model p-value	< 0.001				
Cox & Snell R Square	0.246				
Nagelkerke R Square	0.328				
Hosmer and Lemeshow Test Significant	0.717				
Classification Results					
Failed (No) Successful	69.3%				
Failed (Yes) Unsuccessful	71.3%				
Overall Percentage	70.3%				

The results of logistic regression analysis in table 4.23 indicate the relationship of several independent factors along with the likelihood of respondent's business failed or not (see Appendix, 6).

In the logistic regression model, the value used is in the log-odds unit. The prediction equation is as follow:

Log (p (probability)/1-p) =

6.961 + 0.80 Gender + 0.137 Age of owner – 0.104 Owner Qualification – 0.274 Size of Business + 0.500 Kind of ownership – 0.439 Owner Experience + 0.087 Poor Personal Traits + 0.447 Poor Owner Skills – 0.536 Business Planning – 0.553 Business Location – 0.506 Marketing and Management – 0.323 Employees Competency + 0.296 Inappropriate Economic condition – 0.107 Inappropriate Government Policies – 0.365 Intense Competition.

The whole model which contains all the independent variables is statistically significant with $\chi^2 (15, N209) = 59.0$ value of $p < 0.05$ ($p=0.00$) specify that model can differentiate between respondents who failed (Unsuccessful businesses) and those who had not failed (Successful business).

The model as a whole classified 70.3% of cases and elucidated the between 24.6% (Cox & Snell R Square) and 32.8% (Nagelkerke R Square) of the variance of business failure.

Nevertheless, the model has a better ability to predict the businesses that failed (at 71.3%) as compared to businesses that did not fail (69.3%). Table 4.23 shows that 7 independent variables are statistically significant to business failure with $p < 0.05$. These factors are as follow:

1. Kind of Ownership (KO)
2. Owners Experience (OE)
3. Poor Owner Skills (POS)
4. Business Planning (BP)
5. Business Location (BL)
6. Marketing and Management (MM)
7. Intense Competition (IC)

4.5 Hypothesis Test

H1: Male gender is negatively and significantly related to SMEs failure, where the male gender is less likely to fail as compared to the female gender in the UK fast food industry.

The hypothesis was tested by comparing the gender of owners to predict how likely a gender group tends to fail. The gender p-value ($B = 0.80$, $p = 0.885$) shows that there is no significant association between gender and business failure in the UK fast food industry. This H1 is rejected (see Table 4.23).

H2: Older age of entrepreneurs is negatively and significantly linked to business failure, where the age of entrepreneurs increases the chances of business failure decrease in the UK fast food industry.

Hypothesis two was related to the different age groups to predict the SMEs failure in the UK fast food industry. The p-value ($B = 0.137$, $p = 0.453$) for the age group shows no significant relationship between the age group and business failure, thus H2 is rejected (see Table 4.23).

H3: The education level of business owners is negatively and significantly linked to business failure, where the entrepreneur education increases the chances of business failure decrease in the UK fast food industry.

This hypothesis is associated with testing the likelihood of an entrepreneur's education level as a predictor of business failure in the UK fast food industry. The results ($B = -0.104$, $p = 0.222$) show that no significant relationship between the entrepreneur's education level and business failure exists at a significance level of 5% therefore, H3 is rejected (see Table 4.23).

H4: The size of the business is negatively and significantly related to business failure, where the number of employees increases the chances of business failure decrease in the UK fast food industry.

This hypothesis is related to testing the capability of SMEs size (which is defined by number of employees) to guess business failure in the UK fast food industry. The p-value ($B = -0.274$, $p = 0.272$) for business size shows that no significant relationship between the business size and business failure exists. Furthermore, the results show that having more employees cannot reduce the chances of business failure thus, hypothesis four is rejected (see Table 4.23).

H5: The business ownership type is positively and significantly related to the business failure, where businesses based on partnership are more likely to fail in the UK fast food industry.

This hypothesis is related to testing the capability of kind of ownership to envisage business failure in the UK fast food industry. The results ($B = 0.500$, $p = 0.009$) show that there is a

significant positive relationship between the kind of business ownership and business failure at a significance level of 5% therefore, H5 is accepted (see Table 4.23).

H6: The experience of the owner is negatively and significantly related to the business failure, where the entrepreneur experience increases the chances of business failure decrease in the UK fast food industry.

Hypothesis six is related to testing the capability of the owner experience factor to envisage the business failure in the UK fast food industry. The result of logistic regression analysis ($B = -0.439$, $p = 0.009$) indicates a statistically significant relationship between owner experience and business failure therefore, H6 is accepted (see Table 4.23).

As the owner experience increases the chances of business failure decrease. The results of the odds ratio for the owner experience factor suggest that businesses are 0.645 times unlikely to fall in the failure group with a rising of every one-unit inexperience factor (see Table 4.23).

Table 4.24 shows the mean score for two different types of businesses and results illustrate that the businesses that successful business give more importance to experience factor ($M = 4.43$, $S.D = 0.7845$) as compared to failed businesses ($M = 4.10$, $S.D = 0.957$).

H7: The owner's inappropriate personal traits are positively and significantly associated with the business failure, where the poor entrepreneurial traits decline business failure decrease in the UK fast food industry.

This hypothesis is related to testing the competence of owner traits to predict business failure in the UK fast food industry. The result of logistic regression analysis ($B = 0.087$, $p = 0.581$) indicates no statistically significant affiliation between owner business traits and business failure therefore, hypothesis H7 is rejected (see Table 4.23).

H8: The owner's poor business skills are positively and significantly associated with the business failure, where the poor entrepreneurial skills decrease or business skills enhanced business failure decrease in the UK fast food industry.

Hypothesis eight is concerned with testing the capacity of owner skills factor to anticipate the business failure in the UK fast food industry. The result of logistic regression analysis ($B = 0.447$, $p = 0.021$) indicates a positive statistically significant relationship between owner poor skills and business failure therefore, hypothesis H8 is accepted.

Table 4.24 shows the mean score for two different types of businesses and results illustrate that failed business owners give more importance to the experience factor ($M = 4.21$, $S.D = 0.999$) as compared to successful business owners ($M = 3.96$, $S.D = 0.883$).

H9: The business planning factor is negatively and significantly associated with the business failure, where more important the business planning factor for the businesses lower the chances of business failure in the UK fast food industry.

Hypothesis nine is concerned with testing planning factors' ability to predict the business failure in the UK fast food industry. The result of logistic regression analysis ($B = -0.536$, $p = 0.022$) indicates a significant relationship between entrepreneur experience and business failure therefore, hypothesis H9 is accepted (see Table 4.23).

The results of the odds ratio for the business planning factor suggest that businesses are 0.585 times unlikely to fail with a rise of every one unit in the planning variable (see Table 4.23).

Table 4.24 shows the mean score for two different types of businesses and results illustrate that successful businesses give more importance to the planning factor ($M = 4.42$, $S.D = 0.708$) as compared to failed businesses ($M = 4.08$, $S.D = 0.842$).

H10: The business location is negatively and significantly related to the business failure, where important the business location for the businesses lower the chances of business failure in the UK fast food industry.

This hypothesis is concerned with testing the capability of location factors to predict business failure in the UK fast food industry. The result of logistic regression analysis ($B = -0.553$, $p = 0.023$) indicates a statistically significant relationship between location and business failure therefore, hypothesis H10 is accepted. The results of the odds ratio for location factor suggest that business is 0.575 times unlikely to fail with an increase of every one unit in the importance of location variable (see Table 4.23).

Table 4.24 shows the mean score for two different types of businesses and results illustrate that successful businesses give more importance to location factor ($M = 4.41$, $S.D = 0.830$) as compared to failed businesses ($M = 4.04$, $S.D = 1.058$).

H11: The marketing and management factor is negatively and significantly related to the business failure, where important the marketing and management for the businesses lower the chances of business failure in the UK fast food industry.

This hypothesis is related to testing the ability of marketing and management factors to expect business failure in the UK fast food industry. The result of logistic regression analysis ($B = -0.506$, $p = 0.049$) indicates a statistically significant relationship between marketing and management and business failure therefore, hypothesis H11 is accepted. The results of the odds ratio for marketing and management factors propose that businesses are 0.603 times unlikely to fail with an increase of every one unit in the marketing and management factor (see Table 4.23).

Table 4.24 shows the mean score for two different types of businesses and results illustrate that successful businesses give more importance to marketing and management factors ($M = 4.39$, $S.D = 0.500$) as compared to failed businesses ($M = 4.05$, $S.D = 0.913$).

H12: The employee competency factor is negatively and significantly associated with business failure, where more important the employee competency for the businesses lower the chances of business failure in the UK fast food industry.

This hypothesis is related to testing the ability of employee competency to predict business failure in the UK fast food industry. The result of logistic regression analysis ($B = -0.323$, $p = 0.168$) indicates no statistically significant relationship between employee competency and business failure therefore, the hypothesis H12 is rejected (see Table 4.23).

H13: The poor economic condition is positively and significantly related to business failure, where inappropriate economic conditions increase the chances of business failure in the UK fast food industry.

This hypothesis is related to testing the capability of economic factors to predict business failure in the UK fast food industry. The result of logistic regression analysis ($B = -0.107$, $p = 0.542$) indicates no statistically significant affiliation between economic issues and business failure therefore, the hypothesis is rejected (see Table 4.23).

H14: The inappropriate government policies are positively and significantly associated with business failure, where unsuitable government policies for the businesses higher the chances of business failure in the UK fast food industry.

This hypothesis is related to testing the ability of political factors to predict business failure in the UK fast food industry. The result of logistic regression analysis ($B = 0.296$, $p = 0.251$) indicates no statistically significant affiliation between economic factors and business failure therefore, the hypothesis H14 is rejected (see Table 4.23).

H15: The competition is positively and significantly related to business failure, where the higher the intensity of competition factors the higher the chances of business failure in the UK fast food industry.

This hypothesis is related to testing the ability of competition to anticipate business failure in the UK fast food industry. The result of logistic regression analysis ($B = 0.363$, $p = 0.017$) indicates a statistically significant affiliation between competition and business failure therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. Businesses' failure chances increase by 0.695 times with the increase of every one unit in the importance of competition (see Table 4.23).

Table 4.24 shows the mean score for two different types of businesses and results illustrate that successful businesses give more importance to the competition factor ($M = 4.12$, $S.D = 0.894$) as compared to failed businesses ($M = 3.78$, $S.D = 1.062$).

Table 4.24a: Differences in Mean Score between successful and unsuccessful SMEs

Group Statistics					
Entrepreneur's		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Types					
PE	Successful	101	4.43	0.785	0.078
	Failed	108	4.10	0.957	0.092
PPT	Successful	101	2.94	1.107	0.110
	Failed	108	2.92	1.140	0.110
POS	Successful	101	3.96	0.883	0.088
	Failed	108	4.21	0.999	0.096
BP	Successful	101	4.42	0.708	0.070
	Failed	108	4.08	0.842	0.081
BL	Successful	101	4.41	0.830	0.083
	Failed	108	4.04	1.058	0.102

MM	Successful	101	4.39	0.500	0.050
	Failed	108	4.05	0.913	0.088
EC	Successful	101	4.29	0.585	0.058
	Failed	108	4.02	0.924	0.089
IEC	Successful	101	4.39	0.864	0.086
	Failed	108	4.27	0.957	0.092
IGP	Successful	101	4.27	0.963	0.096
	Failed	108	3.95	1.079	0.104
IC	Successful	101	4.12	0.894	0.089
	Failed	108	3.78	1.062	.102

The logistic regression analysis was performed to identify the factor significant to business failure and fulfil the research objectives. The result indicates that 7 independent variables are statistically significant to business failure with $p < 0.05$ and the factors significant to business failure are presented in figure 4.10.

Figure 4.10: Factors Significant to Business Failure (Author designed based on Findings)

Table 4.24b shows the mean score for entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors. The results of the mean score show that enterprise factors are the most important failure factors according to successful and unsuccessful entrepreneurs with mean scores of 4.4 and 4.1 respectively. The environmental factors secure second place with a mean score of 4.2 and 4 according to successful and unsuccessful business owners. However, the mean score for entrepreneurial factors is 3.8 (successful owners) and 3.7 (unsuccessful owners) which is less than enterprise and environmental factors.

Table 4.24b: Mean Score for the most Important Failure Factors

Mean Score		
Variable	Successful Owners	Unsuccessful Owners
Entrepreneurial Factor	3.8	3.7
Enterprise Factor	4.4	4.1
Environmental Factor	4.2	4.0

4.6 Multicollinearity

Multicollinearity can be defined as a high correlation between independent factors ($r = 0.9$ or above) (Pallant, 2013). The multicollinearity between the entrepreneurial, enterprise, and external indicators was assessed through running a correlation analysis. The results of the correlation analysis indicate a comparative low correlation between variables (see Appendix 6). Consequently, there is no issue of multicollinearity in the model.

Furthermore, variance inflation factor (VIF) was also utilized to evaluate multicollinearity. Variance inflation factor (VIF) is a respectable method to identify a linear relationship between independent variables. According to Field (2005), the VIF of more than 10 is considered problematic. However, there are differences between different researchers regarding the value of VIF. The maximum level of VIF varies from 5 to 10 (Hair *et al.*, 1995; Ringle *et al.*, 2015). The result shows that the VIF value for all the predictors is less than 5 therefore, multicollinearity between variables is not a cause of concern (See Appendix 7).

Qualitative Data Results

This section will discuss the qualitative data collected through three open-ended questions to get an in-depth understanding of the problem and address them. The first question tries to discover the most important failure factor out of three previously identified themes in the UK fast food industry by asking the respondents and trying to identify the reason of respondents chose them.

The second question tried to determine any other failure factors not included in this study. The researcher conducted a comprehensive literature review and included the most important and relevant failure factors in the study. However, there are several failure factors in the literature and it is not possible to include all of them in one single study. Therefore, the main purpose of this question was to identify any other potential failure factors not included in this study.

The third question helped to achieve the last objective and the owners were asked to provide the recommendation, on how the new businesses can avoid failure. The qualitative data analysis software NVivo package was used to analyse the data.

4.7 The most important Failure factor

In the first open-ended question, respondents were asked to give their opinion about the most important factors which could contribute to business failure if ignored and explain the reasons for choosing the intended failure factor to explore the most important failure factor. The qualitative data were categorized and organized into common themes.

In total 209 successful and failed business owners completed the questionnaires out of which 142 SMEs owners completed three open-ended question's part completely or partially. As a result, 95 responses were collected from successful entrepreneurs and 47 responses were collected from unsuccessful entrepreneurs. The owners of the UK fast food retail stores are considered the potential sample as they have a better insight into business problems.

4.7.1 Attitude Towards Enterprise Factors

The results of the first open-ended question show that in total 142 successful and failed business owners answered the first question out of which 72 respondents suggested that enterprise factors are the most important failure factors in the UK fast food industry (see Table 4.25 and Figure 4.12). It shows that the enterprise factors are the most significant and overlooking these factors can cause business failure.

Table 4.25: The Most Important Failure Factors

	Successful	Unsuccessful	Total	
Factor Types	Frequency	Frequency	Frequency	%
Enterprise Factors	42	30	72	51%

Environmental Factors	26	17	43	30%
Entrepreneurial Factors	12	15	27	19%

Figure 4.11: Frequency Analysis for the most Important Failure Factors

Enterprise factors were frequently mentioned factors and the successful and failed business owners explained two main reasons for its importance. The results highlighted the first reason is that enterprise factors can be controlled and managed to achieve the required results. The enterprise factors can be managed to mitigate the effect of external threats and utilise the opportunities. The second reason which emerged as a result of thematic analysis was the dominance of enterprise factors in the performance of a business (see Figure 4.13). For example, marketing, planning, internal resources, and other internal factors can help a business to increase sales, tackle competition, and enhance performance.

Figure 4.12: Reasons for most important failure factors (Author designed based on Findings)

According to 22 out of 72 respondents, the enterprise factors are imperative as businesses can control enterprise factors to achieve the desired outcome. Comments included:

Enterprise factors are controllable factors which if managed properly could benefit a business. For example, good marketing, location can increase sales and planning, capital all these things are crucial for business survival. (Respondent 76 unsuccessful owner)

Enterprise factors can be controlled and managing them would help in increasing your sales, help you in growth, and help to minimize the risk of external factors. (Respondent 57 successful owner)

Enterprise factors as these can be controlled and ignoring them or mismanaging could be a reason for business failure. Initial capital is important to run operations and grow. In addition, strategic planning help in achieving goals, improving resource utilization, and providing a guide. Similarly, marketing, location, employees are the factors that have a great impact on business performance.

(Respondent 102 successful owner)

Enterprise factors are the most important failure factor in the UK fast food industry as these factors are controllable and help in positive performance.

(Respondent 188 failed owner)

Secondly, according to 15 respondents the enterprise factors are important due to their influential nature and dominance in business performance and neglecting these factors can cause a business to fail. Some of the comments included:

Internal factors are more important as compared to the external and entrepreneurial factors due to their influential role in business success or failure.

(Respondent 4 successful owner)

Enterprise factors as they outweigh the other two categories of factors due to their importance in business success.

(Respondent 82 successful owner)

Well, certainly enterprise factors because these factors are very central in the success or failure of a business.

(Respondent 123 unsuccessful owner)

Hence, the results show that enterprise factors are the most important failure factors according to a majority of successful and failed entrepreneurs in the UK fast food industry. Marketing, planning, sales-related strategies, and other enterprise factors play a crucial role in the success of a business and mismanaging these enterprise factors can cause business failure. Furthermore, enterprise factors are very influential in the performance of a business and as these factors can be controlled by the SMEs therefore, they can help reduce the pressure from external factors.

4.7.2 Attitude Towards Environmental Factors

The results show that in total 142 successful and failed business owners answered the first open-ended question and according to 43 respondents, the second most important failure factors are environmental or external factors in the UK fast food industry (see Table 4.25). The result shows that two common themes emerged for choosing environmental or external factors as the second most important failure factor. These two main causes include uncontrollable nature, unexpected and instant failure (see Figure 4.4). Firstly, 15 respondents suggested that environmental factors are uncontrollable, and owners have no control over them. Some of the comments included:

The environmental factors are more important due to their nature uncontrollable. Sometimes one change in the law can make your business shut down or one change in environments such as coronavirus.

(Respondent 109 successful owner)

The economy, politics, competitors, technology, suppliers, law, customers, and even the weather are all overpowering factors that can affect organisational performance. Businesses cannot control these external factors. On other hand, the internal factors and entrepreneurial factors seem within your grip.

(Respondent 118 successful owner)

External factors that shape your business's opportunities and pose potential threats. A business cannot control external factors. All it can do is react to them and make plans to reduce the impact of external factors by utilising the internal resources.

(Respondent 125 unsuccessful owner)

I think external factors are the most important in business failure. Legal environmental or economic factors are unmanageable for business owners therefore businesses feel helpless when these factors struck your business.

(Respondent 149 unsuccessful owner)

Furthermore, respondents suggested the second reason for the significance of environmental factors was their unexpected nature to cause instant business failure. The environmental factors can be suddenly struck the business to the ground. For example, Covid 19 affected every type of business and industry causing huge losses. Several businesses shut down completely as a result of Covid 19. Similarly, a small change in the law can influence the performance of a business. Therefore, respondents proposed environmental factors as the second most important factors due to their immediate effect. Some of the comments included:

I think external factors are more important as they can cause a sudden business failure.

(Respondent 189 successful owner)

Environmental factors are most important to business failure as these factors have an unexpected impact on business performance. So, it can be said that these factors can very severely and swiftly affect a business. Sometimes one change in the law can make your business shut down or one change in the environment such as coronavirus.

(Respondent 200 unsuccessful owner)

In the end, the results of the quantitative data show that environmental factors play a crucial role in the performance of a business due to their uncontrollable and unforeseen nature.

4.7.3 Attitude Towards Entrepreneurial Factors

The entrepreneurial factors are the third most important failure factor according to 43 respondents in the UK fast food industry. The owners' characteristics, personality traits, and skills decide the faith of a business. The respondent suggested that in small businesses business owners make all the important decisions related to business performance therefore, this factor is considered crucial in the success or failure of a business (see Figure 4.4). Comments included:

In small businesses, the owners are the ones who make all the important decisions. If the owner is capable, innovative, motivated, and skilful then he/she can manage all types of factors using his experience.

(Respondent 5 successful owner)

Entrepreneurial factors are the most important to business failure in the UK fast food industry as decision making, planning strategy development, and implementation is done by the entrepreneurs in small level businesses. Entrepreneurs work experience matters when it comes to running a business. Imagine business owners do not have any experience, then they won't know how to overcome challenges of internal and external factors. In the same way, the motivation and personal skills of business owners also matter when it comes to running a business.

(Respondent 91 successful owner)

I would say entrepreneurial factors as everything starts from the business owner. Motivation leads owners to start a business in the first place. The owner's decisions can make a difference to manage internal and external challenges.

(Respondent 101 unsuccessful owner)

The most important factor category is entrepreneurial factors as business owners mostly make all decisions good or bad in small businesses.

(Respondent 126 unsuccessful owner)

In small businesses, all decisions come from the business owner therefore if a business fails it will depend on his decision.

(Respondent 197 unsuccessful owner)

Finally, the entrepreneurs are the ones who make all the decisions related to business performance. Even though, entrepreneurial factors are the third most significant factors still their role cannot be neglected. Entrepreneurs make important decisions, implement plans and develop and implement strategies to enhance business performance. Therefore, entrepreneurial factors also influence the performance of a business.

4.8 Supplementary Failure Factors

An open-ended question was used to explore the further failure factor missing from the literature. The successful and unsuccessful business owners were asked to give their opinion about common fast-food-related failure factors not included in this study. The result shows that respondents mentioned different failure factors based on their experience and observation. The result shows that altogether, 8 factors linked to the business failure were revealed from the second open-ended question as presented in table 4.26.

Table 4.26: Supplementary Emerged Failure Factors

Types	Failure Factors	Successful	Unsuccessful	Total
		Frequency		
Enterprise Factor	Poor Customer Service and Product Quality	17	23	40
External Factor	Pandemic	21	11	32
Enterprise Factor	Poor Inventory Management	14	8	22
External Factor	Legal Issues	5	16	21
Enterprise Factor	Neglecting Home Delivery	9	12	21
External Factor	Supplier Issues	11	3	14

External Factor	Poor Use of Technology	8	2	10
External Factor	Neglecting Third-Party Applications	4	3	7

Figure 4.13: The Typology of Supplementary Failure Factors

(Author designed based on Findings)

The results in figure 4.14 show that one of the most frequently highlighted failure factors by (40) participants extracted from the open-ended question responses include poor customer service and product quality. The customer service and product quality help to boost sales. It also helps businesses to retain customers and acquire new customers. It gives a competitive advantage to a business; therefore, poor product quality and services can affect business performance. The respondent (Respondent 101 unsuccessful owner) highlighted the importance of the customer service factor and mentioned:

“Every type of business depends on customers. So poor customer service can ruin your business. Due to intense competition customers have more bargaining power more options so

poor customer service can harm a business sale. It takes a lot of struggle and money to acquire a new customer while it takes only one bad experience to lose the customers. The sale comes from customers hence poor customer service can increase chances of business failure.”

Similarly, (Respondent 184 unsuccessful owner) mentioned:

“Poor customer service is one of the leading failure factors in fast food. Angry or unsatisfied customers will never return to your shop. Losing one customer won't help a new business. The sale of a business depends on customers no customer means no sale which ultimately means no business.”

The second most frequently highlighted failure factor mentioned by (32) respondents were pandemic. For example, Covid 19 has caused a major economic shock and business closure. The pandemic has affected all big and small businesses. Therefore, pandemic emerged as one of the most important failure factors. As highlighted by the respondent (Respondent 113 successful owner),

“In the current scenario, uncertain events can cause your business to die. If we look at what is happening around us, then coronavirus has affected every field of life including fast-food businesses. A lot of fast-food businesses mostly sit-in restaurants have closed down due to virus spread”.

Another participant (Respondent 152 successful owner) stated:

“I think in the last few months things have changed a lot. The methods to run businesses have changed due to Corona Virus. Now the public health in England has stopped the restaurants to take any orders in person inside the premises and businesses can only take orders online. Therefore, small businesses without online order-taking facilities have gone out of competition as a result.”

Similarly, the respondent (Respondent 89 successful owner) explained that the pandemic has become a threat for all types of businesses including fast food and it is one of the leading failure factors.

Another commonly effective failure factor revealed by (22) participants was poor inventory management. The new businesses have to incur losses as a result of poor inventory management. The poor inventory management was mentioned as a crucial failure factor by

several participants and one of the participants (Respondent 76 unsuccessful owner) shared his experience stating,

“From my experience, I would say poor inventory management as new businesses cannot afford the losses and when you order more and can't sell it expires and the business has to incur losses.”

In the same way, another respondent (Respondent 94 successful owner) mentioned:

“Poor inventory management is one of the major factors poor inventory management causes inefficiencies because you don't have accurate real-time information on how much inventory you have. This increases the risk of mistakes in reordering inventory from suppliers or of selling existent inventory.”

The respondent (Respondent 176 successful owner) also shared similar views:

“I would say that the first factor not included in this study is poor inventory management. Managing this factor can help you to save costs and avoid overheads. When business is new every penny matters so this is an important failure factor.”

Equally important are legal factors as reported by 21 respondents. Several legal factors can influence the performance of a business such as a small change in business law can cause severe problems for businesses. For example, in the early days of the pandemic fast-food businesses had to follow strict rules and regulations set by the government. Restaurants were not allowed to serve customers in-store. There were also restrictions about opening and closing hours. It shows the importance of legal factors and how delegated the legal issues can be for the survival of a business. The participant (Respondent 156 successful owner) shared views about legal factors and business performance:

“In a country like the UK legal factor is crucial in business survival. A change in the law can affect a business's performance sometimes making them go out of the market.”

Similarly, another respondent (Respondent 174 successful owner) stated:

“In recent months UK government regulations for takeaways and restaurants have changed for serving customers in the UK. It has affected many restaurants and takeaways some of them ultimately ended up shutting down.”

According to 21 respondents another major failure factor revealed was neglecting home delivery. The demand for home delivery has increased particularly during the Covid 19.

Customers prefer to order food online instead of visiting the shops and restaurants. So, home delivery adds value by offering convenience to customers. Home delivery offers several benefits to the businesses such as increased sales, profit, and customer loyalty. It also increases the reach of small businesses to a larger market and bigger customer pool. Therefore, neglecting home delivery can cause losses to businesses. One of the respondents (Respondent 65 unsuccessful owner) shared his experience about his business failure and stated:

“These days the customers want convenience. The businesses have to abandon the traditional selling strategies and wait for the customers to enter the shop. Now businesses have to reach the customers add value to the services and that is possible by free home delivery. One of the main reasons causing my business to fail was the absence of this service. I relied on people in a small range I could have increased my reach by doing home delivery. It would also help me to increase my sale.”

Another participant (Respondent 90 successful owner) shared his views and stated:

“Pandemic is a very important reason due to which numerous businesses have a shutdown. The government has banned restaurants and food shops not to serving customers in the shop to avoid gathering. It is affecting businesses a lot. Only those businesses are allowed to operate that offer delivery services. Therefore, the businesses who had no home delivery service have shut down.”

Another factor that emerged as a business failure factor is supplier issues. The supply chain in any business starts from suppliers therefore, they play a crucial role in good product quality and services. Suppliers can cause loss of customer trust and damage business reputation as a result of supplier failure. As respondent (Respondent 88 successful owner) highlighted:

“Suppliers’ issues can also create a problem for businesses which could lead to failure. A business chain starts from suppliers therefore too dependent on a few suppliers could increase their power which is not good for a business.”

Similarly, the respondent (Respondent 94 successful owner) made similar remarks:

“Your product quality consistency to offer services depends on the raw supplies you get from suppliers and on-time delivery therefore suppliers can affect your business. Also, suppliers can help you save costs.”

Another commonly effective failure factor revealed by (10) participants was a poor use of technology. The technology can help a business to increase productivity, efficiency, save cost and enhance business operation. The poor use of technology was mentioned as a crucial failure factor by several participants and one of the participants (Respondent 102 successful owner) shared his experience stating that:

“There are different software’s to secure the data of the customers which businesses can use later to do marketing about price and promotions. The software can also be used to manage inventory order food, track supplies, and make the operations of the business smooth and efficient.”

Lastly, running the business in the fast-food industry is changing very rapidly. With the advancement in technology, there are several opportunities for small businesses to grow. Several food deliveries companies have changed the way fast food and restaurants used to operate. These companies act as an intermediary between the independent takeaway fast-food outlet and customers. By partnering with these companies’ small fast-food businesses can increase their sale and increase their reach to the customers without spending any money on marketing. According to 7 respondents another major failure factor revealed was no use of these intermediary food applications. As one of the respondents (Respondent 2 successful owner) stated:

“In the fast-food business Just Eat, Uber Eats, Hungary Panda and such other applications can help businesses to increase their sales. So, I would say that no use or poor use of these platforms can also contribute to the poor performance of a business.”

The participant (Respondent 102 successful owner) made a similar comment:

“There are different applications for helping new businesses by giving customers. Business just has to make an account on those applications, and they will do the rest for you.”

In the end, the result of the second open-ended question shows that respondents highlighted several factors not included in this study that can influence the performance of a business and mismanaging them could cause a business to fail. These factors include poor customer service and product quality, poor inventory management, pandemic, supplier issues, neglecting home delivery, legal issues, poor use of technology, and neglecting third-party applications.

4.9 Recommendation for SMEs In the UK Fast Food Retail Industry

The third open-ended question aimed to get recommendations from the business owners to reduce the chances of business failure and increase the success rate. The views of the owners assisted in understanding and resolving the research problem in the relevant industry. Thematic analysis was used to analyse the qualitative data and recommendations are presented and categorized into three themes entrepreneurial, enterprise, and external factors. Most of the factors recommended by business owners revolve around already recognized business failure factors along with some additional factors. The result shows that business owners recommended 16 factors as presented in figure 4.15. These factors include gain experience, solid business plan, effective marketing and advertisement, high-quality product and services, prime location, business growth strategies, adequate finance, Inventory management, human resource management, offering home delivery service, financial management, legal compliance, use of technology, use of third-party applications and managing competition. According to successful and, failed business owners' new entrepreneurs need to focus on these factors to increase the chances of business success.

Figure 4.14: Thematic Framework for the Recommended Factors by Business Owners

Recommendation to Avoid Failure

Enterprise Factors	Environmental Factors	Entrepreneurial Factors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on marketing and management • Develop a business plan • Select a prime location. • Offer high quality product and services • Start business with sufficient finance • Focus on inventory management and forecast • Focus on human resource management • Develop strategies to increase sales • Avoid partnership • Offer home delivery services. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manage competition effectively • Use third party applications to increase sale • Focus on legal compliance • Utilise technology to manage business operations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquire adequate experience • Enhance personal skills

(Author designed based on Findings)

Entrepreneurial Factors: The results of the last open-ended question show that 10 respondents recommended achieving some relevant experience before starting a new business

to avoid failure. Experience equips the new entrepreneurs with the skills required to run a business and also offers basic knowledge about business needs. The experience offers basic knowledge to the owners about customers need and markets. As the respondent (80 unsuccessful owner) highlighted:

“Try to gain some experience before starting your business in a similar industry. As experience will give you knowledge about the market and customers and by understanding customers need you can better serve them.”

Similarly, another respondent (110 successful owner) highlighted the importance of previous experience and stated:

“The previous work experience of owners and general management skills for instance business and financial planning, marketing, team management, and human resource skills can help a business to grow and succeed.”

The results of the thematic analysis show that entrepreneurs skills also emerged as a crucial factor that can have an impact on the performance of a business. The result of the thematic analysis shows that 6 business owners recommended focusing on personal skills. The entrepreneurs can utilise these skills to enhance business performance by designing better marketing campaigns, networking with suppliers and other stakeholders, and managing a business effectively. These skills can also assist the entrepreneurs to enhance customer service, solve business problems, think strategically and implement the plan efficiently. As the respondent (73 unsuccessful owner) highlighted:

“Try to enhance personal skills such as marketing, managerial, customer service and other entrepreneurial skills as these skills can help the business owners to increase the sales and profit.”

Similarly, another respondent (101 unsuccessful owner) highlighted the importance of entrepreneur’s skills and stated:

“Business owners need to focus on skills important in business success. These skills include problem-solving, teamwork, networking, management, and leadership. A diverse set of skills can help a business grow. To launch a successful business and make a profit it requires certain skills; therefore, business owners need to focus on enhancing their skills and abilities.”

Enterprise Factors: Marketing and advertising was the most recommended success factor with 39 respondents which can help a business to build a brand, gain more customers, increase sale, and help in avoiding failure. Marketing help to build a strong brand and create product awareness. It helps in acquiring new customers and retaining the existing customers. Marketing and advertisement also help in reducing the intensity of competition as a business stands out of competition. The respondent (22 unsuccessful owners) stated:

“Use effective digital marketing and social media marketing to build a strong brand it might take some time but brands have a competitive advantage. Marketing needs to be done from all aspects traditional methods such as leaflets and through social media.”

Likewise, the respondent (89 successful owners) shed light on the importance of marketing and advertisement and stated:

“Try to build a brand it will not only give you a competitive advantage over your competitors also, increase brand salience. For that devote a budget for marketing and advertisement. Use social media for brand awareness and promotions.”

The second most highlighted enterprise factor by 35 entrepreneurs that helps a business to avoid failure and gain success was business planning. The business plan can bring clarity to the decision-making process and it can help in setting priorities, managing change, developing accountability, and managing cash. According to respondent respondents (110 successful owners), the planning prepares the business owner to face the challenges and further stated:

“Firstly, a business will need a solid business plan and strategies to overcome the hurdles. The plan will give a clear direction to the business. A business owner needs to be proactive and try to be prepared for the upcoming challenges and issues. Develop strategies to overcome those challenges.”

Similar comments made by respondent (R130 unsuccessful owner):

“It’s important to choose a location at a suitable place. The second thing is a business plan explaining your business objectives, strategies, marketing, sales, and financial forecast. This plan will help you to spot potential problems and you can make strategies to tackle those problems.”

The selection of location is the third most recommended enterprise factor by the business owners. It is very important to select a good location for business as it gives easy access to

customers. Location can also help in brand awareness. In the fast-food industry, all big chains prefer a location in areas with high footfall such as near tube stations, malls, and high streets. A location with high footfall has more chances to receive customers. Most of the respondents (71) suggested that the busy locations can help you to attract more customers into your shop. As one of the respondents (14 successful owners) stated:

“If a business wants to succeed it has to choose a good busy location with a good footfall.”

Another participant (Respondent 70 unsuccessful owner) stated:

“Location for any type of business is very important so try to select a good location before you start your business. If more customers go pass outside your shop there are more chances that more customers will come inside.”

Another highly recommended factor is offering home delivery service with 18 respondents mentioning this factor. Home delivery can help a business to increase reach to a bigger pool of customers. Therefore, offering home delivery can help businesses to increase sales. Home delivery also offers convenience to the customers by ordering food online or over the phone and receiving it without leaving their house. So, offering home delivery services adds value to businesses. In recent years home delivery has become a crucial factor that can be very significant in the business success as highlighted by the respondent (70 unsuccessful owner) and stated:

“These days customers want the food to arrive at their doorstep. Every big brand including McDonald’s, KFC, and every pizza chain doing home delivery. Therefore, new businesses can start free delivery to increase their sales by reaching more customers. If the new business finds it difficult to start free home delivery, they can get the services from a third party.”

Home delivery can help you to enhance the reach of the businesses and increase the target market as stated by the respondent (113 successful owner):

“Businesses must have a free home delivery to offer convenience to the customers and add value to your services. It will also help your business to expand by targeting more customers.”

The result shows that customer service and product quality also emerged as very crucial factors in the performance of a business. In the fast-food industry product quality and customer service are considered very important for the success of a business. As the competition is intense in

the fast-food industry, therefore, poor customer service and product quality can cause a business to fail. Good customer service and product quality make customers satisfied and they make a repeat purchase. The customers are willing to pay more money as a result of good customer service. Therefore, good customer service helps businesses to increase customer loyalty and profit. The respondent (8 successful owners) emphasized the quality of products and services and expressed that without customers survival of business becomes unbearable. The respondent (81 unsuccessful owners) mentioned:

“Treat your customers like a family and try to make a strong relationship with them by offering them good customer service and promotions as without customers business cannot survive.”

Another important factor recommended by the respondents is the availability of finance. The supply of money is very important for the survival of a business. In the early days of starting a business, businesses need to have sufficient finance to run operations smoothly as the business does not start giving profit straight away. Finance can be used in business growth, running a marketing campaign, launching new products, competing with competitors, and paying employees training and salaries. The respondent (22 unsuccessful owner) emphasized the finance and stated:

“It's not the cost only required to start a business one also needs capital to run the operation up to a certain time so make sure to have enough funding.”

Similar remarks were made by respondent (successful owner71):

“New businesses need sufficient funding in the first place. Many new entrepreneurs do not know that you do not need money only to start a business but also for running the business as in the early months business won't give you any profit so you have to invest to keep the business running. Try to have multiple sources of lenders.”

Inventory management is the factor highly recommended by 20 respondents. In the early days of starting a business, it is important to save costs. Inventory management can help a business in inventory accuracy such as ordering the products correctly to meet the demand. Inventory management also helps you to save costs such as handling and storing the stocks, and stock cost money until it is not sold. Overstock ordering can also cost you money as some products can expire. Therefore, inventory management can increase profit and offer customers a better experience as they get their orders in time. Managing the inventory properly can help the

business to reduce the costs and increase profit as stated by the respondent (22 Unsuccessful owners):

“In the early days of starting business try to avoid unusual costs by managing inventory, predicting forecast, and avoiding wasting raw materials.”

Likewise, the respondent (79 unsuccessful owner) stated:

“Try to order as much as you can sell easily and avoid wastage. In fast-food business due to competition, the profit margin is narrow. And you can make a profit by reducing your expenses.”

Developing strategies to increase sales is also identified as an integral part of business success with 17 respondents offering recommendations. Regarding this one of the respondents (80 successful owner) mentioned:

“Spend more time developing strategies and implementing them instead of getting busy working as a manager. Have patience and give your business some time before it starts giving a profit. Do not take money out from your business instead keep investing it into the business so it could grow. Money is like blood for the business so keep your business running try not to let your sales drop. Use different strategies to keep selling more.”

Another important enterprise factor highlighted by the 17 respondents is human resource management. Employees are considered an important asset for any business and they play a crucial role in the positive performance of the business. Employees represent the business, interact with customers and contribute to good or bad customer service. Talented employees can increase business sales by offering good customer service and offering good deals for customers. Talented employees learn things quickly so help businesses to avoid extra training costs. Competent employees come up with new ideas and new products which can benefit the businesses. Therefore, employees play a major role in the positive performance of a business. As highlighted by the respondent (71 successful owner):

“Staff play an important part in the success of business keep them happy and empower them so they could contribute in the growth of your business. I think that all would do make a difference.”

Likewise, another respondent (90 Successful owner) recommended, “Focus on human resource management. Workers have a great impact on the performance of a business.”

The results of the thematic analysis show that partnership also emerged as another recommended factor as reported by 10 respondents that can have an impact on the performance of a business. There can be conflict in a partnership due to differences in opinion and individual preferences not being identical. There can be disagreement about marketing, sales strategies, management style, and business structure. Similarly, there can be trust issues between partners. Partnerships also reduce control for an individual in their business decisions. Therefore, the respondent suggested that partnership issues need to be resolved or avoid starting a business in partnership. One of the participants (Respondent 101 unsuccessful owner) shared his experience stating that:

“My business failed because of partnership problems. I had finance issues so I had to start a business in partnership but that was the biggest mistake due to which my business collapsed. We always had disagreement problems and different opinions on matters like marketing, recruiting employees, suppliers, etc. In short, I had no control over my business and sometimes there was an ego factor that created more differences. Therefore, it’s important to resolve issues with partner or avoid going into a business partnership.”

Similarly, another participant (Respondent 115 unsuccessful owner) recommended:

“There are several benefits of partnership however, at the same time it comes with more problems. Business partnership reduces your control over your business, increases decision-making time, creates trust issues, creates problems about management style, etc. Therefore, look for alternative financing options rather than going into a business partnership.”

Environmental or External Factors: The results show that managing competition is a highly recommended external factor by 19 respondents. Regarding the competition, the recommendations are very straightforward to interpret. The intense competition can be a hurdle in the survival of a business as stated by the respondent (R18 successful owner): “Tackle competition with effective pricing and innovative marketing. I think these things can help you to survive.”

It is important to recognise competitors and do market research to better understand the customers and fulfill their needs. Businesses need to differentiate themselves by offering good quality product services, and with pricing strategies. Marketing can also help the business deal with competitors.

As the respondent (70 unsuccessful owner) emphasized the importance of the competition and stated:

“Competition is another challenge new business face. Competition is intensive in the fast-food business, therefore; new businesses have to differentiate themselves and they have to be innovative to tackle competition.”

Another important factor recommended by 16 respondents and emerged is the use of third-party applications. These food delivery companies can help the businesses to reach new customers, acquire them, and increase sales without any marketing or location cost. The demand for third-party applications is increasing nowadays. The number of customers for third-party applications such as UberEATS, just eat and Deliveroo has been increasing. Therefore, businesses can increase their sales by using third-party applications services. The respondent (110 successful owner) stated:

“Technology can further help by increasing sales, for instance, small businesses can register on applications such as Deliveroo, UberEATS, and Jinn where thousands of customers can see your brand and order from your restaurant. It can give a good business every week.”

In the fast-food industry, there is a shift to run operations. Third-party applications are marketplaces where both customers and businesses can register. Customers can find their favourite food restaurants and order food through the applications while businesses receive orders through these third-party applications devices. Therefore, businesses can save the marketing cost and increase sales by using third-party applications services. As another respondent (170 successful owner) recommended:

“Nowadays running businesses have completely changed. There are many small restaurants running businesses from the location inside arches or hidden in buildings. All they have to do is register on these online platforms which give your business includes UberEATS, Just Eats and Deliveroo. You do not have to spend money on marketing or location. You just have to share a little profit of your business as a commission with third party businesses so I think it has completely changed the business model and that’s what will be the future of fast food.”

Legal compliance is another factor recommended by 10 respondents. Respondent (79 unsuccessful owner) stated:

“Legal compliance is very significant in the survival of a business as it can bring sudden death to the businesses. Keep a record of your expenses and fulfil the legal requirements as these things can instantly cause your business to shut down.”

Similar views were shared by the respondent (182 successful owner):

“Follow the legal requirements and regularly scan the environment to look for threats and opportunities. Businesses need to be careful about the external factors as they can bring instant deaths to the businesses.”

The better use of technology has also been recommended by the 9 respondents. The technology helps in easier faster and more effective communication which can make the decision-making faster. Technology can help in avoiding wastage through more efficient stock management. The technology also assists in developing more new innovative approaches to run different business operations. These days businesses can benefit from the advancement in technology and use them in running efficient and responsive operations. The respondent (82 successful owners) stated:

“The use of technology for different purposes can have a positive impact on the performance of your business. Technology can help you manage your stocks, food ordering, lower expenses, forecast, etc. Use digital platforms and social media to market your products and increase brand awareness. invest in training of employees and keep the standard high.”

In the end, the third open-ended question fulfil the last research objective and the thematic framework shows that the respondent highlighted several factors such as internal, external, and entrepreneurial which need the attention of the business owners. These factors include previous experience, business planning, marketing, and advertisement high-quality product and services, location, business growth strategies, adequate finance, Inventory management human resource management, home delivery service, financial management, legal compliance, use of technology, use of third-party applications and managing competition. Managing these factors can increase the chances of business success and avoid business failure.

4.10 Summary

This chapter has presented the findings of the study and evaluates the factors that influence the performance of the UK fast food SMEs. The chapter begins with descriptive analysis and presents the demographic characteristics of owners and businesses. The average participant (successful Owners) in this research is male, over 34 years of age, educated to a minimum

degree level, owned a business, or have working experience in the UK fast food industry. On the other hand, the average participant (unsuccessful owners) in this research is male, 25 – 34 years of age, with no or low education, and holds no previous experience or entrepreneurial activity. Similarly, the average participating business (successful) in this research is established business trading for more than three years, located in London, with an average turnover of less than £2 million, with an average of 5 – 50 employees. While, the average participating business (unsuccessful) in this research is new business trading for 1 - 3 years, located in London, with an average turnover of less than £2 million, and employing 5 – 10 workers.

Then exploratory factor analysis was performed to recognize the structure and relationship amongst the variables. The entrepreneurial aspect is measured by 9 items, enterprise with 15 items, and external environment with 9 items. The new factors were extracted with the help of the principal component method in SPSS which confirms the structure and relationship amongst the variables. The degree of relationship between the resulting factors was discovered through measuring the correlation. Lastly, for each factor, the reliability was also calculated.

Following that, the relationships between constructed factors were investigated through Pearson correlation. The logistic regression analysis was conducted to analyse the entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors to predict business failure and test the hypotheses. The main finding specifies that the model encompassing all the independent variables is statistically significant. The result of logistic regression analysis indicated a statistically significant relationship between 7 variables and business failure these factors included the type of ownership, owner's experience, poor owner skills, business planning, business location, marketing and management, and intensity of competition. The mean score result shows that the enterprise factor is the first, environmental factor is the second, and entrepreneurial factor is the third most important failure factor that influences failure.

Then, multicollinearity was confirmed, and no issues of multicollinearity were found in the model. The logistic regression analysis helped to test the hypothesis and address the first three research objectives. In the end, qualitative data was analysed through thematic analysis and answered the last objective. The first open-ended questions tried to identify the most important factor contributing to business failure and the results showed that the enterprise factors were the first, environmental factors second, and entrepreneurial factors were the third most important failure factor that influences failure based on frequency analysis. These findings support the findings of quantitative data.

The second open-ended question tried to explore further failure factors not included in this study related to the fast-food industry. The results for qualitative data show that participants identified 9 additional factors that can influence the performance of a business these factors included poor customer service and product quality, pandemic, poor inventory management, legal issues, neglecting home delivery, supplier issues, poor financial management, poor use of technology, and neglecting third-party applications.

The last open-ended question tried to seek recommendations from successful and failed business owners to avoid failure. Altogether, 14 factors linked to the business failure were recommended and emerged from the third open-ended question and according to successful and failed business owners focusing on these factors can help a business to reduce the chances of business failure. These factors included previous experience, business planning, marketing, and advertisement high-quality product and services, location, business growth strategies, adequate finance, Inventory management human resource management, home delivery service, financial management, legal compliance, use of technology, use of third-party applications and managing competition. The next chapter presents the discussion.

Chapter 5: Discussion

The present research aims to develop a model and recognize business failure factors in the UK fast food retail industry. The higher failure rate in the UK SMEs created an urge to investigate the business failure factors. The UK SMEs contributes a lot to employment, growth, and economy therefore, identifying these failure factors can help the businesses to succeed and ultimately benefit the economy. It is important to define the SMEs to predict the factors associated with the SMEs' performance.

However, there is no universal definition for SMEs and each country and region has adopted its definition. This study employed the SMEs definition according to the UK Companies Act of (2006) and define SMEs as any enterprise employees less than 250 employees and maintain an annual turnover below or up to £25.9 million or an annual balance sheet below or up to £12.9 million. This definition is more suitable for this study as understudy enterprises operate within the UK. In addition, this definition is more recently updated therefore, it reflects the current market conditions in a better way. The filter questions were used in the questionnaires to include only those SMEs which fulfilled the sampling criteria.

Similarly, there are several definitions for business success and failure. The definition of business success and failure varies according to different researchers and several methods have been used to measure SMEs performance. Generally, two indicators have been used widely to measure SMEs success or failure such as financial indicator and longevity (Simpson, 2004). The SMEs owners are mostly reluctant to share their business financial details, therefore, in present research the performance is measured through the duration of trade for instance successful businesses are those businesses that continued to trade for more than three years while unsuccessful businesses filed bankruptcy within three years (Arasti *et al*, 2015; Pretorius, 2009).

One of the major challenges in the present study was to obtain data and get access to SMEs already ceased to operate in the market. Furthermore, there was no official list of unsuccessful businesses. Therefore, to overcome these challenges and obtain the list of failed businesses different strategies were used as discussed in chapter 3 in detail.

A list of successful and failed entrepreneurs was compiled by the researcher. Then a questionnaire developed on the Google forum was sent by email and posted to almost 4100 strong sampling frames of successful and failed entrepreneurs. Any kind of physical contact

was avoided due to pandemics. After following up 101 responses (4%) from successful entrepreneurs and 108 responses (8%) from failed entrepreneurs were collected. The researcher managed to collect a total of 209 responses in almost 8 months from potential respondents who met the criteria of this study as mentioned in the literature review.

The data collection phase started during the time of pandemic and the researcher took all the precautions to safely collect the data. Initially, the plan was to collect the data from successful entrepreneurs by visiting high streets and personally distributing the paper questionnaires, and collecting them once completed however, due to the pandemic certain precautions were practiced avoiding any physical contact as it could have led to the spread of the virus.

The researcher observed during the data collection phase that during the lockdown the participation of the respondent increased probably because the participant stayed home and had more time. The emails containing questionnaire links were sent to the potential participant however, one of the major challenges that the researcher faced was that several email addresses were abandoned which affected the response rate. The researcher found some contact numbers of the respondents as well therefore, the researcher contacted a few respondents through phone calls and requested the respondents to participate in the study which helped to increase the response rate.

In the present research, several factors were scrutinized in regard to measuring their contribution to the business failure in the UK fast food industry through utilizing binary logistic regression analysis. These failure factors were categorized into entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors based on literature review (Arasti *et al*, 2014; Rody and Stearns, 2013). Logistic regression analysis illustrates several entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors capable of predicting SMEs failure in the UK context. The logistic regression analysis also helped to test the hypothesis developed in chapter 2. The results of the logistic regression analysis assisted in achieving the first three objectives, to critically evaluate entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors, to predict the SME failure in the UK fast food industry. The following section further discusses the influence of the entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental (external) factors on business failure and compares the research findings of present research with other studies from SMEs context.

5.1 Entrepreneurial Factors

In the present research, the entrepreneurial variables are classified into factors associated with owners. The literature on SMEs highlighted that entrepreneur play an important role in the

success or failure of a business. The owners' characteristics, personality traits, and skills decide the faith of a business. Walker and Brown (2004) stated that owners develop the plan to run the business and perform more than one task in the SMEs therefore, owners control the progress of a business. This section further discuss the role of entrepreneurial factors in the failure of SMEs in the UK context.

5.1.1 Gender of Owners

The descriptive analysis results indicate that the number of male participants is much higher than the number of female participants. It suggests that the fast-food industry is dominated by male business owners in the UK. According to the UENI (2020), the percentage of male-owned small businesses (67.63%) is much higher than the percentage of female-owned small businesses (32.37%). The UK government has been taking steps to shrink the gender gap in SMEs however it's evident that still SMEs dominated by males. The intensive literature indicates that gender has an influence on the performance of the business and mostly suggests the male gender has higher chances of success as compared to females (Carter and Williams, 2003; Johnsen and McMahon, 2005; Chowdhury and Endres, 2005). Therefore, the discussion suggests that businesses owned by male entrepreneurs have better chances of business survival or success as compared to female entrepreneurs.

While logistic regression analysis results specify the absence of any statistical relationship between SMEs failure and gender. According to Robb and Watson (2012), no statistically significant difference was found between males and females regarding their influence on business performance in the United States of America. Similarly, Alsaleh (2015) also failed to find any statistical relationship between gender and SME performance.

5.1.2 Age of Owners

The descriptive analysis results indicated that the majority of the respondents belonged to the age group of 35 - 44 with 68 responses in total out of which 36 responses were collected from successful entrepreneurs while 32 responses came from unsuccessful business owners followed by the age group of 45 to 54 with 64 responses. In addition, results for age group 25 - 34 show that number of unsuccessful business owners is higher than 45 as compared to successful entrepreneurs with 19 responses. The smaller number of responses came from the age group 55+ with 13 responses 10 from successful and 3 from unsuccessful business owners in the UK fast food industry. According to The Guardian (2015) the average age of entrepreneurs in the

UK is between 40 and 47 years as career uncertainty, lack of experience and debt discourage the young entrepreneurs to start their own business.

The logistic regression analysis specifies that no statistical relationship existed between owners' age and business failure. The findings of the present study match with the findings of Zhao (2021) and Anura *et al.*, (2011) who found no correlation between owners' age and business performance. Lussier and Pfeifer (2001) also found no statistical relationship between owners' age and business performance and support the findings of the present study. On the other hand, Kautonen *et al.*, (2008) propose that older business owners have high chances of achieving success as compared to the younger ones due to their experience networking and finances.

5.1.3 Education Level of Owners

The education level of the owner plays a crucial role in the performance of the SMEs and lack of education can cause a business to fail (Kim *et al.*, 2006). The descriptive analysis shows that the majority of participants with a degree or higher qualification were owners of successful businesses, on the other hand, the owners of unsuccessful businesses were mostly from a low educational background. Mahmood *et al.* (2021) conducted a study to investigate the impact of an entrepreneur's education on business performance and found that educated entrepreneurs contribute to the positive performance of a business.

Furthermore, inferential analysis outcomes using binary logistic regression indicate no statistically significant results between owner's education level and business failure in the UK fast food industry. These findings are aligned with the findings of Soriano & Castrogiovanni (2010) who conducted research on the impact of CEO and owner's education on SMEs performance within the European Union and found no statistically significant relationship. Furthermore, a similar study was conducted by Lussier and Halabi (2010) in Chile and the results showed no significant relationship between SMEs performance and education level. Cho and Lee (2018) found that an entrepreneur's education has no association with business performance. However, the findings of Ndlovu *et al.*, (2018) show different results as they found a significant relationship between owners' education and SMEs performance.

5.1.4 Experience of Owners

The descriptive analysis illustrates that most of the successful business owners had experience and owned a business previously while mostly unsuccessful business owners had no experience of owning a business. The mean score of entrepreneurs' experiences was higher for successful

business owners as compared to unsuccessful businesses. It shows that successful businesses emphasize more on the importance of the owner's entrepreneurial experience. Peng, Zhou, and Liu (2020) entrepreneurial experience have a strong relationship with business performance therefore, business owners with entrepreneurial experience increase the chances of business success.

Furthermore, logistic regression analysis outcome directs a negative significant relationship between the owner's prior experience and business failure. It shows that the owner experience is inversely proportioned to the business failure which means as the experience increases the chances of business failure decrease or chances of business success increase. The finding in the present study is aligned with the findings of the Lussier and Pfeifer (2001) findings who suggested that lack of experience can increase the chances of business failure as experience can help the owners to exploit the opportunities. According to Ndlovu *et al.*, (2018), there is a positive relationship between owner experience and business performance. Furthermore, Eresia-Eke and Okerue (2019) also suggest that there is a positive relationship between previous experience and business performance. Okpara and Wynn (2007) proposed that poor experience was one of the major failure factors.

The present study finding suggests that entrepreneurs who owned a business previously have better chances of success as they have a broad experience of starting a business from scratch and awareness of the risks or challenges new entrepreneurs face.

5.1.5 The owner Poor Traits

The results of descriptive analysis mean score demonstrate that both successful and unsuccessful business owners tend to give less importance to personal traits. The owner traits were considered one of the crucial factors to predict the SMEs failure however, the results of the logistic regression analysis revealed no significant affiliation between the owner's traits and SMEs failure in the UK fast food industry. The finding in the present study is aligned with the findings of the Lussier and Pfeifer (2001) findings who suggested that there is no significant relationship between owners' characteristics and business performance. Blackburn *et al.* (2013) also propose that entrepreneurs characteristics are not important in influencing business performance. Therefore, entrepreneur's traits are not significant in the failure of SMEs in the UK fast food industry.

However, Franco *et al.* (2019) directed a study to figure out the influence of personality traits on business performance and found out that neuroticism has a negative influence on business performance.

5.1.6 Owners Inappropriate Personal Skills

The descriptive analysis outcome revealed that both types of business owners recognize the importance of the owner's skills however, the comparison of the mean score shows that unsuccessful businesses tend to give more importance to owners' poor skills factor as compared to successful businesses.

The logistic regression analysis outcome shows a positive significant relationship between the owner's poor skills and business failure. It shows that the owner's poor skills increase the chances of business failure. These findings support the work of Ali *et al.* (2020) who identified a relationship between owners' skills and business performance. Anderson, Chandy, and Zia (2018) also found similar results and concluded that owner skills influence the performance of small businesses. Furthermore, Fansuree *et al.* (2019) found a statistically significant relationship between owner skills and performance. While Man *et al.* (2002) developed no statistically significant results between business performance and entrepreneur's skills. The entrepreneur's skills are very crucial in the success of a business as entrepreneurs can use these skills to enhance their sales, improve their managerial operations, manage good relationships with suppliers and exploit opportunities through proactive thinking.

5.2 Enterprise Related Factors

In the present research, the entrepreneurial variables are classified into factors associated with the business. Enterprise factors are considered very important in the performance of a business. These factors can be managed and controlled, therefore; enterprise factors can be used to predict the SMEs failure in the UK context. This section further discuss the role of enterprise factors in the failure of SMEs in the UK context.

5.2.1 Size of Business

In the present research, the size of the business has been measured through the numbers of employees as explained earlier (see chapter 3) according to which SMEs are enterprises with less than 250 employees (UK Companies Act, 2006). The descriptive analysis indicated that the majority of businesses have less than 5 employees, out of 95 responses 43 responses were collected from successful businesses while 52 responses came from unsuccessful business

owners. Similarly, 92 responses were collected from businesses that had 6 to 10 employees. However, only 13% of successful and 8% of failed businesses had more than 10 employees. The results of the descriptive analysis indicate that the majority of businesses were small.

The logistic regression analysis revealed that no statistically significant relationship was found between business failure and business size in the UK fast food retail industry. Saleh (2016) conducted a study to investigate the relationship between firm size and performance and the results were consistent with the finding of the present study.

Furthermore, Becker-Blease *et al.* (2010) examined the association between firm size and profitability within 109 U.S manufacturing industries and found a negative significant relationship between firm size and profitability. This study found that the relation between size and profitability is industry-specific. However, McMahon (2001) also examined the relationship between firm size and business performance and results showed a positive relationship in Australian SMEs. Similar results were found by Doğan (2013) in Turkish SMEs. So, it shows that mixed results were found in different countries and business sectors therefore, the size of business and performance needs to be investigated further to develop robust results.

5.2.2 Type of Ownership

The descriptive analysis outcome indicated that the majority of participants (71%) were sole traders. Likewise, the comparison of the two business groups reveals that the majority of the successful business owner (81%) were sole traders. Similarly, the comparison of the two groups shows that most of the unsuccessful businesses (63%) were in partnership business ownership. It shows that the failure rate was higher in the partnership type of businesses.

Additionally, inferential analysis results indicate a statistically significant positive relationship between owner's position (partnership) and business failure in the UK fast food industry. It indicates that businesses in a partnership are more likely to fail in the UK fast food industry. These findings are aligned with the finding of Atsan (2016) findings who stated that the partnership was one of the major failure factors in Turkey. Similar results were found by Ahmad and Seet (2009) in a comparative study conducted on the SMEs owners of Australia and Malaysia. However, Lee and Tsang (2001) conducted a study in the Singapore market and found a significant positive relationship between SME performance and partnership. However, Siow Song *et al.* (2011) found no significant relationship between ownership type and failure in the Singapore market. Therefore, it is important to consider the partnership factor before starting a business.

5.2.3 Strategic Business Planning

The descriptive analysis outcome revealed that both types of business owners recognize the status of the strategic planning factor however, the comparison of the mean score shows that successful businesses tend to give more importance to strategic planning as compared to unsuccessful businesses.

In addition, the logistic regression analysis outcome specifies a negative relationship between strategic business planning and business failure in the UK fast food industry. It shows that effective business planning can decrease the chances of business failure or increase the chances of business success. These findings support the findings of Raj (2009) who conducted a study in the UK and revealed that planning influences business performance. Bushes (2019), Hodges & Kent (2006) also found that business planning has an impact on business performance. Fatemi *et al.*, (2018) also examined the relationship between business planning and performance and found a statistically positive relationship. George *et al.* (2019) further supports this claim and suggest that strategic planning ensure business success and assists business in deteriorating the probability of business failure.

5.2.4 Business Location

The descriptive analysis outcome highlights that both types of business owners recognize the reputation of the business location. All big and small brands emphasize location and open a new chain at a prime location. Location with high footfall can help a business to drive more customers inside the shop and assist in acquiring new customers.

The results of the logistic regression analysis indicate a negative significant relationship between the business location and business failure in the UK fast food industry. It shows that a good location can lessen the chances of business failure. In other words, the selection of a location can be crucial in the success or failure of a business and a poor location can cause a business to fail. These findings support the findings of Barnard, Kritzing, and Krüger (2011) who conducted a study in South African SMEs and found that location has a positive significant relationship with business positive performance. Kim and Lin (2021) also found a positive association between firm location and performance. Furthermore, Felix *et al.* (2015) also found a strong relationship between business failure and poor location.

5.2.5 Marketing and Management

The descriptive analysis outcome revealed that both successful and unsuccessful business owners recognize the significance of marketing and management. Effective marketing and management can help a business to increase brand awareness, assist in standing out of competition, acquiring new customers, and retaining potential customers.

The results of the inferential analysis indicate a negative significant relationship between marketing and management and business failure in the UK fast food industry. The results indicate that poor marketing and management can increase the chances of business failure, in other words, effective marketing can reduce the probability of business failure. These findings are aligned with the finding of Radipere & Van Scheers (2014) who suggested that poor marketing and management harms business success. Moreover, Turner and Endres (2017), Ming-Tien and Chia-Mei (2004) also found a positive significant relationship between business performance and marketing and management. Agarwal and Dahm (2015) conducted a study on fast food restaurants and found out that competent management plays a crucial role in the performance of a business.

5.2.6 Employees Competency

The descriptive analysis outcome revealed that both types of business owners recognize the status of the employee's competency however, the mean score of successful businesses is more than the unsuccessful businesses. It shows that successful businesses tend to give more importance to employees' competency than unsuccessful businesses.

The employee's competency was considered one of the crucial failure factors to predict the SMEs failure however, the results of the logistic regression analysis revealed no statistically significant relationship between the employee's competency and SMEs failure in the UK fast food industry. The findings of Chi *et al.* (2009) suggest an absence of a direct relationship between employees and financial performance in the USA market, these findings are aligned with the findings of the present study.

The results in the present study are different from the findings of Samad (2013) who found that employee competency is one of the major factors that significantly enhanced the performance of businesses and reduce the chances of business failure.

5.3 Environmental or External Factors

In the present research, the environmental variables are classified into factors associated with the external environment. The business environment is considered difficult and dynamic which poses a threat to the businesses. Along with many opportunities the environment also offers threats for businesses. This section further discuss the role of environmental factors in the failure of SMEs in the UK context.

5.3.1 Unsuitable Economy

The descriptive analysis results revealed that successful owners give more importance to unsuitable economy factors for example the means score according to successful business owners is more than the unsuccessful businesses. It indicates that successful business owners emphasize more on economic factors. Economic factors can influence the performance of a business for instance inflation increases the prices of raw materials and products therefore, the prices of goods increase which influences the purchasing power of customers. Similarly, an increase in interest rates creates hurdles for small businesses as most SMEs rely on the bank and other financial institutions for loans. As the interest rate increases the SMEs have to get a loan at a high-interest rate which reduces the profit for a business. So, economic factors play a crucial role in business performance.

The logistic regression outcome explains that there is no significant relationship between poor economic condition and business failure in the UK context. These findings support the findings of Arasti *et al.* (2014) who found no significant relationship between the economic factor and business failure.

However, Oparanma *et al.* (2010) found poor economic condition as one of the major challenges for SMEs survival. Similarly, Burns (2001) also found a significant positive relationship between inadequate economic conditions and business failure.

5.3.2 Inappropriate Government Policies

Political factors have a huge impact on business performance. Government can raise the taxes or add some new taxes which will impact the profit. Likewise, the government can increase the minimum wage for the employees or bring some new rules which can affect the business performance. After the Covid 19, the government in the UK introduced some new laws according to which businesses were not allowed to serve in the store, and only home delivery was allowed. So, those businesses who offered no home delivery had to stop trading and some

of them went bankrupt due to new government policy. The opening and closing times were limited, and businesses had to follow strict procedures. So, political factors can influence business performance.

The political factor is considered one of the crucial failure factors however, the inferential analysis revealed the absence of significant affiliation between the poor government policies and SMEs failure in the UK fast food industry. Atawodi and Ojeka (2012) found a negative relationship between government policies such as taxes and business growth.

While the findings of Oparanma *et al.* (2010) differ from present research findings and revealed that failure rates are upsurge attributable to excessive taxation and regulation.

5.3.3 Competition

The descriptive analysis outcome revealed that both types of business owners recognize the significance of competition yet, the mean score of successful businesses is more than the unsuccessful businesses. It shows that successful business owners emphasize more on the competition factor. Intense competition can increase the chances of business failure.

Competition is one of the major factors which influence the performance of a business. The regression analysis identified a statistically significant relationship between competition and business failure. These findings support the work of Arasti *et al.* (2014) who found that competition is one of the main factors causing businesses to fail. Furthermore, Gill and Biger (2012) discovered the competition as a major hindrance in the positive performance of the Canadian SMEs. Assaad (2020) also found a positive relationship between business performance and competition.

Qualitative Data Discussion

5.4 The Most Important Failure Factors

The qualitative data were collected to investigate the utmost important failure factors in the UK fast food industry through an open-ended question. The result of the first open-ended question frequency analysis shows that 51% of respondents suggested enterprise factors are the most important failure factor in the UK fast food industry. While environmental factors were considered the second most important failure factors according to 30% of respondents. The enterprise factors were placed on the third spot with 19% of respondents considering it the most important failure factor in the UK fast food industry.

The qualitative data support the results of quantitative data. According to successful and failed entrepreneurs, the enterprise factors are the most important as the mean score for enterprise factors is higher 4.4 (successful owners), 4.1 (unsuccessful owner) as compared to environmental factors with a mean score of 3.8 (successful owners), and 3.7 (unsuccessful owner). The entrepreneurial factors mean score was relatively low 3.8 and 3.7.

It's clear from the qualitative and quantitative data that enterprise factors are the most important factors which can influence the performance of the business in the UK fast food industry. therefore, it is important to emphasize enterprise factors to avoid failure. These findings are aligned with findings of Hove & Tarisai, (2013) who found in a similar study that internal factors are the most important factors that influence the growth and survival of small and medium-sized businesses. Similarly, Dragnić (2014) also conducted a study on Croatian SMEs to identify the impact of internal and external factors on performance and found that internal factors are more significant on business performance as compared to external factors.

The second part of the first open-ended question asked why chosen factor is important in business failure. The result of the thematic analysis shows that successful and failed business owners explained two main reasons for choosing enterprise factors as the most important failure factors such as they are controllable and play an influential role in business performance. The enterprise factors can be controlled to mitigate the effect of external threats and utilise the opportunities. The respondents suggested that managing and controlling the internal factors can help the business owners to reduce the pressure from external factors. In addition, the enterprise factors play an influential role in the performance of a business. For example, marketing, management, planning, finance, sales-related strategies, and other enterprise factors play a crucial role in the success of a business and mismanaging these enterprise factors can cause business failure.

5.5 Supplementary Failure Factors

The second open-ended question aimed to explore the additional failure factors missing from the model, respondents were asked to give their opinion about common failure factors not included in this study. The qualitative data was collected to better understand and provide a richer picture of the problem.

The results of the thematic analysis suggest that there are 8 factors extracted from the open-ended question responses which include poor customer service or product quality, pandemic,

poor inventory management, legal issues, neglecting home delivery, poor use of technology, neglecting third-party applications, and supplier issues.

The result shows that poor customer service or product quality was the most frequently highlighted factor by the participants. Nowadays, due to intense competition customers have more bargaining power and options to select therefore, poor customer service can affect the sale. It takes a lot of struggle and money to acquire a new customer while it takes only one bad experience to lose the customers. Therefore, poor product quality and customer service can make it difficult for a business to survive. In other words, good product quality and customer services can help businesses to retain customers and increase sales. Similar results were found by Susanti (2013) who identified an association between product quality and customer service quality towards customer satisfaction in restaurants. Hoe and Mansori (2018) also found a strong correlation between high product quality and positive business performance.

The second most significant failure factor highlighted by the respondent is pandemic. It is a fact that Covid 19 has affected every industry in the world. There is not a single country in the world that got away with the effect of the pandemic. The respondent suggested that pandemic has also affected the fast-food industry as after the pandemic new rules were introduced by the UK government to run the fast-food businesses. The businesses were stopped from taking any order in-store so, the small businesses which had no website or delivery services had to stop their operations. The business had to comply with the new legal requirements and operational time for food businesses was reduced to avoid the spread of the virus. Bartik, *et al.*, (2020) conducted a study to identify the impact of Covid 19 on small business outcomes, performance and suggested that Covid 19 has a huge impact on businesses performance.

Poor inventory management is the third most significant failure factor according to respondents. Most of the respondents claimed that new businesses fail to manage their inventory properly and the raw material expires due to which businesses incur losses. In the early days of starting a business, it is important to save costs. Inventory management can help a business in inventory accuracy such as ordering the products correctly to meet the demand. Inventory management also helps businesses to save costs such as handling and storing the stocks, and stock cost money until it is not sold. Overstock ordering can also cost you money as some products can expire. Therefore, inventory management can increase profit and offer customers a better experience as they get their orders in time. Atnafu & Balda (2018) found in a study that inventory management practice has a significant impact on business performance.

Muchaendepi *et al.* (2019) also proposed that poor inventory management cause delays in business operations and influence business performance.

Another major failure factor that emerged was legal issues. In a country like the UK legal factor is crucial in business survival. A change in the law can affect a business's performance sometimes even causing them bankruptcy. The results of the qualitative data show that in recent months UK government regulations for takeaways and restaurants have changed for serving customers in the UK. It has affected many restaurants and takeaways some of them ultimately ended up shutting down. Kitching, Hart & Wilson (2015) also found that legal factors can influence business performance.

Similarly, neglecting home delivery emerged as an important failure factor. Nowadays every small and big fast-food brand offers the service of home delivery and it helps many businesses to increase their sales and reach a bigger pool of customers. Due to the pandemic, the customers were reluctant to leave the house and visit the restaurants to order food. Therefore, the demand for home delivery surged. According to Statista (2021) report between 2018 and 2019 food delivery market value augmented from £8.1b to £8.5b. Avinash and Miguel (2020) stated that Covid 19 has changed consumer behaviour and the number of online delivery orders has increased significantly due to health and safety issues. Nakao *et al.*, (2019) researched reflection about the home delivery model in fast food franchises and found twelve elements of home delivery services have a positive impact on the performance of a business. Therefore, new businesses need to focus on offering home delivery services to add value to their business.

Third-party business applications also emerged as an important factor that can affect the performance of a business. As the demand for home delivery has been increasing continuously it created an opportunity for some new businesses to enter this market and offer home delivery services. As a result, some businesses developed a model to be an intermediary between customers and sellers. These third-party business applications offer an opportunity to the customers to order food online and track their orders through their applications. Similarly, these third-party businesses help restaurants and takeaways to increase sales by driving customers to them in return for a small commission. These online applications such as Uber Eats, Deliveroo, Just Eat have been highlighted as another major failure factor by respondents. These platforms helped many small businesses to survive and increase sales during the pandemic. Pollard and Neill (2021) conducted a survey and found that online food delivery platforms are booming as

a result of the pandemic which led to behavioural changes among consumers to purchase more online.

Another failure factor identified by respondents was suppliers' issues. The supply chain in any business starts from suppliers and they play a crucial role in the positive and negative performance of a business. Likewise, the raw material quality and continuous supply affect the operations and performance of a business. The relationship between supplier and business help to gain a competitive advantage through price and quality. Kannan & Tan (2002) support these findings and suggest supplier strategic commitment to the buyer has a great impact on the performance of a business. Arasti *et al*, (2014) also found in a study on business failure factors that a single supplier and access to the supplier is a major failure factor.

The results of the second open-ended question show that poor use of technology is another main failure factor. Nowadays technology contributes to almost any type of business. Technology plays a significant role in the performance of a business. Every small and big business is using technology to run their day-to-day operations and make operations smooth. Technology has changed the way businesses use to operate, internal operations, and business models (Westerman, Bonnet, and McAfee, 2015). The technology helps the business to enhance inventory management (Shire Anshur, Ahmed, and Hassan Dhodi, 2019). In the fast-food industry, technology has changed the way businesses used to operate. Nowadays most customers place an order using an application on the phone instead of going to the store and receiving an order at home. The business can also advertise on social media which is considered very effective marketing. In other words, technology is benefiting both customers and businesses and poor use of technology may affect the performance of a business. Shire Anshur, Ahmed, and Hassan Dhodi, (2019) support these findings and suggest that good use of technology can enhance the performance of a business.

5.6 Recommendation

The results of the thematic analysis suggest that there are several factors extracted from the third open-ended question which if managed properly can help a business to minimize the risk of failure and assist in achieving success. This question helped to achieve the last objective which is to get recommendations from successful and failed entrepreneurs to avoid failure.

The results of the thematic analysis indicate that most of the recommendations revolve around failure factors already recognised by the quantitative method. Most of the respondents recommended emphasizing marketing and management which can help a business to succeed.

Marketing and advertisement can assist in building a strong brand and gaining a competitive advantage over competitors. In addition, the new business owner needs to use online (social media) and offline channels to advertise and reach to maximum audience. Managing day-to-day managerial roles along with marketing can increase the chances of business success. The results of the inferential analysis also back these findings and suggest that marketing and management factor is negatively and significantly associated with business failure, where more important the marketing and management for the businesses lower the chances of business failure in the UK fast food industry. Therefore, it's evident that managing marketing and management factor can help a business to avoid failure. These findings are aligned with the finding of Radipere & Van Scheers (2014) who suggested that poor marketing and management harms business performance. Moreover, Ming-Tien and Chia-Mei (2004) also found a positive significant relationship between business performance and marketing and management.

The results of the thematic analysis reveal that business planning is the second most recommended factor by the respondents. The recommendation about planning is very simple, business owners need to have a business plan as it will prepare them to overcome challenges and give a clear direction to achieve future goals. Business planning helps the owners to develop strategies to overcome hurdles and give a clear direction. The results of the inferential analysis also back these findings and suggest that business planning remains negatively related to business failure, which means better business planning lowers the chances of business failure in the UK fast food industry. So, business planning can play a crucial role in the success of a business. These findings support the findings of Raj (2009) who conducted a study on the UK SMEs and found that better strategic planning can help a business to succeed.

Respondents also emphasized that businesses need to choose a better location before starting a business. The location with high footfall can help the business to acquire new customers without any marketing efforts. The respondents suggested that a location can help a business to be more visible to customers and it can help them to increase their sales. All the big fast-food brands prefer a prime location therefore, a busy location can help a business to minimize the risk of failure. These findings support the finding of quantitative data which suggests that the business location factor remains negatively and significantly related to business failure, where more important the business location for the businesses lowers the chances of business failure in the UK fast food industry. These recommendations are aligned with the findings of Barnard, Kritzing, and Krüger (2011) who conducted a study in South African SMEs and found that location has a positive significant relationship with business performance.

The results of the thematic analysis revealed that product quality and services are another enterprise factor highly recommended by the respondents. The respondents emphasized the quality of products and services and expressed that without customers survival of business becomes unbearable. Poor customer service and product quality can make a customer angry, and they will end up turning to competitors. The customers make a business and without customers, there won't be any business, therefore, it's really important to satisfy the customers' needs with quality products and services. As there is huge competition in the fast-food industry high-quality product and services can help a business to retain their existing customers and acquire new customers. Suchánek and Králová (2015) conducted a study on food companies in the Czech Republic and found a positive relationship between customer satisfaction factors (product and services) business performance. Similarly, Jahanshahi *et al.* (2011) also found a positive correlation between customer service, product quality, and customer loyalty or better business performance.

One more important factor recommended by the respondent is the availability of finance. The supply of money is very important for the survival of a business. Finance is like blood for a business and without blood, a business cannot survive. The respondents suggested that new business owners need to understand that finance is not only required for opening the business but also to run the operations in the early days. The new business owners need to have enough finance as a backup to pay employees' salaries, run marketing campaigns, and run the day-to-day operations if required. In the early days of a business, not all businesses do break-even and business owners need to pump some money into the business to survive. Therefore, the business needs to have multiple channels of finance (lenders with low-interest rates) as a backup for success (Jung *et al.*, 2014). Cowling, Liu, and Zhang (2017) highlighted that access to finance plays a crucial role in the positive performance of a business.

The results of the thematic analysis show that inventory management and forecast are highly recommended factors by the respondents. Managing the inventory properly can help the business to reduce costs and increase profit. When a business is new, it's important to avoid unusual expenses by managing inventory, predicting forecasts, and avoiding wasting raw materials. Likewise, businesses need to order raw materials according to demand to avoid wastage. The higher level of inventory management practices helps the business to gain a competitive advantage which leads to improved business performance (Atnafu and Balda, 2018). The automated procurement practices and other inventory management practices have

a positive impact on the performance of a business (Masudin *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, effective inventory management practices can help a business to be successful.

Another important success factor recommended by the respondent is developing strategies to overcome challenges and increase sales. Developing strategies to increase sales is an integral part of business success. Business owners must develop some strategies to acquire new customers such as the focus on effective marketing, price, promotions, innovative services, and product quality. Furthermore, the business owners need to spend more time developing strategies and implementing them instead of focusing on other inconsequential tasks. The strategies can help businesses to overcome challenges increase sales, enhance inventory management, reduce competition, and enhance business operations and performance. The generic strategies and business capabilities have a positive impact on the business performance (Acar and Zehir, 2010). There are different strategies to increase sales such as increasing trading hours to avoid competition, cost strategy, differentiation strategy, etc. In other words, business owners need to develop strategies and prepare themselves in advance for uncertainties and challenges to survive (Foster *et al.*, 2014).

The results of the thematic analysis show that human resource management is another most recommended factor by the respondents. Employees play an important role in the performance of a business. As highlighted by one of the respondents, staff plays an important part in the success of a business, therefore, keep them happy and empower them so they could contribute to the growth of your business. The employees can help a business to grow, enhance customer service and product quality. Renee (2009) proposed that human resource management supports the increased wellbeing of employees which leads to the positive performance of a business. It shows that utilizing employees properly can benefit a business a lot.

Another important success factor recommended by the respondent is managing competition. Regarding the competition, the recommendations are very straightforward to interpret. Intense competition can be a hurdle in the survival of a business and it's important to make strategies to tackle competition. Bennet (2016) conducted a study in the non-profit domain and found that competition is one of the main factors causing failure in new charities. Lampadarios (2015) found competition one of the main influential failure factors in the UK chemical industry. Furthermore, Saleh (2016) conducted a study on Saudi Arabia SMEs success factor and proposed that intense competition reduces the chances of business success. Thus, it's important to develop some strategies to tackle the competition. There are different ways to keep ahead of

competition such as fulfilling your customer's needs, differentiating, building a strong brand through marketing, developing brand salience, practicing customer retention strategies, expanding your reach, offer better quality products and services as compared to your competitors, etc.

The results of the third open-ended question show that due to highly volatile business environment effective use of technology is another highly recommended factor according to respondents. The entrepreneurs can review their strategic significance through using VUCA model and prepare for volatile business environment. The methods to run business are changing due to volatility. Technology contributes a lot to the success of a business. Technology is helping all small and big businesses to perform their daily tasks smoothly. The technology helps the business to enhance inventory management as with the help of software the inventory can be ordered tracked and monitored (Shire Anshur, Ahmed, and Hassan Dhodi, 2019). Similarly, in the fast-food industry, technology has changed the way businesses used to operate. The software can be used for the training of employees. Nowadays most customers place an order using an application on the phone instead of going to the store and receiving an order at home. The business can also advertise on social media due to advancements in technology which is considered a very effective marketing technique. In other words, technology is benefiting both customers and businesses every how and better use of technology can help a business to be successful (Cao and Dowlatshahi, 2004). The entrepreneurs must change with the changing business environment to compete and enhance the chances of success.

According to Avinash and Miguel (2020), Covid 19 has a big role to play in changing consumer behaviour and as a result number of online deliveries, orders have increased significantly due to health and safety issues. Nowadays consumer behaviour has changed, and customers prefer to order food online. Therefore, demand for home delivery has also increased. Statista's (2021) report suggests that between 2018 and 2019 food delivery market value augmented from £8.1b to £8.5b. Practicing free home delivery is one of the main factors which respondents have highly recommended for the success of a business. In recent years the demand for home delivery has increased rapidly.

Nowadays customers demand convenience and home delivery offer convenience to the customers and add value to the services. Through conventional methods, the sellers had to wait for the customers to enter their shops and buy but now with advancements in technology and changes in consumer behaviour the customers prefer to order food over the phone or through

the internet. All big fast-food brands such as Pizza hut, Dominos, KFC offer home delivery. Home delivery helps a business to reach a bigger pool of people and expand its market. Nakao *et al.*, (2019) researched reflection about the home delivery model in fast food franchises and found twelve elements of home delivery services have a positive impact on the performance of a business. Therefore, to be successful, the new business owners need to adapt to a new method of trading and consider the need of customers to offer home delivery services to the customers.

Respondents also highly recommended the use of third-party application services to achieve success. In recent days the use of third-party application services has also increased. These applications charge a little commission to the businesses and in return provide them reach a new pool of customers. Uber is a famous example of a third-party application that offers services to self-employed drivers in the UK. Similarly, in the fast-food industry there are several third-party services provider applications such as UberEATS, Deliveroo and Just eat which help the small takeaways and restaurants to increase their sale and acquire new customers. These platforms helped many small businesses to survive and increase sales during the pandemic. Pollard and Neill (2021) conducted a survey and found that online food delivery platforms are booming because of the pandemic which led to behavioural changes among consumers to purchase more online. Van Veldhoven *et al.* (2021) investigated the impact of online food delivery services and found a significant performance increase for restaurants joining Deliveroo. Therefore, the new business owners can utilize these platforms during the dark time of pandemics to gain new customers and grow.

The results of the qualitative data show that according to respondents' experience is another major factor that can contribute to the success of a business. The respondents suggested that higher experience increases the chances of business success. In addition, the descriptive analysis reveals that the majority of the successful business owners owned a business previously while mostly unsuccessful business owners had no experience of owning a business. Likewise, the logistic analysis results support the findings and indicate that as experience increased the chances of business survival also increase. The finding in the present study is aligned with the findings of the Lussier and Pfeifer (2001) findings who suggested that lack of experience can increase the chances of business failure as experience can help the owners to exploit the opportunities. Therefore, entrepreneurs need to gain some relevant experience before starting a new business.

Another important success factor recommended by the respondent is legal compliance. The businesses which do not give importance to legal factors have no future. Legal compliance is the first thing a business would consider before starting a business. A change in the law can affect a business's performance even sometimes a change can cause a business to file bankruptcy. Kitching, Hart & Wilson (2015) also found a relationship between regulations and business performance. Therefore, new businesses need to follow legal compliance to survive.

The results of the third open-ended question show that according to respondents' skills are a key factor in business success. The respondents suggested that better entrepreneurs marketing, networking, communication, problem-solving, and managerial skills can increase the chances of business success. These findings support the results of quantitative data which suggest that entrepreneurs' poor personal skills increase the chances of business failure. These findings support the work of Ali *et al.* (2020) who identified a relationship between owners' skills and business performance. Anderson, Chandy, and Zia (2018) also found similar results and concluded that owner skills influence the performance of small businesses. Furthermore, Fansuree *et al.* (2019) found a statistically significant relationship between owner skills and performance.

Another important success factor recommended by the respondent is avoiding partnership in starting a business. In partnership, the ownership of a business is divided between more than one person which sometimes creates many complications in business operations such as control, decision making, etc. One of the main problems identified in partnership style business is lack of control on business which influences the performance of a business. The partners can have a conflict on running marketing activities, budget, and business operations. The partners can have trust issues which can affect the business negatively.

The logistic regression analysis results also support these recommendations and indicated that businesses established on partnership are more likely to fail in the UK fast food industry. Bennet (2016) conducted a study on business failure factors in the non-profit domain sector and found that internal conflict between owners or colleagues major failure factor. Similarly, Arasti *et al.*, (2014) also support these findings and suggest that partnership issues contribute to the failure of a business. Therefore, entrepreneurs need to have sufficient funds to start a business as a sole trader and have full control of their businesses and decision.

In their final comments, a few respondents recommended that new entrepreneurs could focus on the factors mentioned in this research model to gain success. Overall, the results of

qualitative (frequency analysis) and quantitative (mean) suggest that majority of respondents emphasized the enterprise factor and suggested these factors play a crucial role in the success or failure of a business. The environmental factors (external factors) are the second most important factors according to the successful and failed entrepreneurs and entrepreneurial factors are the least important factors in the UK fast food retail industry. However, the importance of the entrepreneurial factors cannot be neglected as literature consider these factors very important in the performance of a business.

5.7 VUCA Analysis in Fast Food Business

The business environment has become very volatile, and trends are changing very rapidly in the UK fast-food industry. The current business environment has changed essentially over the past several years. Major transformations were well underway prior to the global pandemic, but the latter and the ensuing global recession made the business landscape even more extraordinary. The fast-food retail industry is changing because of advancements in technology and globalisation. The method of sale and running business in the fast-food industry has undergone a paradigm shift. Technology has lowered the barriers of starting a fast-food business. The demand for home delivery and use of online application has increased.

The pandemic and advancement in technology has a big role to play in changing consumer behaviour and business model. During the pandemic people avoided going to the takeaways and restaurants and preferred home delivery. According to Avinash and Miguel (2020), Covid 19 has a big role to play in changing consumer behaviour and as a result number of online deliveries, orders have increased significantly due to health and safety issues. Nowadays consumer behaviour has changed, and customers prefer to order food online. Therefore, demand for home delivery has also increased. Statista's (2021) report suggests that between 2018 and 2019 food delivery market value augmented from £8.1b to £8.5b. Nowadays customers demand convenience and home delivery offer convenience to the customers and add value to the services. Customers like to order the food online using different applications and want their food to be delivered to their house. The consumer behaviour has also changed from traditional buying at shop to ordering food online on different applications. As the respondents also suggested that customers prefer convenience ordering and receiving home delivery. All big fast-food brands such as Pizza hut, Dominos, KFC offer home delivery. Home delivery helps a business to reach a bigger pool of people and expand its market. Nakao *et al.*, (2019) researched reflection about the home delivery model in fast food franchises and found twelve

elements of home delivery services have a positive impact on the performance of a business. Therefore, to be successful, the new business owners need to be creative and innovative, adapt to a new method of trading and consider the need of customers to offer home delivery services to the customers. The new business owners must come up with a creative idea to exploit the volatility as sometime change in marker or change in consumer behaviour create opportunities for the entrepreneurs. For example, the demand for vegan product has increased after the hype on social media platforms about veganism. Several restaurants have integrated with vegan options. The new trend shows that people paying attention to their diet cutting down on meat and dairy while eating more plant-based food. According to Statista (2022) the share of vegan in different age group is increasing in the UK. Therefore, creative vegan products based on market research to satisfy the market need can help the new entrepreneurs to establish their business.

The technology has also changed the way customers used to order inside the shop. The ordering inside the fast-food restaurants has also changed with arrival of kiosks installed in the stores. The customers can order the food without saying a word and waiting in long ques. Kiosks add value to businesses since they boost efficiency. All the big brands such as KFC, McDonalds also using kiosks to improve their operations and gain efficiency in receiving order.

Over the past few years, a lot of changes occurring in the fast-food industry as result of pandemic and advancement in technology. The pandemic affected all the industries supply chain was cut off and it also changed the way customers ordered the food. During the pandemic the restaurants and fast-food stores opening hours were reduced and there were strict legal requirements to operate such as wearing mask all the time keeping a safe distance from customers and new food hygiene guidance were introduced.

In the new business model, the restaurants, and fast-food stores utilising third party applications such as Uber Eats, Just Eats, and Deliveroo to acquire new customers and reach to a bigger pool of customers instead of relying on tradition methods to run business. The respondents in the present study also highlighted this factor and suggested that businesses which are reluctant to use these third-party applications are more like to fail as businesses must change and adopt new methods to survive. Now adays customers like to order food on these online applications and wants their food to be delivered at their doorstep instead of reaching to the shop and collecting the food. All the big brands such as McDonalds, KFC, Pizza hut, and Dominos also using these third-party applications to increase sales. These changes can be linked to

Schumpeter creative destruction essentially another term for true innovation which is necessary for introducing new product, methods, and even new ways of organising a business (Diamond, 2016). In time of uncertainty the businesses need to creative, innovative, conduct market research and try to satisfy the market need. For example, during pandemic a lot of businesses went bankrupt while in 2020 YouTube star Jimmy Donaldson opened a virtual burger chain at 300 locations and gain a splendid growth. It shows during uncertain time the businesses can consider and take a view from different perspectives to be successful. Dee Hock (1999) chaordic concepts suggest similar views that at the point of maximum tension the creativity emerge while responding to volatility in market and adopting change in its operations and product offering (Curlee, 2002). When businesses must respond to changing environment, creativity is the only solution for survival.

Some fast-food stores try to be innovative and make the menu large and complex. Its not important to keep adding new products to the menu to be creative and increase sales. The businesses try to be excessively innovative in new product development. Introducing new products and services help the businesses to compete for shelf space, protect market share, and compete with rivals. However, the frequent launch of new products can make the business operations complex and increase the cost to manage that complexity. Therefore, the fast-food stores must be careful and find the right balance between customer satisfaction and operating complexity. The complexity of operations can also be managed with the help of training.

The technological advancement pandemic and uncertainty in business environment has created an ambiguous situation. The agile business is a way to the future as the challenges of the present cannot be resolved by using the strategies of the past. The businesses must change their culture to survive in the VUCA world. The businesses must respond quickly, be creative and focus on customer satisfaction. The managers need to be equipped with VUCA skills to competently manage instabilities. Businesses need to hire those managers who are collaborative and comfortable with ambiguity and change. The businesses must create a culture of rewarding employees based on calculated risk taking, agile behaviour and innovative ideas. The reward system will help to attract and retain agile employees and leaders who can play a crucial role in business success. In the fast-food business employees and managers have a direct interaction with the customers and they understand the customer needs and market situation therefore, these employees need to be empowered to take certain decision in product development and promotions.

In conclusion, digital transformation, volatility, pandemic, uncertainty, and business complexity is changing the nature of running fast food businesses. The impact of the VUCA has spread across many industries. The businesses that can adapt to these changing environments and respond to this pressure can reduce the risks and capture the opportunities better than their rivals. For example, in the present study some respondents suggest that during the pandemic the footfall to fast food stores declined significantly. Due to fear of pandemic and government restrictions customers preferred to order food online or third-party applications such as Deliveroo or Uber Eats. However, respondents had no knowledge or facilities to take orders online or use the third-party applications therefore, they ended up shutting down businesses. On the other hand, those businesses who creatively adapted to the changing environment and used the technology in a better way enjoyed significant growth. The businesses can tackle volatility with agility and changed should not be rejected but accepted. Performing market analysis and evaluating business performance with sufficient information can help businesses to tackle uncertainty. Similarly, the complexity can be managed with restructuration, adjusting its procedure, and operational activities. Reduce the ambiguity with experimenting different strategies and it will help to develop most suitable strategy for business success.

5.8 Summary

This chapter discussed the research findings in detail. The chapter discussed the research problem and the main challenges faced in earlier chapters such as the absence of a universal definition of SMEs, business success, and failure. The qualitative and quantitative research findings were discussed, and these results were compared with literature supporting these findings and compared with literature against these findings. Finally, the summary of the discussion was presented. The next section provides the conclusion chapter.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

6.1 Introduction

This chapter provides the conclusion of the present research. Firstly, the research process review has been discussed in detail. Secondly, it highlights the contribution of the research and then follows the limitation of the present research. In the end, research implications are provided in detail along with future research and a summary of the chapter.

6.2 Research Process Review

It's widely recognized across the world that SMEs have attracted the interest of researchers, policymakers, international organisations, and investors due to their reputation. It benefits and helps the national economy and social development in different countries through creating employment opportunities, improving GDP, and generating income. SMEs have an essential part to play in accelerating economic development, creating jobs, developing, and strengthening economies in developed and developing countries. Furthermore, SMEs create 60% of jobs in the UK with a shared annual turnover of £1.9 trillion almost 51% of the turnover of the whole private sector (Gov, 2017).

The present study aimed to investigate the significant SMEs failure factors as mentioned in chapter one in detail and use them as a predictor of SMEs failure in the UK retail industry. The principal reason behind present research was to identify a phenomenon that received further attention from the researchers in recent years, the key factors causing a large number of SMEs to shut down in the UK. The present study sought to aware new entrepreneurs of the major failure factors and offer recommendations on how to minimize the risk of failure. The present study developed a model to predict SMEs failure in the UK market and emphasized answering the main research question: What are the critical failure factors in the UK fast food retail industry according to the perception of successful entrepreneurs and failed entrepreneurs which might be used to predict SMEs performance and recommend them to avoid failure?

The research has addressed the main question by answering the following questions:

- What are the critical entrepreneurial factors that predict SME failure in the UK fast food industry?
- What are the critical enterprise factors that predict SME failure in the UK fast food industry?

- What are the environmental (external) factors that predict SME failure in the UK fast food industry?
- What guidelines can be developed to reduce the start-up's failure in the UK fast food industry?

Chapter two consisted of a literature review that discussed diverse definitions and reputations of SMEs in different contexts. The present study employed the definition of SMEs according to the UK Companies Act of 2006 that states SME is any enterprise employees less than 250 employees and maintain an annual turnover below or up to £25.9 million or an annual balance sheet below or up to £12.9 million. The literature review further explained different meanings and measurements of SMEs failure and success: Gaskill *et al.* (1993) stated failure definition as owner urge to sell or liquidate the business to evade loss otherwise to pay off a creditor or exit the business without any profit. On the other hand, success is measured by profitability (return on investment, profit) and growth (Saleh, 2016). Some studies consider those businesses successful which continued to trade and make a profit. (Saleh, 2016; Lussier and Halabi, 2010). Meanwhile, another common definition in literature for business failure is bankruptcy. Bankruptcy can be defined as the legal exit or dissolution of business through compulsory liquidation (Sheehan, 2014). Thus, numerous business success and failure explanations are found in the literature instead of a universal definition.

Lastly, the definition which suited the present study and therefore, employed for this research defines business failure as a business in which the owner is unable to hold control of the business anymore due to bankruptcy, business ceased operations with losing the money to creditors, willingly shutting down business operations with unpaid responsibilities or is in bankruptcy or business cease to exist commercially and as a result of the physical structure of small business willingly or unwillingly has to shut down besides business end operating or transacting within three years (Arasti *et al.*, 2014; Pretorius, 2009). The profit or financial indicators to measure performance could not be utilized due to the lack of financial data about the participating businesses. Therefore, the performance of the business to be successful or failed was measured based on the business's ability of trading during a certain period instead of objective measures. According to the definition employed in present research a business is considered failed if ceases to trade within three years and considered successful if continued to trade for more than three years.

Furthermore, the literature review encapsulated the views of several researchers who conducted similar studies related to business performance in developed and developing markets. After that, it explained several variables that influence success and failure in different contexts and industries.

An intensive literature review was conducted to develop the conceptual and theoretical framework for this research. The literature revealed that the failure factors vary in different studies and scholars failed to agree on one specific set of variables that influence performance. However, there are commonly known success and failure factors identified by the previous research. There are several success and failure factors exposed by intensive literature review. While Storey (1994) categorised these success and failure factors as internal and external factors based on their significance. The owners' factors, internal operations, and external environment have a significant effect on the performance. SMEs can control the internal factors while they have little or no control over external factors. SMEs are more likely to fail when incompetent to utilise personal skills and internal resources to overcome the challenges from the external environment.

The literature proposes that there are several causes of start-up failures which have been classified into three general themes as extracted from different journal articles. These themes include (1) entrepreneurial perspective to elucidate start-ups failure, (2) enterprise factors to explain the start-up failures, and (3) environmental factors to explain start-up failure (Mayr, 2020; Alsalaeh, 2015; Lampadarios, 2016; Arasti *et al.*, 2014; Simpson *et al.*, 2012; Jasra *et al.*, 2011). This study offers a comparison of three approaches for studying start-up failure and each approach scrutinizes different aspects of the start-up failure, emphasis a different level of analysis, and utilize several methods.

The chapter then discussed the entrepreneurial factors linked to SME performance. The entrepreneurial approach emphasizes the characteristics, mental and emotional aspects of the individuals or founders that influence the performance of their business (Rody and Stearns, 2013). In the literature, entrepreneurs have been a dominant subject in business failure and the focus is on the characteristics of entrepreneurs therefore, this research will utilize the entrepreneurship theories to identify the factors associated with SMEs failure and take a broader look to better understand the problem. The chapter also explains the influence of internal and external factors on business performance (Alsalaeh, 2015; Lampadarios, 2016; Arasti *et al.*, 2014).

Furthermore, based on three themes the hypothesis for the entrepreneurial factors were established depending on the gender of the owners, age of the owners, education level of the owners, previous experience, personal traits, and personal skills of the owners. Secondly, the hypothesis related to enterprise factors were developed based on the size of the business, ownership type, business planning, marketing, location, and employee competency. Lastly, the hypothesis related to environmental factors were developed based on political factors, economic factors, legal factors, and competition. Thus, these classifications of entrepreneurial, enterprise and environmental factors helped in developing a model that is scrutinised to predict SMEs failure in the UK context.

Chapter three discuss and review the methodological approaches adopted in the present research. To begin with, paradigms of the research were elucidated, and the employed paradigm was further discussed and justified. Following this, the research approach, and data collection methods, were conversed and justified. In addition, the data analysis plan for the present research was explained for quantitative and qualitative data. In the end, research ethics and research consideration were explained in detail.

To begin with, paradigms of the research were elucidated, and the employed paradigm was further discussed and justified. In this study to achieve the aim and objective researchers employ as per Bryman and Bell (2011) the objectivistic approach as social entities occurs as an expressive reality and believe that there is an exterior lookout that can be used to view the organisation. The present research pursues to distinguish or assess a phenomenon of business failure factors, identifying the other common failure factors missing from the literature, and present recommendations to encourage SMEs supportable development and success in the UK fast food retail industry. The nature of these questions is confirmatory and explanatory therefore, it back the positivism paradigm. In the present study online, a self-administered questionnaire has been used to collect the data. These questionnaires were sent to the participants by internet and post.

Simple random sampling was adopted for the present research to generalize the findings and give an equal probability to the sampling frame to participate. The small and medium-size fast food businesses were selected randomly from the list obtained from The Gazette and Company House websites. The sample was selected based on different criteria. As the United Kingdom is very large and it's not possible to collect the data from different parts of the country due to limited time and resources. Therefore, data were collected from the small and medium-size fast

food businesses from London as it is the largest city in the UK with the highest number of SMEs and failure rates.

Another criterion of the sample was the age of the business which helps in measuring the performance of the business, business will be considered successful if trade for more than three years and failed if went bankrupt within three years (Arasti *et al.*, 2015; Pretorius, 2009). Furthermore, regarding the sampling frame, only those responses were considered valid which full fill the following criteria: SMEs which employees less than 250 employees, located in London, single business entity, deprived of any manufacturing ability, maintain an annual turnover below or up to £25.9 million or an annual balance sheet below or up to £12.9 million.

After following up 101 responses (4%) from successful entrepreneurs and 108 responses (8%) from failed entrepreneurs were collected. The researcher managed to collect a total of 209 responses in almost 8 months from potential respondents who met the criteria for this study as mentioned in a literature review. It took longer than the planned time to collect data due to the difficulties mentioned earlier. There were 15 respondents excluded from the study as they failed to complete the question regarding the status of the business. So, in total 209 responses were accepted for the analysis.

The duration to collect data for the main study took more than the planned time due to the pandemic. It took almost 6-8 months to collect data due to difficulties that occurred such as Covid 19, the absence of successful and failed SMEs list. A questionnaire developed on the Google form was sent by post and email to almost 4100 strong sampling frames of successful and failed entrepreneurs and any kind of physical contact was avoided due to pandemics. Finally, descriptive data analysis and inferential data analysis such as principal component analysis and logistic regression analysis were adopted to achieve the objective of the present research. Likewise, thematic analysis was used to find common themes in qualitative data.

Chapter four elaborated the findings of the research. This chapter contained four main analyses i.e., descriptive, principal component, logistic regression, and thematic analysis. These analyses helped in answering the research questions. The first part of the questionnaire discusses demographic characteristics of business owners and SMEs, analysed through descriptive analysis. Then to identify the correlation between variables and group them, exploratory factor analysis was utilized using principal component analysis for entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors (Pallant, 2011). Accordingly, three factors were developed from entrepreneurial factors, four factors from enterprise factors, and three factors

from environmental factors based on a theoretical framework presented in chapter two. In the end, logistic regression analysis was employed to test hypotheses and predict the research model, and identify the entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors associated with business failure in the UK fast food industry. The logistic regression analysis helped to develop a model to predict business failure.

The logistic regression analysis was utilized as the outcome variable was dichotomous success or failure (Austin and Merlo, 2017). The entrepreneurial factor was fragmented into factors related to the business owners such as gender, owners age, owners previous experience, owner education level, ownership type, poor personal traits, and the poor owner's skill. Then enterprise factors associated with business such as the size of the business, business planning, business location, marketing and management, and the employee's competencies. The third and last environmental factors consisted of the level of competition, inappropriate government policies, and poor economic factors. These three types of factors formed the independent variables (IVs) helped in predicting the SMEs failure. While the business failure is a dependent variable (DV). Businesses considered successful if they traded for more than three years and classified as failed if ceased to exist or went bankrupt within three years. Thus, the dependent variable (DV) was coded as failed (0) yes or (1) no.

The results of the logistic regression analysis indicated the influence of the number of factors on the likelihood of business success or failure. The result of the model covering the entire predictors variable was statistically significant which reflects the capability of the model to distinguish between respondents considered successful or failed. The model classified 70.3% of cases and elucidated the between 24.6% (Cox & Snell R Square) and 32.8% (Nagelkerke R Square) of the variance of business failure.

Nevertheless, the model has a better ability to predict the businesses that failed (at 71.3%) as compared to successful businesses that did not fail (69.3%). Logistic regression analysis helped to achieve the first three objectives. The result indicates that 7 independent variables are statistically significant to business failure with $p < 0.05$.

- Kind of Ownership (KO)
- Owners Experience (OE)
- Poor Owner Skills (POS)
- Business Planning (BP)
- Business Location (BL)

- Marketing and Management (MM)
- Intense Competition (IC)

Three open-ended questions were also added to the questionnaire to get a better understanding of the problems and suggest the solution for them based on participants' responses. To explore the most important failure, factor the respondents were asked to give their opinion and explain the reasons for choosing the intended failure factors. This question aimed to identify the most important factor which can influence the performance of a business, and the reason for their importance according to respondents. The views of the owners collected in the form of qualitative data assisted in understanding and resolving the research problem in the relevant industry. Thematic analysis in NVivo was used to analyse the data and organize it. The qualitative data were categorized and organized into common themes.

The results of the frequency analysis revealed that in total 142 respondents answered the first question out of which 72 respondents 51% suggested that enterprise factors have the most impact on the business failure in the UK fast food industry. The mostly respondent suggested that enterprise factors are controllable and can be used as a tool to manage the performance of a business. These factors can help in exploiting the opportunities and avoiding threats from the external environment. On the other hand, according to 31% of respondents environmental or external factors were the second most important factors to influence business failure. The respondents suggested that these factors cannot be controlled, and their impact is severe therefore, neglecting these factors can cause a business to fail in a very short period. Lastly, 19% suggest that entrepreneurial factors have a great impact on business failure. The respondent explained that in small businesses the owners are the ones who make all the decisions and their skills and experience play a crucial role in the performance of a business.

To explore the further failure factors the respondents were asked to give their opinion about common failure factors not included in this study. The respondents mentioned different failure factors based on their experience and observation. These factors were categorized and organized into common themes. Altogether, 8 factors linked to the business failure were revealed from the second open-ended question.

- Poor Customer Service and Product Quality
- Pandemic
- Poor Inventory Management
- Legal Issues

- Neglecting Home Delivery
- Supplier Issues
- Poor Use of Technology
- Neglecting Third-Party Applications

The poor customer service was a highly mentioned failure factor. Poor customer service and product quality can cause a business to fail as an angry customer would end up going to competitors. Nowadays, due to intense competition customers have more bargaining power and options therefore, poor customer service can affect business performance. Pandemic was the second most highlighted factor by the respondent. The pandemic is highlighted as one of the leading failure factors. Several businesses have been shut down due to pandemics. According to the respondent's absence of home delivery is another major failure factor in the UK fast food industry. After the pandemic, there is a change in consumer behaviour. Customers want to receive the food at home without leaving their houses. Therefore, the demand for delivery has gone up, and chances of business failure increase in absence of home delivery.

Another commonly effective failure factor revealed by participants was neglecting third-party applications such as UberEATS and Deliveroo. Third-party applications have changed the way fast food and restaurants used to operate. Third-party applications such as UberEATS act as an intermediary between the independent takeaway fast-food outlet and customers. These third-party companies receive the order from the customers and pass it on to takeaways or restaurants and charge them a commission fee. By partnering with these companies' small fast-food businesses can increase their sale and increase their reach to a bigger pool of customers without spending any money on marketing. Therefore, those fast-food SMEs are more likely to fail which does not use utilise these platforms.

Poor inventory management was mentioned as a crucial failure factor by several participants. New businesses cannot afford the losses due to limited resources and finance. However, when businesses order raw materials more than required and cannot sell within the time it expires and the business must incur losses. Therefore, poor inventory management can be a disaster for businesses. Legal factor is another emerged failure factor, and it has a major role in business performance. In a country like the UK legal factor is crucial in business survival. A change in the law can affect a business's performance sometimes making them go out of the market.

Similarly, suppliers' issues can also have a huge impact on the survival of a business. A business chain starts from suppliers therefore too dependent on a few suppliers could increase

their power which is not good for a business. The quality of products and services can be affected due to poor suppliers.

The third open-ended question helped to achieve the last objective which is to get recommendations from successful and failed entrepreneurs to avoid failure. The qualitative data about recommendations were presented and categorized by thematic analysis. Altogether, the respondents recommended emphasizing 16 tangible and intangible variables to avoid failure. Tangible variables are usually physical assets owned by a business such as location, products, and finance. On the other hand, intangible variables have monetary value and do not physical exist such as business planning, marketing, competition, human resource management legal compliance and offering different services. It is difficult to differentiate between tangible and intangible variables for instance it seems like employees are tangible assets as they are standing right there in a physical form while, businesses considers employees their valuable assets. It is not employees that are their assets rather its their skills. To recruit an employee company, evaluate their skills which meets the requirements of a business therefore, human resource is considered as intangible variable.

The successful and failed entrepreneurs recommended to gain some experience in a relevant field (intangible variable), develop a better business plan (intangible variable), utilise marketing, and advertisement (intangible variable), focus on high-quality products and services (tangible variable), select a prime location (tangible variable), emphasise on business growth strategies (intangible variable), have sufficient finance (tangible variable), focus on Inventory (tangible variable), focus on human resource management (intangible variable), offer home delivery services (intangible variable), emphasize on legal compliance (intangible variable), make better use of technology (tangible variable), partner with third-party applications (intangible variable) and manage competition effectively (intangible variable).

Chapter five discussed the research findings and compare the findings of the quantitative data with qualitative data findings and previous studies' findings in various contexts. It also discussed the main observation about the research.

6.3 Limitation of the Research

The present study has limitations as it is communal in any academic work. It is very important to discuss these limitations as they can influence the research findings. These limitations are explained in this section.

The first and most important limitation was the absence of SMEs financial data to evaluate the performance of the participating businesses such as turnover or profitability over a period, so it was not possible to measure the performance of SMEs based on financial indicators. Therefore, the performance of the business to be successful or failed was measured based on the business ability of trading during a certain period instead of objective measures. According to the definition employed in present research a business is considered failed if ceases to trade within the first three years and is considered successful if continued to trade for more than three years.

Even though there is adequate research available on business success and failure, however, there is an absence of a common definition of business success and failure. Similarly, the definition of SMEs varies according to different scholars in different contexts. So, it's very difficult to decide which definition of business success and failure can be used in this context. Therefore, the present study employed the definition of SMEs presented by the UK Companies Act of 2006 which is more suitable for this research.

In addition, there was no official list of successful and failed businesses therefore, the researcher had to compile a list of successful and failed businesses from different sources such as The Gazette, insolvency register, and company house. It was very challenging to compile a list of the fast-food businesses which fulfil the sampling criteria. The data file acquired from the Gazette, insolvency register, and company house was very large and unorganised. The researcher spent some time organising and filtering the data to separate the businesses that fulfil the sampling criteria. As the data was large and unorganised there is a possibility that some of the businesses (successful and failed) are missing from the list and the list does not represent the actual number of successful and failed businesses from London. All the businesses in the collected databases were discretely confirmed by the researcher to guarantee that they satisfy the conditions and requirements of the study.

This study is precise to one area of retail so, some factors may be more important in some other retail sectors. Focusing on one sector of retail makes the research limited and the failure factors

could vary in the other sectors of the retail industry. Therefore, this research emphasizes future research to research different sectors of retail and different industries to generalize the results.

Another important limitation is the geographical area. The present research focused on fast food businesses from London and so, the factors associated with the performance can be different in the other areas of the UK. It was not possible to access all the SMEs in the UK due to limited time and resources.

Furthermore, due to limited time and lack of resources, it was not possible to include all the failure factors found in the literature review. However, the research included an open-ended question investigating any other failure factors missing from this study to make sure the most relevant failure factors related to the fast-food industry could be identified. The recommendation also includes some factors identified through qualitative data. In the previous literature, there is not a single list of agreed factors that influence the performance of a business positively or negatively. Therefore, it was a difficult job to assemble a list of factors influencing business performance. To overcome this issue the researcher focused on factors that were backed by several authors and ignored the others. Although a rigorous literature review was performed, however, some factors may have not been included. Therefore, this study also utilized open-ended questions to identify any other failure factors missing from the literature. The factors identified through qualitative data can be tested in future research to generalise the results.

The researcher also acknowledges that there are numerous methodological limitations such as data collection method mainly depend on one method a questionnaire. The interviews with respondents could have helped to triangulate the findings. However, using more than one data collection method may cause sampling issues, reporting issues, and increase the time and resources required (barney, 2009).

One of the most important limitations of the present research is the fact that it's not possible to find out if the planned person (business owner) completed the questionnaire or whether it was answered by another colloquies or managers. Likewise, there is no way to find out the honesty of responses but then again must count on the goodwill of the participants.

6.4 Research Contribution

There are numerous critical failure factors (CFFs) found in business literature that tries to explain the different parts of small business failure. Though, the standing of these failure

factors available in the literature is questionable as the success and failure factors diverge from each industry and country. In other words, one failure factor may have an excessive significance in one industry however, the same factor may have no or less importance in another country or industry (Saleh, 2016; Lampadariou, 2016; Chemagility, 2008; Smallbone and Wyer, 2000; Rauch *et al.*, 2000; Alfaadhel, 2010; Lussier and Pfeifer, 2001; Ogundele, 2007). Therefore, it is obvious problem that gave clear direction to the present study. The success and failure factors of small businesses diverge from each industry and country. It urges further to conduct empirical research on each separate industry and in detailed country situations to examine the impact of previously known failure factors. Hence, it is essential to examine the failure factors in a precise industry and country to discover the critical failure factors related to that industry. In this regard, the present study focuses on the failure factors of one specific industry retail instead of focusing on all industries at the same time.

Even though several pieces of research related to SMEs can be found in the UK context, however, these studies emphasized more on success factors in different industries. On the other hand, the present study focuses on the failure factors of the UK fast food retail stores.

The literature review indicates that not a sole approved list has been developed to reveal the factors linked to SMEs performance. Therefore, the present research integrated and stretched the previous research work related to business performance and developed a model based on the perception of the UK fast food retail owners' which tend to offer new avenues to the research related to business failure factors in the UK market.

The measure of performance is another theoretical contribution present research adds to SMEs field in the UK fast food industry as different measures of performance can be employed to determine the business success or failure. There are different measures of performance such as increase in number of customers, customers satisfaction, increase in market share, achieving business goals etc. However, commonly used measure of performance is profit or loss. However, business owners are reluctant to share their financial information due to their competitive advantage. Therefore, the present research defines the measure of performance based on definition utilised by the other studies such as that of Pretorius (2009) who used different approach than financial measure of performance. in the present research trade duration has been used to measure the performance of a business instead of profit or loss as this definition better fit with research goal. So, the present definition can be utilized as an effective tool to measure business failure or performance in the UK context.

As mentioned in the literature review those factors associated with business success and failure vary therefore, the present research has contributed through selecting a group of factors related to the UK retail industry from different models and studies. This study has provided evidence about the interaction amongst entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors and their roles to predict SMEs failure from the UK context. The results of the logistic regression analysis revealed the capability of the model to predict business failure in the UK context and the association between factors and failure. Consequently, present research determines the most important factors related to performance and focuses on entrepreneurial, enterprise, and environmental factors.

The result of the logistic regression analysis shows that two entrepreneurial factors, owners' prior experience, and owners' poor skills are statistically significant to business failure and these two factors have the aptitude to predict the SMEs failure in the UK context. Similarly, the result identified four enterprise factors such as kind of ownership, strategic planning, location, and marketing & management statistically significant to business failure and capable to predict the SMEs failure in the UK context. The model also identified one environmental factor, competition statistically significant and can predict failure.

In the present research, the results of the (qualitative data) frequency analysis suggested that enterprise factors have the most impact on the business failure in the UK fast food industry. On the other hand, according to respondents environmental or external factors were the second most important factors and entrepreneurial factors have the least impact on business failure. This research has contributed to exploring the further failure factor missing from the literature. The qualitative data were categorized and organized into common themes. The respondents mentioned different failure factors based on their experience and observation. Altogether, 8 additional factors linked to the business failure were revealed from the second open-ended question. These factors include:

- Poor Customer Service and Product Quality
- Pandemic
- Poor Inventory Management
- Legal Issues
- Neglecting Home Delivery
- Supplier Issues
- Poor Use of Technology

- Neglecting-Party Applications

The present research is the first study that recommends identifying the major failure factors in the UK fast food industry. The literature suggests that most studies concluded on identifying the major performance-related factors. However, the present study after developing a business failure prediction model recommends how to overcome these challenges and become successful. These recommendations should serve as a framework that helps the new business to launch their business successfully in the UK retail industry. In addition, the model established based on regression analysis is fit to practice in the other retail sectors. The model can also help to identify the failure factors in other similar countries such as the EU and other developed countries which share the same values, culture, and economy.

Likewise, limited research can be found in the UK and Europe related to the SMEs failure therefore, the present study further adds the knowledge relevant to UK fast food retail industry and create a model to predict the SMEs failure.

Another contribution of the present research is the sample of the respondents as they belong to two unlike groups successful business owners and unsuccessful business owners. In the UK context, researchers have not included both sample groups in the one research. However, this research has adopted a different methodology and collected the data from successful business owners and failed business owners in the fast-food retail industry about business failure to compare their views and better understand the problem. Therefore, the sample supported in developing an inclusive opinion related to the business failure in the UK context.

The results of the present study can help policymakers to develop better policies to increase the chances of business success in the retail industry. As SMEs contribute heavily to the economy of any country, therefore, enhancing the SMEs success rate will help in reducing unemployment and improving the economy. Furthermore, the pandemic has been identified as one of the major factors through qualitative data analysis which caused many businesses to fail. Therefore, policymakers can make rules and policies that favour SMEs in achieving success during this hard time of the pandemic. The findings of the present study will further support the stakeholders such as the government, policymakers, entrepreneurs, business owners to develop a better strategy and enhance the decision-making process to improve the success rate or reduce business failure.

The model developed in present research can be used by government public policymakers and others to evaluate the business potential for success thus the society could utilise the limited resources to enhance the business potential. Overall, this research is expected to enhance the business failure knowledge, solve a problem and add further knowledge to literature related to SMEs failure, offer academic support for decision-makers, and present a common ground for academics to debate and examine factors vital for the SMEs failure in the fast-food retail industry. The present research contributes by identifying the factors linked to the SMEs performance and offers guidelines on how to enhance the chances of business success and avoid failure based on recommendations from successful and failed business owners.

6.5 Implications

Business failure can have a huge impact on the country's economy and successful SMEs are crucial for a stable economy. The present research findings can be utilized in the policy implications of SMEs.

These findings can assist the practitioners to minimize the chances of failure and increase the success rate by examining the factors that contribute to business failure. The failure factors have been classified in entrepreneurial, enterprise and environmental factors and this classification can help the business owners to comprehend the significance of each type of factor in business performance. The present research also highlighted that out of three which type of factors has the most impact on business failure.

The research findings offer a model that helps retail business owners to distinguish the factors and assist in reducing business failure by focusing on these identified factors in the UK context. In this model one of the significant factors in business failure is business planning and it suggests that enhanced strategic planning can help a business to succeed. Consequently, in practice business owners should conduct market research and develop a strategic plan before starting a business. Planning should be a continuous process and according to situations and challenges the new plans can take place.

The model also raised awareness about the experience factor in business performance. The model highlighted those owners need to gain some relevant experience before starting a business. It is evident that as the experience increases the chances of business failure decrease. The experience offers awareness to the entrepreneurs about management, suppliers, industry situation, daily tasks, and other business elements which play a crucial role in success.

Furthermore, owners should emphasize more on their skills as it can benefit business owners in improving business performance. Networking skill plays a significant role in the success of a new business as it provides market knowledge, expertise, marketing skills, managerial skills, information related to opportunities and threats from competitors. Entrepreneurs become part of a big social network that assists them in achieving different opportunities. Sometimes entrepreneurs recognize an opportunity in the business environment however, due to the absence of social skills, fail to exploit the opportunity and start a business. Therefore, owners should work on their skills and try to enhance them.

Another important factor in the logit model is the location which is considered a vital factor in the performance of a business. The survival of a venture depends on the presence of an ideal business location. The location gives an edge to the business by driving customers into the shop without any marketing and advertisement efforts. The location also offers convenience to the customers as there are empirical pieces of evidence that suggest that customers prefer to buy from a shop more convenient to them. The market size is large in densely populated areas and it helps the business to attract more customers. Even though, all the big brands from different industries prefer to open their outlets at a busy high street. Therefore, business owners need to focus on the location factor and select a prime location to avoid the risk of failure. Along with location marketing and management is another important factor that requires business owners' attention. Marketing and advertisement help a business to attract new customers. Marketing creates awareness among customers and helps a business to build a strong brand. Similarly managing the business operation effectively helps a business to grow. Therefore, business owners need to focus on marketing and management to attract new customers, build a strong brand and manage the operation smoothly to reduce the chances of failure.

In addition, the present research also emphasizes environmental factors such as competition. Competition plays an important role in the performance of a business. Therefore, owners need to emphasize competition and develop strategies to tackle it. Business owners can be innovative and creative to avoid competition. In these regards marketing, product quality, and pricing can help a business to tackle competition.

Similarly, qualitative data also support the quantitative findings and helped in identifying some further factors which need owners' attention not included in the model. The new business owners need to focus on customer service and product quality as it helps a business to add value to the customers. The owners can also manage inventory effectively to avoid losses and

increase their profit. The owners have to be aware of all the legal requirements as a violation of legal factors can cause a business to go out of the market. Furthermore, in recent days the demand for home delivery has gone high therefore, new business owners can utilize the home delivery option to reach more customers and increase their sales. Similarly, the use of third-party applications such as Deliveroo, Uber Eats, and Just Eat can also help businesses to increase their customers and offer their products to a completely new audience. The technology can also help businesses to run their daily task effectively, enhance customer service and product quality, aid productivity, and tackle competition.

Any supply chain in business starts with suppliers therefore, new businesses need to select good suppliers and keep a good relationship with them as suppliers can influence the product quality. Lastly, quantitative, and qualitative data results suggest that partnership is another major issue that requires consideration. Along with several benefits of partnership, it also carried numerous problems. Partnership causes many problems such as the conflict in decision making, lack of control over the business, and lack of trust. Therefore, business owners need to address these issues before they decide to start a business in partnership.

6.6 Future Research

The present research opens new avenues for further research. Firstly, in the present research, the failure factors recognition is based on the perception of successful and failed entrepreneurs (non-financial measure) therefore, in the future, a study based on financial measures can be conducted. Once the financial data become available it can be useful to utilize growth indicators such as turnover increase, or profitability to conduct similar research.

Although, the present study recognises the failure factors for SMEs in one specific industry it would be of great value to investigate the mechanic of each failure factor individually and in-depth to generate robust results. The present research used open-ended questions to better understand the problem and identified a few new failure factors associated with the fast-food industry based on thematic analysis. Future research is recommended with the use of more advanced qualitative methods that could produce richer data and provide comprehensive results. Pandemic is one of the factors identified through thematic analysis and it needs to be investigated in future research as many business owners successful and failed mentioned pandemic as one of the most important factors causing businesses to shut down. As a result of the pandemic, several legal changes occurred such as the business running hours being

changed, any physical contact prohibited, and instore orders being forbidden. Thus, the pandemic effect on business survival needs to be investigated in future research.

Furthermore, as the failure factors vary in different industries it's important to conduct further research in different industries and countries to better understand the factors impacting each industry. Similar studies can be conducted to identify whether there are any differences in critical failure factors conducted in different countries and industries. It will also help to test the model in different industries and geographical settings, to further examine the predictor variables and get more robust results. Similarly, conducting the research based on comparing the failure factors in different industries and countries would be of great interest.

Another contribution is the identification of certain factors such as a pandemic, free home delivery, and third-party applications which influence the performance of the SMEs in the UK context therefore, future studies can be focused on each factor using different approaches in further detail. Further studies can be conducted to identify the impact of each factor on the performance of SMEs and how these factors influence their performance. In addition, the researchers can focus on finding the solutions to reduce the impact of these factors on the negative performance of businesses.

A future investigation can be conducted with a more in-depth analysis of SMEs success factors in one specific industry in the UK. Similarly, the definition of small business failure can be further explored to ensure a uniformity of opinion on business failure definition to eliminate any methodological weaknesses. The future research can be based on exploring business success and failure definition according to industry experts and business owners in this industry.

The data collection in the context of SMEs is a difficult and lengthy process. Researchers have to consume time and resources to get the list of SMEs because in most countries the data related to SMEs is not available. Apart from that, it's a difficult task to find the business owners who failed or went bankrupt. Further studies can be conducted in case of any official list of SMEs is available or there is a systematic way to collect the data. Furthermore, it's hard to approach the business owners, therefore, managers or people working in managerial positions can be included in the study to make the data collection process easier. People with managerial experience can have a lot of related information about factors that influence business performance.

Lastly, the factors that influence business performance can vary in developing and developed countries. There are cultural differences among developing and developed countries therefore, further research from developing countries can be very useful to understand the problem. Apart from culture, there are other important differences among developing and developed countries such as physical infrastructure and access to capital therefore, it's important to consider differences between the contexts.

6.7 Summary

The research process was presented at the beginning of this chapter and offered a brief explanation of key measures carried out at each stage along with the main outcomes of each chapter. Then research limitations were discussed in detail. Theoretical contribution for the present research was discussed followed by suggestions for future research opportunities.

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Appendices

Appendix (1): Conceptualisation and Operationalisation

The Entrepreneurial Factors			
	Conceptualisation	Operationalisation	Items of Construct
Owner			
Gender	Shows understanding of how owner gender could predict SMEs failure.	The construct was measured by one question and practiced as classificatory.	Q1
Age	Demonstrate how owner age could predict SMEs failure.	Measured with one question and practiced as classificatory.	Q2
Education	Assist to understand how owner qualification could predict SMEs failure.	Measured with one question and practiced as classificatory.	Q3
Experience	The construct demonstrate how experience could predict the SMEs failure.	The measurement of scale was consisted of 3 items designed in a 5-point Likert scale	Q11, Q12, Q13
Personal Traits	The construct shows how traits could guess the SMEs failure.	The measurement of scale was consisted of 3 items designed in a 5-point Likert scale	Q14, Q15, Q16
Skills	The construct reflects how skills could predict the SMEs failure.	The measurement of scale was consisted of 3 items designed in a 5-point Likert scale	Q17, Q18, Q19
Enterprise Factors			
Enterprise			
Size of Business	Illustrate how owner age could predict SMEs failure.	The construct was measured by one question and practiced as classificatory.	Q7
Kind of Ownership	Demonstrate how owner age could predict SMEs failure.	The construct was measured by one question and practiced as classificatory.	Q8
Strategic Planning	The construct demonstrate how strategic planning	The measurement of scale was consisted of 3 items designed	Q20, Q21, Q22

Strategic Planning	The construct demonstrate how strategic planning could predict the SMEs failure.	The measurement of scale was consisted of 3 items designed in a 5-point Likert scale.	Q20, Q21, Q22
Location	The construct reflects how location could predict the SMEs failure.	The measurement of scale was consisted of 3 items designed in a 5-point Likert scale.	Q23, Q24, Q25
Marketing and Management	The construct reflects how marketing and management could predict the SMEs failure.	The measurement of scale was consisted of 6 items designed in a 5-point Likert scale	Q26, Q27, Q28, Q29, Q30, Q31
Employees Competency	The construct shows how employees' competency could predict the SMEs failure.	The measurement of scale was consisted of 3 items designed in a 5-point Likert scale.	Q32, Q33, Q34
Environmental Factors			
External Factors			
Political	The construct shows how political factors could predict the SMEs failure.	The measurement of scale was consisted of 3 items designed in a 5-point Likert scale.	Q35, Q36, Q37
Economic	The construct shows how economic factors could predict the SMEs failure.	The measurement of scale was consisted of 3 items designed in a 5-point Likert scale.	Q38, Q39, Q40
Competition	The construct shows how competition could predict the SMEs failure.	The measurement of scale was consisted of 3 items designed in a 5-point Likert scale.	Q41, Q42, Q43

Appendix (2) Questionnaire

Developing a Model to Predict Critical Failure Factors of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises:

An Empirical Study of the UK Fast Food Retail Industry.

Participant Information Sheet

Title of Study: Developing a Model to Predict Critical Failure Factors of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises: An Empirical Study of the UK Fast Food Retail Industry.

Principal Investigator: Muhammad Ilyas

Introduction: You are kindly invited to participate in this research. Please take time to read the following information carefully to decide whether or not you wish to participate.

Background

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) contribute in accelerating economic development, jobs creation, development, and strengthening economies in developing and developed countries. Yet, regardless of the country and industry, SMEs face similar impediments that influence their performance and survival rate. Literature suggests that SMEs face a high failure rate all over the world.

Similarly, Start-up survival rate in London is very underprivileged, only 50.1% businesses could survive for first three years which is 3.6% lower than national average. SMEs have strong presence in UK fast food retail industry therefore, identifying the failure factor in the specific industry becomes of significant importance. Even though extensive literature is available on small business failure and several failure factors has been identified while, critical failure factors for SMEs depend upon and vary with the industry and country they operate in; which means if one factor is important in business failure in one industry it may not be of equally important in another industry. Therefore, these critical failure factors need to be tested and validated for each industry in a specific country. In the case of present research, the focus is on UK fast food Industry. Furthermore, in this study viewpoint of successful and failed businesses about start up failure will be compared to better understand the problem and make recommendation how to avoid or minimize failure.

Purpose of the Study

This research aims to identify the main causes of early-stage failure factors in the UK fast food retail stores and propose a framework or recommendation to reduce the failure. The

original and significant contribution of this thesis would be the identification of the factors critical to the failure of UK fast food SMEs, propose a framework to reduce it and make recommendation to avoid failure. The recommendation of research will assist both small businesses entering the market and existing businesses struggling to improve performance. Please note that for the purpose of this study, businesses filed the bankruptcy within first three years of operations are considered as failed businesses while the other still running operation for more than three years are considered successful. Participants are kindly requested to adhere to this study's definition of success and failure when responding to the questionnaire.

Procedure

The volunteer participants have to join a survey and several open and closed ended questions will be asked to describe the failure factors in business. There is no right or wrong you can choose answers closer to reality. It will take 15-20 minutes to complete the survey. This survey can be taken at or away from your place of work.

Possible Risks or Benefits

The present research aims to help the fast-food retail industry and people involved in it directly or indirectly. The information gained from this study will be used to identify the failure factors in UK fast food industry and to avoid failure.

Participation and Withdrawal

Taking part in this study is entirely voluntary and refusal and withdrawal will involve no penalty or loss at any time. Upon request of withdrawal all information obtained from you will be destroyed. You may also choose to refuse the answer while still participating in survey. This study has obtained clearance from University of Scotland research ethic committee.

Anonymity and Privacy

Any information obtained during this study will be kept strictly confidential. Every effort will be made to ensure confidently, and no individual name will be used to protect personal belief. All efforts will be made to keep you name and identity confidential during this study. all data will be identified only through a code with personal details kept in locked file with access only by researcher. After the completion of this study all the data will be destroyed. The data obtained may be published in journal or conference paper however, the researcher will make sure to keep your name and identity confidential.

Voluntary Consent Form

The researcher requests your consent for participation in a study about business failure factors in the UK fast food retail industry. This consent form asks you to allow the researcher to record and view the questionnaire and to use your comments to enhance understanding of the topic.

Participation in this study is completely voluntary. If you decide not to participate there will not be any negative consequences. Please be aware that if you decide to participate, you may stop participating at any time and you may decide not to answer any specific question.

The researcher will maintain the confidentiality of the research records or data, and all data will be destroyed after completing this research.

By submitting this survey, you are consenting to participate in this study.

Available Source of Information

In the case of any further questions or enquiries, please don't hesitate to contact me on details mentioned below:

Part 1: This part contains the questions related to yourself and your business, please select the option that matches your view most closely.

Q1: What is your gender?

- (a) Male
- (b) Female
- (c) Other

Q2: What is your age group?

- (a) 18-24
- (b) 25-34
- (c) 45-54
- (d) 55+

Q3: What is the highest level of education you have achieved?

- (a) No Education
- (b) Primary Education Certificate
- (c) GCSEs
- (d) A-Levels
- (e) Diploma
- (f) Bachelor's Degree
- (g) Master's Degree
- (h) PhD
- (i) Professional Qualification

Q4: Did you have any experience before starting a business?

- (a) No Experience**
- (b) Owned a Business**
- (c) Government/Public Sector**
- (d) Fast food related/ Managerial**
- (e) Other**

Q5: Please indicate the total duration of the business trade?

- (a) Less than 1 years**
- (b) Between 1 and 2 years**
- (c) Between 2 and 3 years**
- (d) More than 3 years**

Q6: Please Indicate the annual turnover of your business?

- (a) Less than £2 million**
- (b) £2 million- £6 million**
- (c) £6 million- £25.9 million**
- (d) More than £25.9 million**

Q7: Please, mention the total number of employees in your business?

- (a) Less than 5**
- (b) 6-10**
- (c) 11-50**
- (d) 51-250**
- (e) More than 250**

Q8: What is your position in your organization?

- (a) Owner**
- (b) CEO**
- (c) Senior Manager**
- (d) Other**

Q9: Is your business still operating in the UK market?

- (a) Yes**

(a) No

Q10: Where is your business located in the UK?

(a) London

(b) North West England

(c) North East England

(d) Midlands

(e) South West England

(f) South East England

(g) Scotland

(h) Wales

Part 2: Entrepreneurial Factors

For each of the following items please indicate the significance of the following entrepreneurial factors in the failure of SMEs in the UK Fast Food retail industry. Please circle () the box that matches your view most closely.

		Not Important at all	Unimportant	Neutral	Important	Very Important
		1	2	3	4	5
Q11	Prior Work Experience	1	2	3	4	5
Q12	Industry Experience	1	2	3	4	5
Q13	Entrepreneurial Experience	1	2	3	4	5
Q14	Lack of Need for Achievement	1	2	3	4	5

Q15	Lack of locus of control	1	2	3	4	5
Q16	Lack of Motivation for Continuation of Job	1	2	3	4	5
Q17	Poor Marketing Skills	1	2	3	4	5
Q18	Poor Networking Skills	1	2	3	4	5
Q19	Poor Management Skills	1	2	3	4	5

Enterprise Factors

For each of the following items Please indicate the significance of the following enterprise factors in the failure of SMEs in the UK Fast Food retail industry. Please circle () the box that matches your view most closely.

		Not Important at all	Unimportant	Neutral	Important	Very Important
		1	2	3	4	5
Q20	Business Plan	1	2	3	4	5
Q21	Alternative Business Plan to overcome Emergency Changes	1	2	3	4	5
Q22	Clear Direction to Run Business	1	2	3	4	5
Q23	Location with high Footfall	1	2	3	4	5
Q24	Location Suitable for Business	1	2	3	4	5

Q25	Prime Location	1	2	3	4	5
Q26	Traditional Marketing and Advertisement	1	2	3	4	5
Q27	Advertisement through Internet	1	2	3	4	5
Q28	Social Media marketing	1	2	3	4	5
Q29	Effective Management	1	2	3	4	5
Q30	Knowledge of Managerial Tasks	1	2	3	4	5
Q31	Good Control	1	2	3	4	5
Q31	Motivated Staff	1	2	3	4	5
Q32	Skilled Staff	1	2	3	4	5
Q33	Staff Retention	1	2	3	4	5

Business Environment Factors

For each of the following items Please indicate the significance of the following environmental (external) factors in the failure of SMEs in the UK Fast Food retail industry. Please circle () the box that matches your view most closely.

		Not Important at all	Unimportant	Neutral	Important	Very Important
		1	2	3	4	5
Q:34	Poor Government Policies	1	2	3	4	5
Q:35	Lack of Government Support to Entrepreneur	1	2	3	4	5
Q:36	High Government Taxes	1	2	3	4	5
Q:37	Unstable Economic Environment	1	2	3	4	5
Q:38	High Interest Rate	1	2	3	4	5
Q:39	Poor Economic Growth	1	2	3	4	5
Q:40	Intense Competition	1	2	3	4	5
Q:41	International competitors and high quality of their products	1	2	3	4	5
Q:42	No product differentiation	1	2	3	4	5

Part 3

Q 43: From the entrepreneurial, enterprise and environmental factors, which one do you consider to be the most important to failure of SMEs in the UK Fast Food industry?

Please explain why?

Q 44: What reasons other than mentioned in this study do you think could contribute to the demise of businesses in the Fast-Food Industry?

Q45: What are your recommendations to avoid failure for the UK Fast Food retail stores?

Appendix (3): Exploratory Factors Analysis for Entrepreneurial Factors

The Loading Score for Entrepreneurial Factors

	Component		
	1	2	3
Poor Prior Work Experience	.999		
Inadequate Experience	.992		
Poor Industry Experience	.996		
Lack of Need for Achievement		.984	
Lack of Locus of Control		.991	
Lack of Motivation for Continuation of Job		.989	
Poor Marketing Skills			.973
Poor Networking Skills			.990

Appendix (4): Exploratory Factors Analysis for Enterprise Factors

The Loading Score for Entrepreneurial Factors

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Poor Business Plan		.981		
No emergency plan to overcome		.987		
Unclear Direction to Run Business		.986		
Location with Less Footfall				.990
Bad Location				.993
Location Unsuitable for Business				.990
Poor Advertisement and Promotion	.872			

Lack of Advertisement through Internet	.860			
Poor Social Media marketing	.933			
Poor Management	.933			
Lack of Knowledge of Managerial Tasks	.909			
Lack of Control	.907			
Lack of Motivated Staff			.991	
Lack of Skilled Staff			.993	
High Staff Turnover			.982	

Appendix (5): Exploratory Factors Analysis for Environmental Factors

The Loading Score for Entrepreneurial Factors

	Component		
	1	2	3
Poor Government Policies			.978
High Government Taxes			.951
Lack of Government Support to Entrepreneur			.962
High Interest Rate	.964		
Poor Economic Growth	.995		
Unstable Economic Environment	.997		
Intense Competition		.996	
International Competitors and High Quality of their Products		.995	
No Product Differentiation		.984	

Appendix (6): Logistic Regression Analysis

Factors	B	Sig	Exp (B)	95% for EXP (B)	
				Lower	Upper
Gender (male=1, female= 2)	0.80	0.885	1.083	0.336	3.205
Age (18-24= 1, 25-34= 2, 35-44= 3, 45-54= 4, 55+= 5)	-0.134	0.460	1.631	0.801	1.631
Education Level of Owners (No Education=1, Primary Education Certificate=2, GCSEs or Equivalent=3, A-Levels or Equivalent= 4, Diploma=5, Bachelor's Degree=6, Master's Degree=7, PhD=8, Professional Qualifications=9)	-0.112	0.175	0.894	0.760	1.051
Size of Business (Less than 5=1, 6-10=2, 11-50=3, 51-250=4, More than 250=5)	-0.254	0.297	0.776	0.481	1.250
Kind of Ownership (Sole Owner=1, Manager=2, Business Partnership=3, Other=4)	0.462	0.011	1.587	1.110	2.270
Owners Experience (Likert Scale:1= Very Unimportant, 5= very important)	-0.515	0.010	0.598	0.405	0.883
Poor Personal Traits (Likert Scale:1= Very Unimportant, 5= very important)	0.100	0.522	1.105	0.813	1.502
Poor Owner Skills (Likert Scale:1= Very Unimportant, 5= very important)	0.506	0.006	1.658	1.152	2.387
Business Planning (Likert Scale:1= Very Unimportant, 5= very important)	-0.531	0.015	0.588	0.383	0.903
Business Location (Likert Scale:1= Very Unimportant, 5= very important)	-0.346	0.051	0.708	0.494	1.013
Marketing and Management (Likert Scale:1= Very Unimportant, 5= very important)	-0.547	0.030	0.579	0.353	0.949
Employees Competency (Likert Scale:1= Very Unimportant, 5= very important)	-0.283	0.219	0.754	0.480	1.183
Economic Policies (Likert Scale:1= Very Unimportant, 5= very important)	0.293	0.237	1.340	0.825	2.179

Political Policies (Likert Scale:1= Very Unimportant, 5= very important)	-0.066	0.696	0.937	0.674	1.301
Intense Competition (Likert Scale:1= Very Unimportant, 5= very important)	-0.418	0.013	0.659	0.474	0.915
Constant	6.961	.000	758		
Model Test Results					
-2 Log Likelihood	230.5				
Model Chi-square	59.0				
Model Significant	0.00				
Cox & Snell R Square	0.246				
Nagelkerke R Square	0.328				
Hosmer and Lemeshow Test Significant	0.717				
Classification Results					
Failed (No) Successful	69.3%				
Failed (Yes) Unsuccessful	71.3%				
Overall Percentage	70.3%				

Appendix (7): Multicollinearity

		Owner Experience	Inappropriate Personal traits	Poor Owner Skills	Business Planning	Business Location	Marketing and Management	Employees Competency	Political Factors	Economic Factors	Competition
Owner Experience	Pearson Correlation	1	.246	.250	.062	.067	.220	.278	-.100	.117	.103
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.376	.334	.001	.000	.149	.093	.139
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
Inappropriate Personal traits	Correlation Coefficient	.246	1	.229	.145	.178	.111	.104	.141	.007	.020
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.001	.036	.010	.110	.133	.042	.924	.771
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
Poor Owner Skills	Correlation Coefficient	.250	.229	1	-.078	.106	.050	.029	.029	-.047	.052
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.001		.262	.128	.468	.672	.679	.502	.454
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
Business Planning	Correlation Coefficient	.062	.145	-.078	1	.135	.025	.068	-.041	.037	.022
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.376	.036	.262		.052	.718	.325	.555	.598	.748
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
Business Location	Correlation Coefficient	.067	.178	.106	.135	1	.344	.031	.669	.100	.076

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.334	.010	.128	.052		.000	.654	.000	.150	.277
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
Marketing and Management	Correlation Coefficient	.220	.111	.050	.025	.344	1	.162	.277	.031	-.033
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.110	.468	.718	.000		.019	.000	.659	.640
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
Employees Competency	Correlation Coefficient	.278	.104	.029	.068	.031	.162	1	.022	.050	.098
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.133	.672	.325	.654	.019		.755	.472	.158
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
Political Factors	Correlation Coefficient	-.100	.141	.029	-.041	.669	.277	.022	1	.162	.108
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.149	.042	.679	.555	.000	.000	.755		.019	.118
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
Economic Factors	Correlation Coefficient	.117	.007	-.047	.037	.100	.031	.050	.162	1	.409
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.093	.924	.502	.598	.150	.659	.472	.019		.000
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209
Intensity of Competition	Correlation Coefficient	.103	.020	.052	.022	.076	-.033	.098	.108	.409	1
	Sig. (2-	.139	.771	.454	.748	.277	.640	.158	.118	.000	

	tailed)										
	N	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). **

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). *

Appendix (7a): The Variance Inflation Factor

		Coefficients		Collinearity Statistics	
		95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Tolerance	VIF
Model		Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
1	(Constant)	2.325	3.736		
	OE	-.152	.012	.749	1.335
	PPT	-.037	.085	.858	1.165
	PES	.017	.159	.875	1.143
	BP	-.181	-.015	.911	1.097
	BL	-.190	-.003	.486	2.059
	MM	-.197	-.013	.813	1.231
	EC	-.143	.026	.898	1.114
	PF	-.043	.156	.487	2.054
	EF	-.097	.039	.799	1.252
	IC	-.137	.004	.812	1.231

a. Dependent Variable: Business Failure